

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Cubic Function

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Abstract

*This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10.000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using **cubic function** along with basic operations. Previously, the author also worked [7]-[27] with numbers up to 300.000 using only basic operations along with **square-root, factorial**, etc. For more details refer author's work in reference list. Similar kind of work is given with **Triangular numbers** [40], **Fibonacci sequence values** [?] and **square function** [?]. This kind of work using **cubic function** is never seen before in the literature. It is done for the first time here.*

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers	2
1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing	2
2 Triangular Numbers and Fibonacci Numbers	2
2.1 Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Values	3
2.2 Selfie Numbers: Palindromic-Type	3
2.3 Selfie Numbers: Symmetric Representations	4
2.4 Selfie Numbers: General Representations	5
3 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Cubic Function	6

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1 Introduction

First we shall give some different ways of representing natural numbers using the digits 0 to 9 or 1 to 9. See the subsections below

1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are* represented in three different types.

1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [7] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{101} &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{102} &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{103} &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\ \mathbf{104} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{105} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{106} &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{107} &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ \mathbf{108} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1. \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{786} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{999} &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\ \mathbf{2535} &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{2607} &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\ \mathbf{10483} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{10549} &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\ \mathbf{10550} &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\ \mathbf{10553} &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\ \mathbf{10554} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{11807} &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1. \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer [7]-[27]. These works brings the representations of natural numbers from 1 to 300.000. Soon, we shall extend it to half-milion, i.e., 500.000.

2 Triangular Numbers and Fibonacci Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics [?]. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**" as seen in subsection ??.

In this paper our aim is to bring **selfie numbers** by used of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections. Due to high quantity of numbers, we restricted our work up to four digits, i.e., from 1 to 9999. There are different ways of calling these numbers, such as, **tri-gonal**, **triangular** or **triangle selfie numbers**. For simplicity, we shall call them as **triangular selfie numbers**.

2.1 Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Values

Below are few examples of natural numbers written in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular number** values.

1 := $F(2)$	1 := $T(1)$	22 := $F(2) + F(8)$	22 := $T(1) + T(6)$
2 := $F(3)$		23 := $F(3) + F(8)$	
3 := $F(4)$	3 := $T(2)$	24 := $F(4) + F(8)$	24 := $T(2) + T(6)$
4 := $F(2) + F(4)$	4 := $T(1) + T(2)$	25 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(8)$	25 := $T(4) + T(5)$
5 := $F(5)$		26 := $F(5) + F(8)$	26 := $T(1) + T(4) + T(5)$
6 := $F(2) + F(5)$	6 := $T(3)$	27 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(8)$	27 := $T(3) + T(6)$
7 := $F(3) + F(5)$	7 := $T(1) + T(3)$	28 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(8)$	28 := $T(7)$
8 := $F(6)$		29 := $F(6) + F(8)$	29 := $T(1) + T(7)$
9 := $F(2) + F(6)$	9 := $T(2) + T(3)$	30 := $F(2) + F(6) + F(8)$	30 := $T(2) + T(3) + T(6)$
10 := $F(3) + F(6)$	10 := $T(4)$	31 := $F(3) + F(6) + F(8)$	31 := $T(2) + T(7)$
11 := $F(4) + F(6)$	11 := $T(1) + T(4)$	32 := $F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	32 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(7)$
12 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6)$		33 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	
13 := $F(7)$	13 := $T(2) + T(4)$	34 := $F(9)$	34 := $T(3) + T(7)$
14 := $F(2) + F(7)$	14 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(4)$	35 := $F(2) + F(9)$	35 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(7)$
15 := $F(3) + F(7)$	15 := $T(5)$	36 := $F(3) + F(9)$	36 := $T(8)$
16 := $F(4) + F(7)$	16 := $T(1) + T(5)$	37 := $F(4) + F(9)$	37 := $T(1) + T(8)$
17 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(7)$	17 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(4)$	38 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(9)$	38 := $T(4) + T(7)$
18 := $F(5) + F(7)$	18 := $T(2) + T(5)$	39 := $F(5) + F(9)$	39 := $T(2) + T(8)$
19 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(7)$	19 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(5)$	40 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(9)$	40 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(8)$
20 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(7)$			
21 := $F(8)$	21 := $T(6)$		

For more details refer author's work [35].

2.2 Selfie Numbers: Palindromic-Type

This section brings *selfie palindromic numbers* by use of triangular numbers. The idea of starting the work with palindromic numbers is as they are symmetric in itself, i.e., remains the same by changing the order of digits. Below are *selfie palindromic numbers*:

$$66 := T(T(T(6)))/T(6)$$

$$171 := T(17+1)$$

$$222 := T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2))$$

$$232 := -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2)$$

$$242 := T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$252 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2$$

$$525 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5$$

$$666 := T(-6 + T(6) + T(6))$$

$$696 := T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6))$$

$$777 := T(7) \times T(7) - 7$$

$$969 := T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9)$$

$$2222 := (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))$$

$$2332 := T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$2442 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2)$$

$$2552 := (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2)$$

$$2662 := 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)}$$

$$2772 := -T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$$

$$3003 := T(T(T(T(3))))/003$$

$$3333 := T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$$

$$3773 := T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3)$$

$$3993 := -T(3 \times 9) + T(93)$$

$$4224 := T(42) + T(T(2)^4)$$

$$4334 := T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))$$

$$4884 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4$$

$$5445 := T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5)$$

$$5665 := T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5$$

$$5775 := T(5) \times 77 \times 5$$

$$5995 := 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5)$$

$$6336 := (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6$$

$$9339 := T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9))$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.3 Selfie Numbers: Symmetric Representations

In this section, we shall give **selfie numbers** in terms of **triangular numbers** along with basic operations. These representations are in symmetric way, i.e., all is same except the digits 0 to 9. This happens in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits. In some cases numbers can written in both the ways. Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order and its reverse:

$$120 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$121 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$122 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$123 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$124 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$125 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$126 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$127 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$128 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$129 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$210 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 0 = 0 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$211 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 1 = 1 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$212 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 2 = 2 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$213 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 3 = 3 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$214 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 4 = 4 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$215 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 5 = 5 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$216 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 6 = 6 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$217 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 7 = 7 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$218 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 8 = 8 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$219 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 9 = 9 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$990 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 0 = 0 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$991 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 1 = 1 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$992 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 2 = 2 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$993 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 = 3 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$994 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 4 = 4 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$995 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5 = 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$996 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 = 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$997 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 7 = 7 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$998 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 8 = 8 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$999 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 9 = 9 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.4 Selfie Numbers: General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= T(1 \times 5) \\ &:= T(5) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21 &:= T(T(1+2)) \\ &:= T(T(2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(3)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= T(T(2)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= T(3) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39 &:= -T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45 &:= T(4+5) \\ &:= T(5+4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49 &:= 4 + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55 &:= T(5+5) \\ &:= T(5+5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63 &:= T(6) \times 3 \\ &:= 3 \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= T(-1 + T(05)) \\ &:= T(T(5) - 01) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T((T(3) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 136 &:= T(T(1+3)) + 6 \\ &:= T(6 + T(3+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147 &:= T(T(-1+4)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(4-1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 152 &:= -1 + T(T(5) + 2) \\ &:= T(2 + T(5)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 154 &:= T(T(T(-1+5)))/T(4) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(5-1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 167 &:= -1 + 6 \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times 6 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168 &:= 1 \times T(6) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 176 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \\ &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 185 &:= (1 + T(8)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(8) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 186 &:= -T(1+8) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - T(8+1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 221 &:= -T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$223 := -2^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) - 2^{T(2)}$$

$$:= T(7) + T(54 \times 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2) - 4 \\ &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1462 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(6) - 2 \\ &:= -T(2 \times 6) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225 &:= T(2 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (5 \times T(2))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1463 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(6 + T(3)) \\ &:= -T(T(3) + 6) + T(T(T(4))) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 226 &:= -2 - T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - 2 - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1464 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1446 &:= T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) \\ &:= (T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1472 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2)) \\ &:= -T(T(2)) - 7 + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1447 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1474 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - 4 \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(4) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1448 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\ &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1479 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 + 9)) \\ &:= -T(T(9 - 7)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1449 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9 \\ &:= -T(9 + 4) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1482 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(2)) + T(8) \times 41 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1455 &:= T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5)) \\ &:= -T(5) - T(5) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1483 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 8 + T(3) \\ &:= -T(T(3)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1456 &:= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1484 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$1457 := T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7)$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [37].

3 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Cubic Function

In this work we have written natural numbers from 0 to 10000 in terms of increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 by use of **cubic function** along with basic operations. In [39, 40, 41], the author wrote numbers from 0 to 10000 using **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers** and **square function** respectively. Here we have done it by using **cubic function**. Not all the numbers are possible with **cubic function**. These are given without use of **cubic function**. Moreover, in the results below there are extra brackets. These can be easily removed by simple calculations. To be more clear, below is a definition of **cubic function**:

$$C(n) = n^3, n \geq 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{0} &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{0} &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1} &:= (-1 + 2)^{3456789} & \mathbf{1} &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 - 6)^{54321} \\
\mathbf{2} &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{2} &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{3} &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{3} &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{4} &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{4} &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) / 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{5} &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{5} &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7)^6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{6} &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{6} &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{7} &:= ((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) / (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{7} &:= 9 - \sqrt{C(8) - 7 - C(6)} + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{8} &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{8} &:= 9 - (8 - 7)^{654321} \\
\mathbf{9} &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{9} &:= 9 \times (8 - 7)^{654321} \\
\mathbf{10} &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{10} &:= 9 + (8 - 7)^{654321} \\
\mathbf{11} &:= 1 - 2 - C(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{11} &:= (9 + C(8) + 7) / (6! / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{12} &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{12} &:= (9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13} &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{13} &:= (-9 + \sqrt{C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)}) \\
\mathbf{14} &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{14} &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{15} &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{15} &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{16} &:= 1 + 2 \times C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{16} &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) / 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{17} &:= (1 - 2 + C(3)) \times \sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{17} &:= (C((-9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{18} &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{18} &:= (-9 + \sqrt{C(8 + (7 - 6)^{54321})}) \\
\mathbf{19} &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times \sqrt{4}) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{19} &:= \sqrt{-9 \times 8 + C(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
\mathbf{20} &:= 1 + C(2 \times 3) / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{20} &:= 9 + (8 - 7)^{65} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{21} &:= (1 - 2 - C(3)) / \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{21} &:= 9 + \sqrt{C(8 + 7 - 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
\mathbf{22} &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) / \sqrt{4}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{22} &:= (((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{23} &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{23} &:= (-9 + (C(8) / (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
\mathbf{24} &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{24} &:= ((-9 \times 8) / (7 - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{25} &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{25} &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{26} &:= C(1 \times 2 + 3) - C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{26} &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{27} &:= \sqrt{C((-1 - 2 - C(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))} & \mathbf{27} &:= (-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{28} &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & \mathbf{28} &:= (((-9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{29} &:= (-1 - 2 + 3) + C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{29} &:= (((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) / 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{30} &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{30} &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{31} &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{31} &:= 9 + \sqrt{C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
\mathbf{32} &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{32} &:= (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{33} &:= (-1 - (2 + 3 - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{33} &:= (-9 + (\sqrt{C(8 + 7 - 6)} + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{34} &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3 - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{34} &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{35} &:= ((-1 + 2)^{34} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{35} &:= \sqrt{-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
\mathbf{36} &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{36} &:= 9 \times C(8) / ((7 + 6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$37 := (-1 + 2 - (3 - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$38 := (1 - 2)^3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$39 := (-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$40 := (-1 \times (2 - (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$41 := (((-1 - 2 + C(3))/4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$42 := (1 + 2) \times C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$43 := (-1 + (2 + (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$44 := (-1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$45 := (-1 + \sqrt{C(2+3) - 4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$46 := (-1 + (2^3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$47 := ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$48 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$49 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$50 := (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$51 := 1 + 2 + C(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$52 := (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$53 := (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$54 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$55 := (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$56 := (-1 \times (2 \times ((3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$57 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$58 := (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$59 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$60 := 1 \times 2 + C(3) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$61 := (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$62 := C(1 \times 2 - 3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$63 := (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$64 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$65 := (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$66 := (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$67 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$68 := (-1 \times (C(2 - 3 + 4) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$69 := 1 + 2 + C(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$70 := ((-1 + 2 - (3 - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$71 := 1 - 2 - C(3) + C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$72 := (1 - 2) \times C(3) + C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$73 := ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$74 := ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$75 := ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$37 := (C((-9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$38 := (-9 + 8 + C(7)) / (-6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$39 := ((-9 + \sqrt{C(8+7) - 6 - 5}) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$40 := ((-9 - 8 - C(7)) / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$41 := 9 + C(8) / (7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$42 := (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) / 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$43 := (-9 + ((8 + C((7 + 6 - 5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$44 := (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + 6 + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$45 := ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$46 := (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$47 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$48 := ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$49 := (-9 + \sqrt{C(8+7) - (6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)})$$

$$50 := ((-9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$51 := 9 + \sqrt{C(8+7-6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1}$$

$$52 := (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) / 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$53 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$54 := (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$55 := \sqrt{-9 + 8 - C(7) - 6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$56 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$57 := ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$58 := (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$59 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$60 := ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$61 := (-9 + ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$62 := 9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6 + 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$63 := ((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$64 := (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$65 := (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$66 := (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$67 := ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$68 := (-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$69 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$70 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$71 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6)^5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$72 := 9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6)^{54321}$$

$$73 := ((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$74 := (C((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$75 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$76 := (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - C(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$77 := (((-1+2+C(3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$78 := ((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$79 := ((-1-2 \times 3) - (C(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$80 := ((-1 + ((2+C(3)) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$81 := ((-1-2) \times (C(3)/(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$82 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$83 := 1 \times 2 \times C(3) + C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$84 := ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$85 := ((-1 + C(2+3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$86 := (C(-1+2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$87 := (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$88 := (-1+2 + (3 \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$89 := C(1 \times 2 \times 3)/4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$90 := (C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$91 := (((-1 + C(2+3)) + \sqrt{4}) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$92 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$93 := (C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$94 := ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$95 := (C(-1+2+3) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$96 := (C(-1+2 \times 3) - (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$97 := ((-1+2-3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$98 := (-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$99 := (C((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$100 := (((-1+2)^3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$101 := (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + 4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$102 := (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$103 := (C(-1+2+3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$104 := 1 \times 2 + 3 + C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$105 := 1 + 2 + 3 + C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$106 := (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$107 := (((-1 + (2 \times C(3+4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$108 := (1+2) \times 3 + C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$109 := ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - C(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$110 := (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$111 := (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$112 := 1 - 2 - C(3) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$113 := (1-2) \times C(3) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$114 := C(1 \times 2 + 3) + 4! - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$115 := 1 + C(2+3) + 4! - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$76 := (((-9+8+7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$77 := ((-9-8-7+C(6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$78 := (((-9-8) \times (7-6-5)) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$79 := (-9+8 + (7+6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$80 := ((-9+8 \times (7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$81 := 9 \times (8 + (7-6)^{54321})$$

$$82 := (-9+8-7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$83 := 9 + C(8+7-6-5) + 4+3+2+1$$

$$84 := (-9-8-7 + (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$85 := (((-9 - (8+7+6)) + C(5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$86 := (-9 - ((C(8) + C(7))/(6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$87 := (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$88 := (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6)/5) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$89 := (-9 - (((8 + C(7)) - C(6+5))/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$90 := ((-9-8+7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$91 := (-9 - ((8 - (7+6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$92 := ((-9+8 - (7 \times 6)) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$93 := ((-9+8-7+C(6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$94 := ((((-9+8) \times 7) + C(6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$95 := ((-9-8+C(7)) - (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$96 := ((-9+8+7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$97 := (((-9 - (8+7-6)) + C(5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$98 := ((-9-8+C(((7-6) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$99 := (-9 \times (((8-7-6)/5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$100 := (((-9 + (C(8) + 7))/6) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$101 := (9 \times (C(8) - C(7)) - 6)/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$102 := (-9+8-7 + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$103 := (9 + C(8) + 7)/6 + (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$104 := (-9 - (C(8) - (((7+6) \times C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$105 := ((-9 - (8+7+6)) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$106 := (C(-9+8+7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$107 := (C(-9+8+7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$108 := 9 \times (\sqrt{C(8+7-6)} - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$109 := (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$110 := (-9 + ((8 \times (7+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$111 := ((-9+8+C(7)) - (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$112 := (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$113 := (((-9+8-7+6) + C(5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$114 := ((-9+8+7) + (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$115 := (C((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$116 := ((-1+2+3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$117 := 1+2 \times (C(3) - 4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$118 := 1+C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) + 5+6+7+8) - 9$$

$$119 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (\sqrt{4} - (5+6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$120 := ((C(-1+2+3) - (4! + 5+6+7+8+9)))!$$

$$121 := (C(-1+2+3) + (\sqrt{C(4+5)} + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$122 := (-1 - 2 + C(((3+4) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$123 := (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$124 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$125 := C((-1+2 - (C(3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$126 := (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$127 := (-1+2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$128 := ((-1+2+C(3)) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$129 := 1+2+C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8) + 9$$

$$130 := (((C(-1+2+3)/\sqrt{4}) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$131 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$132 := 1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$133 := 1+2 \times (C(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$134 := (C(-1+2+3) + (\sqrt{4} \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$135 := (-1 \times (2+3 - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$136 := (C(-1+2 \times 3) - (4! - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$137 := (((-1+2+C(3)) \times 4) - 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$138 := ((-1+2-3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$139 := (1-2)^3 + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$140 := ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$141 := (((-1+2)^3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$142 := (((-1+2-3) \times 4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$143 := C(1 \times 2 \times 3) / \sqrt{4} + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$144 := (1+2) \times (C(3) - (4+5) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$145 := (-1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$146 := (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - C(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$147 := (((-1+2+C(3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$148 := (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$149 := (-1 + ((2 + (C(3)/(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$150 := (-1 + (((2+C(3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$151 := (((-1+2)^{34}) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$152 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$153 := (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$154 := C(1 \times 2 + 3) + C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$116 := ((-9+8+7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$117 := ((-9 \times ((8-7-6) - C(5)))/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$118 := (-9-8 + (C(((7-6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$119 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$120 := (((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$121 := ((-9+8-7-6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$122 := ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$123 := 9-8-7-6+C(5) + 4+3+2+1$$

$$124 := (-9 - ((8-7 - C(6+5))/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$125 := C((-9 - ((8-7)^6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$126 := ((-9+8+7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$127 := ((-9+8+7+6) + C(5) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$128 := (-9 + (\sqrt{C(8+7-6)} + (5! - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$129 := ((-9 \times (8-7 - C(6)))/(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$130 := 9 + C(8) - C(7) - 6!/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$131 := (((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1))$$

$$132 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$133 := ((-9+8-7+6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$134 := ((-9/(8+7-6)) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$135 := (C((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$136 := ((-9-8 \times 7 + C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$137 := (-9 + (8 \times 7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$138 := (-9 + ((8 + C(7+6))/(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$139 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$140 := (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 + C(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$141 := ((-9+8+C(7)) - (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$142 := ((-9-8-7+C(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$143 := ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6+5+4)))) + C(3+2+1))$$

$$144 := (-9 \times (8 \times (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$145 := ((9+8) \times 7 + C(6+5))/(4+3+2+1)$$

$$146 := (-9+8 + (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$147 := (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$148 := (-9 + (\sqrt{C(8+7-6)} + (5! + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$149 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$150 := (((-9+8+7+6) \times C(5))/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$151 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$152 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$153 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$154 := (((-9 + C(8+7-6))/5) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$155 := 1 + C(2+3) + C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$156 := ((-1+2+3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$157 := (((-1+2) \times 3) \times C(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$158 := ((-1+2+(3 \times C(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$159 := ((-1-(2-(3+4))) + (C(5)+6+7+8+9))$$

$$160 := (C((-1 \times (2-(3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$161 := (((-1+2+3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$162 := (1+2) \times C(3-4+5) - 6-7-8-9$$

$$163 := (-1 + (C(2+3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$164 := (C(-1+2 \times 3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$165 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$166 := 1-2 + C(3) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$167 := (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$168 := (-1+2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$169 := 1 \times 2 + C(3) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$170 := ((-1-2+C(3)) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$171 := (((-1+2+3) \times 4) + (C(5)+6+7+8+9))$$

$$172 := 1-2 + (C(3) - 4 + 5 \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$173 := (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$174 := (1+2+3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8) - 9)$$

$$175 := ((-1 \times 2 + C(3!)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$176 := ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$177 := (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$178 := 1 + C(2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$179 := (-1 + (((2 \times C(3))/(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$180 := ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times 4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$181 := (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) / 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$182 := ((-1+2-3) \times (C(4) - (C(5)+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$183 := (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$184 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$185 := C(1 \times 2 \times 3) - (-4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$186 := 1 + C(2 \times 3) + 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$187 := (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$188 := (C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) - (C(5)+6+7+8+9))$$

$$189 := 1 + 2 \times (C(3-4+5) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$190 := ((-1-2+C(3+4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$191 := (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$192 := (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$193 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$194 := 1 \times 2 \times C(3) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$155 := ((((-9+8 \times 7) - C(6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))$$

$$156 := (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7)))/6) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$157 := 9 + C(8) - (C(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$158 := ((-9+8-7+C(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$159 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$160 := (-9 + C(8) - C((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$161 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$162 := ((-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + 6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$163 := 9 + C(8) - (C(7!/6!) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$164 := (-9 + ((C(8) + 7)/((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$165 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + C(6+5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$166 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$167 := (((-9 + C((8-7+6))) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$168 := ((((-9+8+C(7)) - 6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$169 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$170 := (9 \times C(8) - C(7) \times 6)/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$171 := 9 - C(8) + C(7) + C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)$$

$$172 := (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7+6) + C(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$173 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$174 := (((-9+8+(C(7)+6)) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$175 := (-9 + C(8) - (C((7!/6!)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$176 := (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + C(6+5)))/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$177 := ((-9-8-7+C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$178 := 9 + (C(8) - C((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$179 := 9 + (C(8) - (C(7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$180 := 9 \times \sqrt{C(8) - C(7) + C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1}$$

$$181 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$182 := (((-9 - (C(8) - C(7))) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$183 := 9 + C(8) - ((7 + C(6+5)) - C(4+3+2+1))$$

$$184 := ((-9+8-7) - ((C(6)/(5+4)) - C(3+2+1)))$$

$$185 := ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5)))/(4+3+2+1))$$

$$186 := (C(-9+8+7) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$187 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + (C(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$188 := (-9+8+(7 \times C(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$189 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$190 := (((-9+8 \times (7+6))/5) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$191 := (((-9-8+7) + C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$192 := ((-9 + C(((8-7) \times 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$193 := ((-9+8-7+C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$194 := 9 + (C(8) + (7 + C(6+5)))/(4+3+2+1)$$

$$195 := ((-1 + (2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$196 := (-1 + ((2 \times 3^4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$197 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$198 := (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (C(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$199 := (-1 - ((C(2^3)/C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$200 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$201 := (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$202 := (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) / 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$203 := (C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$204 := (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$205 := (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$206 := ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$207 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$208 := ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$209 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$210 := (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) / 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$211 := ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$212 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$213 := ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$214 := ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$215 := (-1 + C((2 - (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$216 := ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$217 := 1 + C(2 - C(3) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$218 := (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$219 := (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$220 := (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$221 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$222 := (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$223 := (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$224 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$225 := (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$226 := (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$227 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$228 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$229 := 11 + 3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8$$

$$230 := ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$231 := (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$232 := (1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9)$$

$$233 := 1 + 2^3 \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9)$$

$$234 := (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$195 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$196 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$197 := ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$198 := 9 \times \sqrt{C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$199 := (-9 - 8 + C((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$200 := (((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) - C(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$201 := (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$202 := (-9 + (C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$203 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$204 := (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$205 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$206 := (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$207 := (-9 + C(((8 + 7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$208 := (9 - 8) \times 7 + C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$209 := 9 - 8 + 7 + C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$210 := (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - C(6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$211 := (-9 + (((8 + C(7 + 6)) - 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$212 := ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$213 := ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$214 := ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + C(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$215 := 9 - 8 - 7 + C(6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$216 := C(((((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))!$$

$$217 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$218 := ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$219 := ((((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - C(6 + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$220 := 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$221 := ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$222 := (-9 + (C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$223 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$224 := (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$225 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$226 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$227 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$228 := 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$229 := (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$230 := 9 + (8 + C(7 + 6) + 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$231 := ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$232 := ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$233 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$234 := ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$235 := (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$236 := ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$237 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$238 := (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$239 := 1 + 2 + 3^4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$240 := ((1 - 2)^3 + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$241 := (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$242 := 1 - 2 - C(3) + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$243 := (1 - 2) \times C(3) + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$244 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$245 := C(1 \times 2 \times 3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9)$$

$$246 := 1 + C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9)$$

$$247 := (C(((1 - 2) \times 3)!) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$248 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3!)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$249 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$250 := (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$251 := (C(((1 - 2 + C(3))/4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$252 := (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (4 - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$253 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$254 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$255 := (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$256 := (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) \times 5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$257 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$258 := ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$259 := (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$260 := (((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$261 := (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9)$$

$$262 := 1 - 2 + C(3) \times 4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$263 := (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$264 := (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$265 := (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$266 := ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$267 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$268 := 1 - 2 \times C(3!) + C(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$269 := (1 - 2)^3 + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$270 := 1 + 2 \times (C(3!) - C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$271 := (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$272 := (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$273 := ((-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$274 := (1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$235 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$236 := ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$237 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$238 := (9 - 8) \times 7 + C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$239 := ((-9 \times (C(8) - 7)) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$240 := (9 + (C(8 + 7) + C(6))) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$241 := (9 + 8 - 7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$242 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$243 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$244 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$245 := (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$246 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$247 := (-9 - (C(8) / (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$248 := (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$249 := (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$250 := ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$251 := 9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$252 := ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$253 := ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$254 := ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) / (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$255 := (9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$256 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$257 := (-9 - (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$258 := (((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$259 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$260 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$261 := ((9 + (C(8) + (7 - 6))) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$262 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$263 := (-9 - (C(8) + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$264 := (-9 + (((C(8) + C(7)) / (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$265 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$266 := ((-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$267 := (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$268 := (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$269 := (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$270 := ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$271 := (-9 \times 8 + C((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$272 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$273 := (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$274 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$275 := (C((-1+2) \times 3!) + (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$276 := (-1 + 2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$277 := 1 \times 2 + C(3!) + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$278 := (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$279 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$280 := ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$281 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$282 := (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$283 := (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$284 := ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$285 := (1 \times 2 + 3) \times C(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$286 := 1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$287 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$288 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$289 := (-1 + 2 + ((C(3 \times 4) \times 5) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$290 := (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$291 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$292 := 1 + (2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$293 := (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$294 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$295 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$296 := (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$297 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$298 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$299 := 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$300 := 1 + 2 + 3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$301 := (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$302 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$303 := (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times 4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$304 := (C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$305 := ((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$306 := ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$307 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$308 := (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$309 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$310 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$311 := 1 + 2 + C(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$312 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$313 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$314 := 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times C(4) + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$275 := ((-9 \times (C(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$276 := ((9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$277 := (9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$278 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$279 := ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$280 := ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$281 := (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$282 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$283 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$284 := ((-9 + C((8 - 7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$285 := ((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$286 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$287 := (-9 + C(8) - C((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$288 := ((-9 \times C((8 - 7 + 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$289 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$290 := (9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$291 := 9 + (C(8) + ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$292 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$293 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$294 := (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7 + 6))) / (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$295 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$296 := (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$297 := 9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$298 := 9 \times 8 + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$299 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$300 := ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$301 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$302 := ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$303 := (((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + 6) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$304 := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$305 := ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$306 := (9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$307 := ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$308 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$309 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$310 := (9 \times C(8) + 7 \times 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$311 := ((9 \times (C(8) + 7)) - 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$312 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$313 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$314 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
315 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3!) + (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 315 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) / (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
316 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 316 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
317 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 317 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
318 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 318 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - C(7 + 6)) / 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
319 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 319 &:= ((-9 + C((8 - 7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
320 &:= ((-1 \times C((2 + 3) \times 4)) / (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 320 &:= ((9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
321 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 321 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
322 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 322 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
323 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 323 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
324 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 324 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
325 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 325 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
326 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 326 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
327 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 327 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
328 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 328 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - C(7 + 6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
329 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3 + C(4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 329 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
330 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 330 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
331 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 331 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
332 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 332 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
333 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 333 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
334 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 334 &:= (-9 + C((8 - (7 - 6)^{54321}))) \\
335 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 335 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
336 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 336 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - 7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
337 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - C(4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 337 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
338 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 338 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - C(7 + 6)) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
339 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 339 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
340 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 340 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7 - C(6)) / 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
341 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 341 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
342 &:= (-1 + C(((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 342 &:= (9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
343 &:= C(((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) / (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 343 &:= C((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
344 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 344 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
345 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 345 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
346 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 346 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
347 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 347 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
348 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 348 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
349 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 349 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
350 &:= ((-1 + \sqrt{(C(2 + 3) - 4)}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 350 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 \times 6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
351 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 351 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
352 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 352 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
353 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 353 &:= (C(((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
354 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 354 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$355 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$356 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$357 := 1 + C(2 \times 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$358 := C(1 \times 2^3) - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$359 := (1 + 2) \times C(3) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$360 := (1 - 2 - 3 + C(4)) / 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$361 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(((C(3) - 4)!)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$362 := (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$363 := (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$364 := (C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$365 := ((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$366 := ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$367 := (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$368 := (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$369 := ((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$370 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$371 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$372 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$373 := (C((-1 + 2 - (3 - 4 - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$374 := (C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$375 := (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$376 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$377 := (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$378 := (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$379 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$380 := ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$381 := (((-1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$382 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$383 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$384 := (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$385 := (\sqrt{C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - 4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$386 := ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$387 := (-1 + (2^3 + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$388 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$389 := (-1 - (((2 - 3) - C(4)) / 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$390 := 1 + 2 \times (C(3!) - 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$391 := (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$392 := (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$393 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$394 := (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$355 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$356 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$357 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$358 := ((-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(6)) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$359 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$360 := (((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + 6!) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$361 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$362 := (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$363 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$364 := (-9 + 8 - (((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$365 := ((-9 + 8) \times (((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$366 := (-9 - (C(8 + 7) / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$367 := (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$368 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$369 := 9 + 8 + (C(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$370 := ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$371 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$372 := ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$373 := ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$374 := (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$375 := 9 + 8 + (C((7!/6!)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$376 := ((-9 - C(8 + 7)) / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$377 := (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$378 := 9 \times (8 + 7 + C(6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$379 := (-9 \times C(8) - (7 + 6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$380 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$381 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$382 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$383 := (9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$384 := (-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$385 := (((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$386 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$387 := (-9 - (C(8 + 7 - 6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$388 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$389 := (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$390 := 9 + 8 + C(7) - 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$391 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$392 := ((-9 \times C(8)) + (((7 - 6) \times 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$393 := (-9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$394 := 9 \times 8 + C(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$395 := (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$396 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$397 := (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$398 := (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$399 := (1 + 2) \times (4 \times C(3) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$400 := ((-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$401 := (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$402 := ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) + C(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$403 := (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$404 := ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$405 := ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$406 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$407 := (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$408 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$409 := (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$410 := (((-1 - 2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$411 := (1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$412 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$413 := (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$414 := (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$415 := (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$416 := ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$417 := 1 \times 2^3 \times C(4) - C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$418 := 1 + 2^3 \times C(4) - C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$419 := (1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$420 := 1 + 2 \times 3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$421 := (1 + 2) \times (C(3!) - C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$422 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$423 := (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$424 := 1 - 2 + (C(3) + C(4)) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$425 := (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$426 := ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$427 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$428 := (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$429 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$430 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$431 := (-1 + (2 \times C((C(3) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$432 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$433 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$434 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$395 := (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$396 := (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$397 := ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$398 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$399 := (9 - C(8) + 7) \times 6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$400 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$401 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + 6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$402 := (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$403 := (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$404 := ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$405 := ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$406 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$407 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$408 := ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$409 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$410 := \sqrt{-9 - C(8) + C(7 + 6) + 5} \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$411 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$412 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$413 := (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$414 := (-9 - (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$415 := (((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$416 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$417 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$418 := ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$419 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$420 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$421 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$422 := ((-9 + ((8 + C(7 + 6)) / 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$423 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$424 := ((-9 \times C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$425 := (-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) / (-5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$426 := (((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$427 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$428 := (-9 + C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$429 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$430 := ((-9 \times 8 + C((7 + 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$431 := 9 + (8 \times (-7 + C(6)) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$432 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$433 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$434 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
435 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3+4) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
436 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3+4) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
437 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
438 &:= (C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
439 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3+4) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
440 &:= 1 \times 2 + C(3+4) + C(5) - (6+7+8+9) \\
441 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
442 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
443 &:= (C(-1+2^3) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
444 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
445 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
446 &:= ((-1+C(2 \times 3)) - (4+5 - (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
447 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
448 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3+4) + (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9))))) \\
449 &:= 1 + 2^3 \times (C(4) - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
450 &:= (((-1-2+C(3)) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
451 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
452 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
453 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
454 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
455 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) / \sqrt{4} \\
456 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
457 &:= (((-1-2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
458 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
459 &:= 1 + 2^3 \times (-C(4) + C(5)) - (6+7+8+9) \\
460 &:= 1 + (2 + C(3)) \times (4+5+6) + 7+8+9 \\
461 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
462 &:= (1+2) \times (3-4+C(5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
463 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3!) - 4+5+6+7+8+9 \\
464 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
465 &:= ((C(-1+2 \times 3) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
466 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
467 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4+5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
468 &:= (((-1+2-3) + (4 \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
469 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
470 &:= (((-1-2 - (3+4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
471 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times 4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
472 &:= ((-1+C(2^3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
473 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
474 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3+4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
435 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
436 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
437 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
438 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
439 &:= (-9 + C(8) - C((7 - ((6 \times 5) / (4+3+2+1)))) \\
440 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
441 &:= (9 \times (C(8) + (7 + C(6)))) / (5+4+3+2+1) \\
442 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7+6)) / 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
443 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
444 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (C(7+6) + 5+4)) / (3+2+1))) \\
445 &:= (-9+8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
446 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6 + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
447 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
448 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
449 &:= (-9 + (C((8-7+6)) + (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
450 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7+6-5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
451 &:= (9-8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5 / (4+3+2+1))) \\
452 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
453 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7-6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
454 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7-6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
455 &:= ((-9-8 + C(7)) - (6 - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
456 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
457 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
458 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - C(6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
459 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) / 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
460 &:= (9 \times C(8) - (7+6-5)) / (4+3+2+1) \\
461 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7+6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
462 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
463 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7-6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
464 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7+6) \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
465 &:= 9 + C(8) - 7! / (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
466 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7+6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
467 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
468 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
469 &:= ((9-8) \times C(7+6)) - C((5! / (4+3+2+1))) \\
470 &:= 9+8 + (C(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
471 &:= (-9-8 - (C((7+6-5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
472 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
473 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - (6-5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
474 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (((7-6) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$475 := ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$476 := ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$477 := (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$478 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$479 := (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$480 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$481 := ((-1 + C((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$482 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$483 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$484 := (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$485 := (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$486 := (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$487 := (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$488 := (C((-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4 + 5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$489 := -C(-1 + 2^3) + C(4) \times (-5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$490 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$491 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$492 := (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$493 := (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$494 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$495 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$496 := (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$497 := (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$498 := (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$499 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$500 := 1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4) + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$501 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$502 := (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$503 := (1 - 2) \times C(3) + 4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$504 := (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$505 := (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$506 := (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$507 := (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$508 := 1 + (2 - C(3) + C(4)) \times (-5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$509 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$510 := ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times 4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$511 := (-1 + C(((C(2 \times 3) + C(4)) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$512 := C((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$513 := (((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$475 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$476 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$477 := (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$478 := (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$479 := ((-9 - C(8)) + (((7 - 6)^5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$480 := ((9 + (C(8) + 7)) / (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$481 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$482 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$483 := (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - 6 - 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$484 := (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$485 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$486 := 9 \times (C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$487 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$488 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$489 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$490 := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$491 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$492 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$493 := (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - 6)^5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$494 := (((-9 + C(8)) + ((7 - 6)^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$495 := (-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$496 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$497 := (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$498 := (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$499 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$500 := (((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$501 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$502 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 - 6)^{54321})$$

$$503 := ((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - 6)^{54321})$$

$$504 := ((-9 + C(8)) + (7 - 6)^{54321})$$

$$505 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$506 := ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$507 := 9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$508 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$509 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$510 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$511 := (-9 + 8 + C(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$512 := C(((((-9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$513 := (-9 \times (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$514 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4 + C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$515 := (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$516 := ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$517 := (-1 - ((2^3 \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$518 := (-1 \times ((2^3 \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$519 := (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$520 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - ((4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$521 := (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$522 := (-1 \times (2^3 - (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$523 := (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$524 := (-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$525 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$526 := (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$527 := (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$528 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$529 := ((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$530 := (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$531 := (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$532 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$533 := C(1 \times 2^3) - 4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$534 := (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$535 := ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$536 := ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$537 := (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$538 := (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$539 := (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$540 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$541 := (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$542 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$543 := (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$544 := (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$545 := 1 - C(2^3) + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$546 := (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$547 := (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$548 := ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times C(4))) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$549 := ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times 4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$550 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$551 := C(1 \times 2^3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$552 := 1 + C(2^3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$514 := ((-9 + C(8)) + (((7 - 6)^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$515 := (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$516 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$517 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$518 := (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$519 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$520 := ((((-9 + 8 + C(7))/6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$521 := (-9 + 8 + (C((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$522 := (9 + C(8)) + (7 - 6)^{54321}$$

$$523 := (-9 - ((C(8) - C((7 + 6 + 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$524 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$525 := (-9 + 8 - (C(7) + ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$526 := ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$527 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$528 := 9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$529 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$530 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$531 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$532 := (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$533 := (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$534 := (-9 - (C(8) + (((7 - C(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$535 := (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times C(5))/4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$536 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$537 := (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$538 := ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$539 := (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$540 := (9 + \sqrt{C(8 + 7 - 6)}) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$541 := ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$542 := (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$543 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$544 := (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$545 := (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$546 := (((-9 + C(8 + 7))/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$547 := (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$548 := ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5))))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$549 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$550 := ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$551 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$552 := (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$553 := ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times 4!) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$554 := (-1-2 + (C(3) + (4 \times C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$555 := (((-1-2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$556 := ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$557 := (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times C(5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$558 := (-1+2 + (C(3) + (4 \times C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$559 := ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4)) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$560 := 1+2+C(3)+4 \times C(5)+6+7+8+9$$

$$561 := ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$562 := (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$563 := ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 \times (5+6 - (7+8+9))))$$

$$564 := (-1-2 - (C(3) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$565 := (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$566 := ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$567 := (-1-2 + (((C(3) \times 4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$568 := (-1+2 - (C(3) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$569 := 1 \times 2 + C(3) \times (-4-5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$570 := (((-1+2+C(3)) - 4-5) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$571 := (-1+2 + ((C(3) \times 4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$572 := (-1-2 - ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$573 := (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$574 := (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$575 := (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$576 := (-1+2 - ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$577 := (-1 - (C(2+3+4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$578 := ((-1 + C(2+3+4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$579 := (C((-1-2+3 \times 4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$580 := ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 - C(4)) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$581 := (-1 + ((2^3 \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$582 := (C(-1+2+3) + (4 \times C(5) - (6 - (7+8+9))))$$

$$583 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$584 := (((-1+2 \times 3) \times C(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$585 := (((-1-2) \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$586 := (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) + (6 - (7+8+9))))))$$

$$587 := (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))$$

$$588 := (((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4) + C(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$589 := (1+2) \times 3 \times C(4) - 5-6+7+8+9$$

$$590 := ((-1 + (2 \times 3))^4 - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$591 := (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$592 := 1+2 \times C(3+4) - C(5) + 6+7+8+9$$

$$553 := ((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times C(5))) - C(4+3+2+1))$$

$$554 := (-9 + (C(8) + ((7-6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$555 := ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (6 \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$556 := (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$557 := (-9-8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$558 := 9 + (C(8) - (7+6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$559 := ((-9 \times (8+7 - C(6))) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$560 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$561 := (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times (6+5)) / (4+3+2+1))$$

$$562 := (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times 6 - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$563 := (-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$564 := (-9 + ((C(8) + (C(7+6) + C(5+4))) / (3+2+1)))$$

$$565 := 9-8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$566 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$567 := (C(-9+8+7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$568 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$569 := (-9-8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))))$$

$$570 := ((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$571 := (((-9-8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$572 := ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$573 := (-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$574 := (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) - C(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$575 := (-9 + ((8 + C((7+6+5))) / (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$576 := (((-9 + C(8+7)) / 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$577 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + 6) - C(5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$578 := 9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$579 := ((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$580 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$581 := (-9 + (((8 - (C(7) \times 6)) / 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$582 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$583 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7+6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$584 := (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6-5 - C(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$585 := ((-9-8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$586 := (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$587 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + C(6)) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$588 := (((-9 + C(8+7)) / 6) + C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))$$

$$589 := (-9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) / 5) + C(4+3+2+1))$$

$$590 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$591 := 9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$592 := ((-9+8+C(7)) - ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
593 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
594 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
595 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
596 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
597 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
598 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3) \times C(4) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
599 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
600 &:= (1 \times 2 + C(3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
601 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
602 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
603 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3) \times C(4) + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
604 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4 + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
605 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
606 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
607 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
608 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
609 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
610 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
611 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
612 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
613 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
614 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
615 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
616 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
617 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3)/4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
618 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
619 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
620 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
621 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
622 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
623 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
624 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
625 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) + 4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
626 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
627 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
628 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
629 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
630 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
631 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
632 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
593 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times C(7)) + C(6))/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
594 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
595 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - 6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
596 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
597 &:= 9 \times 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
598 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + C(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
599 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 + 6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
600 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
601 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
602 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
603 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
604 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
605 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
606 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
607 &:= 9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6)/5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
608 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
609 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
610 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
611 &:= 9 \times (C(8) - C(7)) - ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
612 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + C((6 + 5 + 4))))/(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
613 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
614 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
615 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
616 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
617 &:= 9 - (C(8) + ((7 + 6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
618 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
619 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - 6) + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
620 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
621 &:= (9 - ((C(8) + 7) \times 6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
622 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
623 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
624 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
625 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
626 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7 - 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
627 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((C(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
628 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
629 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + (6! - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
630 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
631 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
632 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$633 := (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$634 := (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$635 := (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$636 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$637 := ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$638 := (-1 - ((2+3)! - (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$639 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$640 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$641 := (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (C((4+5-6)) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$642 := (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$643 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$644 := (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (C(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$645 := ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (C(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$646 := (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$647 := (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$648 := (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$649 := 1 \times 2 + C(3) + 4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$650 := ((-1 + (2 \times C(3+4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$651 := (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$652 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C((4+5-6)) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$653 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$654 := (-1 - (((2 - (3+4)) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$655 := (((-1 \times (2 - (3+4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$656 := (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (C(4+5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$657 := (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$658 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$659 := (1 + C(2+3)) \times 4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$660 := ((-1 + (2 \times 3))^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$661 := (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$662 := (C((-1+2+3+4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$663 := (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$664 := (C(-1+2+3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$665 := 1 + 2 \times (3 \times C(4) + C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$666 := (-1 + 2 + ((3+4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$667 := (C((-1+2+3+4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$668 := (-1 - ((2 \times C(3+4)) - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$669 := (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$670 := (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$671 := ((((-1-2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6))) - (7+8+9))$$

$$672 := (-1 + ((2 \times C(3+4)) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$633 := 9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$634 := (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$635 := ((-9 - 8 - 7) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$636 := (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$637 := (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$638 := (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$639 := (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$640 := (C(((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$641 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$642 := (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$643 := (-9 - (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$644 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$645 := (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$646 := ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$647 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times C(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$648 := ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6)))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$649 := 9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$650 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$651 := (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$652 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$653 := (-9 - (C((8 - 7 + 6)) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$654 := (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$655 := (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$656 := (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$657 := (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$658 := ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$659 := (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - 6 - 5) + C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$660 := (9 + \sqrt{(C(8) - 7 + 6!)}) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$661 := (((9 - C(8)) \times 7) + C(6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$662 := ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$663 := (-9 \times 8 + (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$664 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$665 := (-9 + 8 + 7 - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$666 := (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$667 := (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$668 := ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$669 := (9 - 8 - C(7)) + ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$670 := (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$671 := (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$672 := (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (6 \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
673 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
674 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
675 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
676 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C((4 + 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
677 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
678 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
679 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - ((4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
680 &:= ((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
681 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
682 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
683 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
684 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
685 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
686 &:= ((-1 \times C(2 \times (3 + 4))) / (5 - (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
687 &:= 1 + C(2 \times 3) + 4 \times C(5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
688 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
689 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) - C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
690 &:= (1 + C(2 - 3 + 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
691 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
692 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
693 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
694 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
695 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3 \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
696 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
697 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
698 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
699 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 + C(4 + 5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
700 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
701 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) / 4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
702 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
703 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
704 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
705 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
706 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
707 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
708 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
709 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
710 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4))) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
711 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
712 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
673 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
674 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
675 &:= 9 - (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
676 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
677 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
678 &:= ((-9 - (C(8 + 7) + 6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
679 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
680 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
681 &:= (9 \times C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
682 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6) / 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
683 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
684 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
685 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
686 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
687 &:= (9 - C(8)) - (((7 - 6) - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
688 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + (C(6) / (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
689 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
690 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
691 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
692 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
693 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
694 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
695 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 - (6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
696 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
697 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
698 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
699 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
700 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
701 &:= 9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
702 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
703 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
704 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
705 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
706 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
707 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
708 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + C(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
709 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) \times 7) + 6) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
710 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + ((7 - 6)^5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
711 &:= 9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
712 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C((7 - (6 - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
713 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
714 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 3) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
715 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C((C(3) - (4 \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
716 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4)) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
717 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
718 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4 + 5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
719 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
720 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
721 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3 \times 4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
722 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
723 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
724 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
725 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
726 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
727 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
728 &:= (-1 + C(((2 - 3) - ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
729 &:= C((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
730 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
731 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
732 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
733 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
734 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
735 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
736 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
737 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
738 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
739 &:= (((((-1 + 2)^3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
740 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
741 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
742 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
743 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
744 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
745 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C((C(3) - (4 \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
746 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
747 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
748 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
749 &:= 1 - C(2 + 3) + C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
750 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
751 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
752 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
713 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
714 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
715 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
716 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + 6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
717 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
718 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
719 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + C((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
720 &:= (-9 + C((8 + (7 - 6)^{54321}))) \\
721 &:= 9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
722 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
723 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
724 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
725 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
726 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
727 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
728 &:= (C(((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
729 &:= C(((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
730 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
731 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
732 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
733 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
734 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
735 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
736 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
737 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
738 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
739 &:= (C(((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) / 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
740 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
741 &:= 9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
742 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
743 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
744 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) / (7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
745 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
746 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
747 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
748 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
749 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
750 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
751 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7 - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
752 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
753 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
754 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
755 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
756 &:= (((-1-2-3) \times (4-C(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
757 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
758 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
759 &:= (C((-1-(2-(3+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
760 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
761 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4+5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
762 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
763 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
764 &:= (C((-1-2+3 \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
765 &:= (((-1+C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
766 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
767 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3 - C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9))) \\
768 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
769 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 3) \times 4 - C(5) + 6+7+8+9 \\
770 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
771 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times (4+5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
772 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3)+4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
773 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3)+4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
774 &:= (-1 + ((2-C(3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
775 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3+4))) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
776 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3)+4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
777 &:= (-1-2 + ((C(3)+4-5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
778 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3)+4-5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
779 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
780 &:= (-1-2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
781 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
782 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + C(4)) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
783 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
784 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
785 &:= (((-1+C(2 \times 3)) - C(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
786 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
787 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3) + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
788 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times ((5+C(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
789 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
790 &:= (-1-2 + ((3-C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
791 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
792 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((C(4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
753 &:= 9 + (C(8+7-6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
754 &:= (((-9-8+7) \times (6+5)) + (4 \times C(3+2+1))) \\
755 &:= ((-9-8-7) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
756 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
757 &:= ((-9 \times C((8 - ((7-6) \times 5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
758 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times 6 - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
759 &:= (-9-8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
760 &:= ((-9+8+7 \times (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
761 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6)) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
762 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
763 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (6 - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
764 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) - 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
765 &:= ((-9-8-7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
766 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7+6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
767 &:= ((9-8) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
768 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
769 &:= 9 - ((8+7 - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
770 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7-6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
771 &:= ((-9+8-7) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
772 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
773 &:= (-9 - (C((8-7+6)) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
774 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - 7 - C(6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
775 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
776 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (6+C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
777 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6) / (5+4)) + C(3+2+1)) \\
778 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
779 &:= ((-9-8+7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
780 &:= (-9 - (C(((8-7) \times 6)) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
781 &:= ((-9+8-7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
782 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
783 &:= (-9+8 - (C((7 - (6-5))) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
784 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + 5) + C(4+3+2+1) \\
785 &:= (-9+8+7 - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
786 &:= (-9-8-7 + (6 \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
787 &:= (-9+8 - (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
788 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
789 &:= ((-9+8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
790 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7-6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
791 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
792 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - ((6 \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
819 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
820 &:= 1 + (-2 + 3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
821 &:= 1 + 2 \times (C(3 + 4) - 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
822 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
823 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
824 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
825 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
826 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
827 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
828 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
829 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) + (C(5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
830 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
831 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
832 &:= ((C(C((-1 - 2 + 3))) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
793 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
794 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
795 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
796 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
797 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
798 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
799 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
800 &:= (C(((9 - 8 + 7) + (6 \times 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
801 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
802 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
803 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
804 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
805 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
806 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
807 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
808 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
809 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times 6 + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
810 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
811 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
812 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
813 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
814 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
815 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
816 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
817 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
818 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
819 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
820 &:= (((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
821 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
822 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (6 - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
823 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
824 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
825 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
826 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
827 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
828 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
829 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times 6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
830 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
831 &:= 9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
832 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
873 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
874 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
875 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
876 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
877 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
878 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
879 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
880 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
881 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
882 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 + C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
883 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
884 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
885 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
886 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
887 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3 - 4 - 5) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
888 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
889 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 3) \times 4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
890 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
891 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
892 &:= C(1 \times 2^3) + 4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
893 &:= (1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
894 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
895 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
896 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
897 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
898 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
899 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
900 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
901 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
902 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
903 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
904 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
905 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
906 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
907 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
908 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (5 + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
909 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
910 &:= ((-1 + C(2 - 3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
911 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 - 3 + 4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
912 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
873 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
874 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
875 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
876 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
877 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
878 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
879 &:= ((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) - (5! - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
880 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
881 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
882 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - C(6 + 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
883 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
884 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
885 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
886 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
887 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
888 &:= (((-9 + 8 - (C(7) + C(6)))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
889 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
890 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
891 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) + C(6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
892 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
893 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 + 5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
894 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + C(7 + 6))/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
895 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
896 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
897 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
898 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
899 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
900 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
901 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
902 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
903 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
904 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
905 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
906 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
907 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + 7))/6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
908 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
909 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
910 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
911 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
912 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
913 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9) \\
914 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
915 &:= (((-1-2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
916 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
917 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - (5+6 - (7+8+9))))) \\
918 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
919 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
920 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
921 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4) \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
922 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
924 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times ((4+5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
925 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
926 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
927 &:= ((-1-2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
928 &:= ((-1 - C(2+3)) + ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
929 &:= ((-1 \times C(2+3)) + ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
930 &:= ((-1-2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
931 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
932 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) \times (4+5))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
933 &:= (((-1+2^3) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
934 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4 \times C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
935 &:= (((-1+2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
936 &:= ((-1-2 + C(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
937 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 \times (4 - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
938 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 \times (4 - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
939 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
940 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
941 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) \times (4+5)) + C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
942 &:= (-1+2 + (((3+4) \times (C(5)+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
943 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
944 &:= (-1 + (C(2-3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
945 &:= (C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
946 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (C(4+5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))))) \\
947 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) - C(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
948 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4+5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
949 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
950 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
951 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3+4)) + (5 \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
952 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
913 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
914 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7-6)) - 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
915 &:= (-9+8+7 - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
916 &:= ((-9+8+7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
917 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + 7))/6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
918 &:= ((-9-8 - ((7+6) \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
919 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + 7+6)/(5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
920 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7+6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
921 &:= ((-9+8+7)! + (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
922 &:= ((-9+8 - (7 \times (6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
923 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7 \times (6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
924 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7-6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
925 &:= (((-9 - ((8-7) \times 6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
926 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
927 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 + C(6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7-6)^5) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
929 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7-6)^5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
930 &:= ((-9-8 + (7 \times C(6+5)))/(4+3+2+1)) \\
931 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7 \times 6))/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
932 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7-6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
933 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) + 6)/(5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
934 &:= ((-9+8 - ((7+6) \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
935 &:= (((-9+8) \times ((7+6) \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
936 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
937 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7-6)^5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
938 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
939 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
940 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7 - C(6))) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
941 &:= ((-9+8+7)! + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
942 &:= (((-9+8-7) \times (6 - C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
943 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6-5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
944 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - C(5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
945 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
946 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7+6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
947 &:= ((((-9+8-7) \times 6) - 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
948 &:= (-9 + (((8-7 - C(6))/5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
949 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
950 &:= (((-9 - (8+7+6)) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
951 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7-6) \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
952 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + 7))/(6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
953 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
954 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (C(3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
955 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
956 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
957 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
958 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
959 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 - 3 + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
960 &:= (1 - 2) \times (C(3) - C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
961 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
962 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
963 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
964 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
965 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
966 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
967 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
968 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) + 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
969 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
970 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
971 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
972 &:= (1 + 2) \times (C(3 + 4) - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
973 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
974 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
975 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
976 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times C(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
977 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C((3 - (4 - 5 - 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
978 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
979 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
980 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
981 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (C(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
982 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
983 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
984 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
985 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
986 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
987 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (C(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
988 &:= 1 - (2 + 3) \times C(4) + C(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
989 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
990 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
991 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (C(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
992 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
953 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
954 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
955 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((C(6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
956 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
957 &:= ((((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
958 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7 - C(6))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
959 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
960 &:= ((9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
961 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
962 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
963 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
964 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
965 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
966 &:= ((-9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
967 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
968 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
969 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
970 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
971 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
972 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
973 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6)/5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
974 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
975 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
976 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
977 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
978 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
979 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
980 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
981 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
982 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
983 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6)/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
984 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
985 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
986 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 - C(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
987 &:= ((9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
988 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
989 &:= ((-9 + (8/(7 - 6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
990 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
991 &:= (-9 + C((8 - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
992 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - C(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
993 &:= (1-2)^3 + 4^5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
994 &:= (1+2) \times C(3+4) - (5+6+7+8+9) \\
995 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
996 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3+4+5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
997 &:= 1 + 2 \times (C(3+4) + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
998 &:= 1 - 2 + C(3+4+5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
999 &:= (-1 + C((2 \times ((3+4) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1000 &:= C((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1001 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1002 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1003 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1004 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (((4+5) + C(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1005 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times (3+4)) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1006 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times (3+4)) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1007 &:= 1 - C(2 \times (3+4)) + C(5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
1008 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) + (4+5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1009 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (4+5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1010 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1011 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4+5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1012 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - (5+6 - (7+8+9))) \\
1013 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) \times 4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1014 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1015 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1016 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3+4) \times C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
1017 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) + (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1018 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1019 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1020 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1021 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1022 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1023 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1024 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1025 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1026 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5+6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1027 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
1028 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1029 &:= (-1 + (C(((2 \times 3) - 4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1030 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1031 &:= 1 + C((2 \times 3 - 4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
993 &:= ((-9 - (8/(7-6-5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
994 &:= (((-9 - (8+7+6))/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
995 &:= ((-9+8+7-6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
996 &:= (((-9 \times 8)/(7+6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
997 &:= (-9+8 - (C(7) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
998 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
999 &:= ((-9+8) \times (((7-6)^5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1000 &:= C(((9-8+(7 \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1001 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7+6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1002 &:= ((-9 + ((8-7) \times (6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1003 &:= ((-9+8 - (7-6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1004 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7-6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1005 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1006 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1007 &:= (((-9+8+7+6) - 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1008 &:= 9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1009 &:= (((-9 \times (8-7-6))/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1010 &:= ((-9-8-7) - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1011 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6)) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1012 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1013 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times C(7)) + 6)/C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1014 &:= ((-9 + (C(8+7+6)/(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
1015 &:= (-9 - (C(8) \times (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1016 &:= ((-9 - (8-7-6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1017 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7+6+5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1018 &:= (((-9 \times 8)/(7-6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1019 &:= (((-9+8 \times (7+6))/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1020 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1021 &:= ((-9 + ((8-7) \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1022 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1023 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7-6-5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1024 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1025 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7+6-5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1026 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7+6) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1027 &:= (C((-9+8 - (7-6-5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1028 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
1029 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1030 &:= (((-9+8-7+C(6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1031 &:= (-9 - (((8+7+6) - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1032 &:= ((-1+2+(C(3)+(4+5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1033 &:= (C(-1+2+3)+(C(4+5)+(C(6)+7+8+9))) \\
1034 &:= (-1+(C(2 \times 3+4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1035 &:= (C((-1 \times (2-3 \times 4)))+5+6+7+8+9) \\
1036 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)+C(4)) \times (5+6))+7+8+9) \\
1037 &:= ((-1+2+3)+((4^5)+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
1038 &:= (-1+2-3-(C(4)-((5 \times C(6))+7+8+9))) \\
1039 &:= (-1+(((2+3) \times C(4))+(5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
1040 &:= ((-1+2-C(3)) \times (4!-C((5!/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1041 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3-(C(4) \times 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1042 &:= (C(-1+2^3)+(C(4+5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
1043 &:= (-1+((C(2+3)-4-5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
1044 &:= ((C(-1+2 \times 3)-4-5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
1045 &:= (1-2+3 \times 4) \times (C(5)-(6+7+8+9)) \\
1046 &:= C(1 \times 2+3)+C(4+5)+C(6)-(7+8+9) \\
1047 &:= (1+2) \times (3! \times C(4)-(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1048 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3)+4^5-(6+7+8+9) \\
1049 &:= (-1+((2^3+\sqrt{C(4+5)}) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1050 &:= (-1-2+(C(3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1051 &:= (-1 \times 2+(C(3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1052 &:= 1-2+C(3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
1053 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1054 &:= (-1+2+(C(3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1055 &:= (((-1+2)^3)+((4^5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
1056 &:= 1+2+C(3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
1057 &:= (-1+2^3) \times (-4+C(5)+6+7+8+9) \\
1058 &:= ((C(-1+2+3)+4^5)-(6+7+8+9)) \\
1059 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (4-C(5)))-(6+7+8+9) \\
1060 &:= (\sqrt{-1+2+3} \times (4 \times C(5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
1061 &:= (-1+((2^3 \times (4+C(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
1062 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (4+C(5))+6+7+8+9 \\
1063 &:= (C((-1+2+3!))+((4!/(5!/(6+7+8+9))))!) \\
1064 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3^4))+C(5+6)-(7+8+9)) \\
1065 &:= (((-1+(C(2 \times 3)+4)) \times 5)-(6+7+8+9)) \\
1066 &:= (-1-2+(C(3+4)+((C(5) \times 6)-(7+8+9)))) \\
1067 &:= (C((-1+2^3+4))-((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1068 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3-(C(4+5)-(C(6)-(7+8+9)))))) \\
1069 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (C(4)+(5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) \\
1070 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (C(4)+(5 \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1071 &:= 1 + (2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1072 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (C(C(3 + 4 + 5)/C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1073 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (C(4) + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1074 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1075 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1076 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1077 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1078 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1079 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1080 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1081 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1082 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1083 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1084 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1085 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1086 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1087 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1088 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1089 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1090 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times 4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1091 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1092 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1093 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1094 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1095 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1096 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1097 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1098 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1099 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1100 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1101 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1102 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1103 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1104 &:= (1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1105 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1106 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + C(4))) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1107 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1108 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1109 &:= 1 + 2 \times C(3) + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1110 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1071 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1072 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) - (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1073 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1074 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7))/6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1075 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1076 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1077 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1078 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1080 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1081 &:= (9 \times (8 + ((7 - 6)^5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1082 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1083 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1084 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1085 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1086 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - C(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1087 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((C(6)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1088 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1089 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1090 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1091 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1092 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6)) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1093 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + C(5))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1094 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1095 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1096 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1097 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1098 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6)/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1099 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1100 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1101 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - C(5 + 4)))/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1102 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1103 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1104 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1105 &:= -C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1106 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1107 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1108 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1109 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1110 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1111 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1112 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1113 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1114 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1115 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1116 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1117 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1118 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1119 &:= C(1 \times 2 + 3) + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1120 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1121 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4) + ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1122 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1123 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1124 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1125 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1126 &:= 1 + C(2 + 3) \times (-4 - 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1127 &:= (-1 + (C((2 \times 3!)) + (4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1128 &:= ((((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1129 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1130 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1131 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1132 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1133 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1134 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1135 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) + (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1136 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1137 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1138 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1139 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1140 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1141 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1142 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1143 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1144 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1145 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1146 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1147 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1148 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1149 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1150 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1111 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1112 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1113 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1114 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1115 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1116 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7)/((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1117 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1118 &:= (-9 + ((C(8 + 7) + 6)/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1119 &:= (-9 - ((C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1120 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1121 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1122 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7))/((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1123 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1124 &:= ((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1125 &:= (C((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1126 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7)/6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1127 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1128 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1129 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1130 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1131 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1132 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1133 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1134 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1135 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1136 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + C(6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1137 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1138 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1139 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1140 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1141 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6 + 5) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1142 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1143 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1144 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1145 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1146 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) + C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1147 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) + ((5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1149 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1150 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7)^6 - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1151 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3 - (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1152 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3^{\sqrt{4}}) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1153 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1154 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1155 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1156 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1157 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1158 &:= (((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + C(5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1159 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C((4 + 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1160 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1161 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1162 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1163 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1164 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1165 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1166 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1167 &:= 1 - C(2 + 3) - C(4) + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1168 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3)) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1169 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) - C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1170 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1171 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1172 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1173 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1174 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1175 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1176 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1177 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1178 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1179 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1180 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1181 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1182 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + C(5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1183 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1184 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1185 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1186 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1187 &:= (((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1188 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1189 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1190 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1151 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 - 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1152 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1153 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1154 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) - 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1155 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1156 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1157 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1158 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1159 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1160 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1161 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1162 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1163 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1164 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((C(7) - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1165 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1166 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1167 &:= 9 + (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1168 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((7 - 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1169 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1170 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1171 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1172 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1173 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1174 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) - 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1175 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1176 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1177 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1178 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1179 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1180 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1181 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1182 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1183 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1184 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1185 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1186 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1187 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1188 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1189 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1190 &:= ((-9 - (C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1191 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7+8+9))) & 1191 &:= ((-9+8+C(7+6)) - (5+C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1192 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3^4) - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) & 1192 &:= ((((-9+C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1193 &:= 1 + C(2^3) + (C(4) \times (5+6) - 7-8-9) & 1193 &:= ((-9-8+(7 \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1194 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (C(4) + C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 1194 &:= (-9+C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1195 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3+4) + (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) & 1195 &:= ((-9-8+C(7)) - ((6+C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1196 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1196 &:= (-9+8+7 - ((6-C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1197 &:= (-1-2 - ((3 - (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 1197 &:= (-9 \times ((8-7-C(6+5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
1198 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 1198 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - (5+4-C(3+2+1)))))) \\
1199 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3)/C(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1199 &:= (-9-8+(C((7-(6-5))) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1200 &:= (1+2 \times 3! + \sqrt{C(4+5)}) \times (6+7+8+9) & 1200 &:= (((-9-8-7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1201 &:= (-1+2 - ((3 - (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 1201 &:= (-9+8+(C(7+6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1202 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) & 1202 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) + C(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1203 &:= (((-1+2 - C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) & 1203 &:= ((-9+8-7+C(6)) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1204 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) + (5 \times (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 1204 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + C(6)) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1205 &:= 1 + ((2+3) \times (4 \times 5 + C(6)) + 7+8+9) & 1205 &:= (C(-9+8+7) - (6+5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1206 &:= (-1 + (((2 - C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1206 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1207 &:= (-1 - (2^3 \times (4 - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 1207 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C((C(7) - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1208 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 \times (4 - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 1208 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7 \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1209 &:= (((-1+C(2 \times 3)) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1209 &:= ((-9+8+(7 \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1210 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1210 &:= (((-9 - (8-7-6)) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1211 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4+5))) + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 1211 &:= ((-9+8+C(7)) - ((6+C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1212 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4 \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9) & 1212 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1213 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) & 1213 &:= (-9+8-7+(C(6) + (5+C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1214 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) + 4)) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) & 1214 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7+6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1215 &:= 1+2 \times (C(3+4) + (5+6) \times (7+8+9)) & 1215 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1216 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4+5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) & 1216 &:= (((-9-8) \times (C(7) - C(6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1217 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1217 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + ((6-5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1218 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7+8+9))) & 1218 &:= ((-9-8-7) - (6 \times (5+4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
1219 &:= (-1 - (((2-3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1219 &:= (-9+8+((C(7) - (C(6)+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1220 &:= (((-1 \times (2-3 \times 4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1220 &:= ((-9 - (8+7+6)) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1221 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3+C(4))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) & 1221 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1222 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1222 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1223 &:= (((-1+2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) & 1223 &:= (-9+8+(C(7) + (6 - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1224 &:= (-1 - (((2+C(3)) - C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1224 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + C((7+6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1225 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1225 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1226 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) & 1226 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1227 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) & 1227 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1228 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) - (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 1228 &:= (-9-8 - ((C(7) \times (6 - (5+4))) - C(3+2+1))) \\
1229 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) - 4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1229 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1230 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (3^4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1231 &:= 1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1232 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1233 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1234 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1235 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1236 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1237 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1238 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1239 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3)/C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1240 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1241 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1242 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1243 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 - C(4) + C(5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1244 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1245 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1246 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1247 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1248 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1249 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1250 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1251 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1252 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3)/4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1253 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1254 &:= (-1 + (((2 - C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1255 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1256 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1257 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1258 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1259 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1260 &:= (1 - 2 - C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1261 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1262 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + 4)) + (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1263 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1264 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1265 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1266 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1267 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1268 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1269 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1230 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1231 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7)^6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1232 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1233 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1234 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1235 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1236 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1237 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1238 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1239 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1240 &:= (((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1241 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1242 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1243 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1244 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1245 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1246 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1247 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1248 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1249 &:= ((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1250 &:= (C((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1251 &:= (9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1252 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1253 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1254 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - 6) + C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1255 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
1256 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1257 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1258 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1259 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1260 &:= (-9 - (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1261 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1262 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1263 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1264 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C(6 + 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1265 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1266 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1267 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + C(6) - (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1268 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1269 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1270 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1271 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1272 &:= ((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1273 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1274 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1275 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1276 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1277 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1278 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1279 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1280 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1281 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - ((4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1282 &:= 1 + 2 \times (C(3) - C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8) + 9 \\
1283 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1284 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1285 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1286 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1287 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times 4) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1288 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - ((C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1289 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1290 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1291 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 - C(4) + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1292 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1293 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1294 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1295 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1296 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1297 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1298 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3 + 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1299 &:= 1 - (2 + 3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8) - 9) \\
1300 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1301 &:= (C((-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1302 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - 3) \times 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1303 &:= (((-1 - (2 - 3 + 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1304 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1305 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3 - 4)) + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1306 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1307 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{34}) \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1308 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{34}) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1309 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1270 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1271 &:= (-9 - ((C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1272 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1273 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1274 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1275 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1276 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1277 &:= ((((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6) - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1278 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1279 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1280 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1281 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1282 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1283 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6) - (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1284 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7))/6) + (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1285 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + C(7))/6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1286 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1287 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C((7 - (6 - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1288 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1289 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1290 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1291 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7 - 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1292 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times C(6)) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1293 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1294 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1295 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1296 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1297 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1298 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1299 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6)))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1300 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1301 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1302 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1303 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1304 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1305 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1306 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7))/(6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1307 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1308 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1309 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1310 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times 4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1310 &:= (((-9+8+C(7)) - (C(6)-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1311 &:= (((-1-(2-(3+4))) + C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1311 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times C(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
1312 &:= (((-1 \times (2-(3+4))) + C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1312 &:= ((-9+C(((8-7) \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1313 &:= (-1+(2 \times 3 \times (C(4)+(C(5)+6+7+8+9)))) & 1313 &:= ((-9+8-7+C(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1314 &:= (1+2) \times (C(3+4)+C(5)-(6+7+8+9)) & 1314 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + C(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1315 &:= (((-1+2+3+4)+C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1315 &:= ((-9-8+C(7)) - (6+5-C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1316 &:= (((-1-2+3 \times 4)+C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1316 &:= (-9+8-((C(7) \times 6) - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1317 &:= (-1-2-((3^4-C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1317 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1318 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3^4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1318 &:= ((-9-8+(C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
1319 &:= (-1+(((C(2 \times 3)+4)/5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1319 &:= (-9+8+((C(7)-(C(6)-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1320 &:= (-((-1+2) \times 3)^4 + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9) & 1320 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7 + C(6)) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1321 &:= (-1+2-((3^4-C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1321 &:= (-9+8+(C(7+6)+(C(5)-C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1322 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (4 - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1322 &:= (-9+C(((8-7)^{65} + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1323 &:= ((((-1+2+3) \times 4) + C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1323 &:= (-9+8-7+C((6-(5-(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1324 &:= (-1+2+(C(3)+((4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 1324 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + C((6-(5-(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1325 &:= (-1+2-(C(3)+(4-(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) & 1325 &:= (((-9+(C(8) \times 7))/(6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1326 &:= (((-1+(2+3) \times 4) + C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 1326 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (C(6)-(5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1327 &:= (-1-(C(2-3+4)-(C(5+6)+7+8+9))) & 1327 &:= (((-9+8+7)+C(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1328 &:= (-1 \times (C(2-3+4) - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1328 &:= (-9-(((C(8)-C(7+6))/5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1329 &:= (-1+(2 \times (3+4) \times (C(5)-(6+7+8+9)))) & 1329 &:= ((-9+C((8-7+6))) - (5-C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1330 &:= ((-1+2-(C(3)-C(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1330 &:= (-9+8+C(((7-6)^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1331 &:= C(((((-1-2-3) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 1331 &:= C((-9-(8-(7+6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1332 &:= (-1-(C(2+3)-(C(4+5)+C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 1332 &:= (-9+(C(((8-7) \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1333 &:= (-1+2-(C(3)-(4+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) & 1333 &:= (-9+8-7+(C(6+5)+4+3+2+1)) \\
1334 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1334 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (C(6+5)+4+3+2+1)) \\
1335 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3) \times 4) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1335 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1336 &:= (C(-1+2+3)+((C(4)-5-6) \times (7+8+9))) & 1336 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (C(6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1337 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1337 &:= (-9-8+(C(7)+((6+5)+C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1338 &:= (((-1+C(2+3))/4) + (C(5+6)-(7+8+9))) & 1338 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times ((6+5-4)+C(3+2+1))) \\
1339 &:= (1-2-3) \times 4 + C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1339 &:= (-9+(C((8-7+6)) + (5+C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1340 &:= ((-1-(2 \times (3+4))) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1340 &:= ((-9-8+7) + (6 \times ((5+4)+C(3+2+1)))) \\
1341 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1341 &:= 9+8-7+C((6-(5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1342 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) - 4) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1342 &:= (-9-(C(8)+((7 \times C(6)) - C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1343 &:= (-1-(2 \times (C(3)-(C(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))) & 1343 &:= (C(((9+8+7+6)-5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1344 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3)-(C(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))) & 1344 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (C(6)+5+4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
1345 &:= (((-1+2^3+4) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1345 &:= ((-9+8 \times (7+6)) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1346 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3+4)) + (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) & 1346 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times C(6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1347 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) + (5-(6+7+8+9))) & 1347 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (C(6+5)+4+3+2+1)) \\
1348 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1348 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) + C(6+5)) - (C(4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
1349 &:= 1-2+C(3) \times (4 \times 5+6+7+8+9) & 1349 &:= (-9+C(8)-((7+6+5)-(4 \times C(3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1350 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1351 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1352 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1353 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1354 &:= (-1 + (C(((2 + 3 - 4) \times (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1355 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{34}) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1356 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1357 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1358 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1359 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1360 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1361 &:= (C((-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1362 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1363 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1364 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1365 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + C(4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1366 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1367 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1368 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1369 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + C(4)) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1370 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1371 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1372 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1373 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1374 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1375 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1376 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1377 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1378 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1379 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1380 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - C(4))) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1381 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1382 &:= (C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1383 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1384 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1385 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1386 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1387 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1388 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1389 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4 \times C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1350 &:= (9 \times (C(8) + 7 + 6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1351 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7 + C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1352 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1353 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1354 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1355 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 + (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1356 &:= (-9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1357 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1358 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1359 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1360 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1361 &:= ((-9 \times C(8) - C(7 + 6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1362 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1364 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1365 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 + 6) + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1366 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1367 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1368 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1369 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 - (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1370 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) + C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1371 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1372 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1373 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1374 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1375 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1376 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1377 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - 6) + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1378 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1379 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1380 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1381 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1382 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1383 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1384 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1385 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1386 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1387 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6)))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1388 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1389 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1390 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1391 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1392 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1393 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1394 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1395 &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1396 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1397 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1398 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1399 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1400 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1401 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1402 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1403 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1404 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1405 &:= (((-1 + 2^3 + 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1406 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1407 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1408 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1409 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C((3 \times (4 + 5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1410 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1411 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1412 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1413 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1414 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1415 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1416 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1417 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1418 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1419 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1420 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1421 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1422 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1423 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1424 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1425 &:= ((-1 + 2^3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1426 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1427 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1428 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1429 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3) + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1390 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1391 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + 6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1392 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1393 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) / 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1394 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1395 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1396 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1397 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1398 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) / (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1399 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1400 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1401 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1402 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1403 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6)))) / 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1404 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1405 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1406 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1407 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1408 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1409 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + 6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1410 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 + C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1411 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1412 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1413 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1414 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1415 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1416 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1417 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1418 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1419 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1420 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1421 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1422 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1423 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1424 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - 6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1425 &:= ((9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1426 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1427 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1428 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1429 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1430 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1431 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1432 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1433 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1434 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1435 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1436 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1437 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1438 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - 4 - 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1439 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1440 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1441 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1442 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 + 3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1443 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1444 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1445 &:= 1 - 2 + C(3) + C(4) + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1446 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1447 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1448 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1449 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1450 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1451 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1452 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1453 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1454 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1455 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1456 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1457 &:= (-1 + (2 \times C(((3 + 4 + 5) - 6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1458 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1459 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4 + 5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1460 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1461 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1462 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1463 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1464 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1465 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1466 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - C(4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1467 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1468 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1469 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1430 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 + C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1431 &:= ((-9 \times C(((8 - 7) \times 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1432 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7 + 6))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1433 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1434 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4))))/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1435 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1436 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1437 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1438 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1439 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
1440 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7 + 6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1441 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1442 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1443 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1444 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1445 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1446 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - C(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1447 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1448 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1449 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1450 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1451 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1452 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1453 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C((7 + 6 + 5)))/4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1454 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1455 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1456 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1457 &:= (-9 + (C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1458 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1459 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1460 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1461 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1462 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5 - 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1463 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C((7 + 6 + 5))/4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1464 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7 + 6))/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1465 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1466 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1467 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1468 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1469 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1470 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9) \\
1471 &:= ((-1+2 + ((3 \times 4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1472 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1473 &:= (((-1-2 \times 3) \times (4+5 - C(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
1474 &:= (-1 + ((2+3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1475 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1476 &:= (C(-1+2 \times 3) - (4 - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1477 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1478 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5+6 - (7+8+9))))) \\
1479 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) \times ((4+5) \times 6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1480 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1481 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1482 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1483 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1484 &:= (C(-1+2 \times 3) + (4 + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1485 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
1486 &:= (C((-1+2^3+4)) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1487 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) \times (4-5-6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1488 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) \times (4-5-6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
1489 &:= ((-1+2 + C(3+4+5)) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1490 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
1491 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
1492 &:= ((-1+2 + ((3 \times 4) \times C(5))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
1493 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + C(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1494 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1495 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))))) \\
1496 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1497 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1498 &:= ((-1+2^3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1499 &:= 1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4)) \times (5+6) + 7+8) + 9 \\
1500 &:= ((-1+2+3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1501 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1502 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + C(4+5)))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
1503 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((C(4) + (5-6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1504 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1505 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1506 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (C(4) - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1507 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6 - (7+8+9))))) \\
1508 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7+8+9) \\
1509 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (4 \times C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1470 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1471 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + (C(6)/(5+4))) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
1472 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + (6 + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1473 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1474 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
1475 &:= (((-9+8 \times (7+6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1476 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (C(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
1477 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + (C(6+5) - (C(4) + 3+2+1))) \\
1478 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (C(6) + C(5))) \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1480 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1481 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1482 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1483 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + C(6) - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1484 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times C(6))) - C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
1485 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7+6+5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1486 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1487 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
1488 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
1489 &:= (((-9+8+7) + C(6+5)) - (C(4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
1490 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1491 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
1492 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1493 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 \times (5+4 - C(3+2+1))))) \\
1494 &:= (-9+8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1495 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C((7+6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1496 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1497 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - (6-5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1498 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7-6) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1499 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7-6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1500 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1501 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1502 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7-6)^5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1503 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) + (((7-6)^5) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1504 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) + (((7-6)^5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1505 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1506 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
1507 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7-6-5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1508 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7-6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1509 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - (6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1510 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times C((5 \times 6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
1511 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1512 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1513 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4+5) - C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1514 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
1515 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4+5) - C(6))) - (7+8+9) \\
1516 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3^4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1517 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3 + 4) \times C(5))) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
1518 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (4 - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1519 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1520 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1521 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times C(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1522 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1523 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1524 &:= (-1 - ((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1525 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1526 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1527 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1528 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1529 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) - C(4))) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1530 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1531 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1532 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3+4)) \times 5)) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
1533 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1534 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9))) \\
1535 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) \times (4-5-6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
1536 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) \times (4-5-6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
1537 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1538 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1539 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times C(4+5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1540 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3+4) + (5 \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1541 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + C(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1542 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
1543 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1544 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1545 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1546 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1547 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1548 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1549 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1510 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1511 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C((7+6-5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1512 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1513 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7+6) \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1514 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1515 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7-6) \times 5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1516 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1517 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1518 &:= 9 - 8 + ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1519 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1520 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7-6))) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1521 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7+6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1522 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1523 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 - ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
1524 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1525 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - C(6))) - ((C(5) \times 4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
1526 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1527 &:= (-9 - (C(8) \times (7 - (6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1528 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1529 &:= (((-9 \times (8-7-6)) \times C(5)) - (4^{3+2+1})) \\
1530 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1531 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((C(7+6) + C(5)) \times 4) / (3+2+1))) \\
1532 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1533 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6))) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1534 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
1535 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - C(6)))) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1536 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1537 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1538 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1539 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1540 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7+6))) / 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1541 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1542 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1543 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1544 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1545 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1546 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1547 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1548 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1549 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1550 &:= ((-1 - (C(2+3) - C(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1551 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times ((4+5) + C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1552 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4) + ((5 \times C(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
1553 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1554 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1555 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((C(4) - (5-6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1556 &:= (((-1+2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1557 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1558 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1559 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1560 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + 4 - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1561 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1562 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
1563 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1564 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1565 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1566 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (4 - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1567 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))) \\
1568 &:= (C((-1+2+3+4)) + ((5 \times C(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
1569 &:= ((-1 + (C((2+3) \times 4)/5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1570 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) \\
1571 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1572 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1573 &:= (C(((2+3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1574 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) \\
1575 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1576 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1577 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1578 &:= (C(((2+3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1579 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1580 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3+4)) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1581 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1582 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3+4+5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1583 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1584 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3))/4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1585 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1586 &:= ((-1 - (C(2+3) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1587 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1588 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1589 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1550 &:= ((((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1551 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1552 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1553 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1554 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1555 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1556 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7))/6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1557 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1558 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1559 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1560 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1561 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1562 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1563 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1564 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1565 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) + C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1566 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + C(7))) + C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1567 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + 6) - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1568 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1569 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1570 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1571 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1572 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1573 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1574 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1575 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1576 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1577 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1578 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1579 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1580 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1581 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1582 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1583 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times C(7)) + C(6))/5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1584 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1585 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1586 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1587 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1588 &:= ((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) - 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1589 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) - ((5 \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1590 &:= (-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (-4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1591 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1592 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1593 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1594 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1595 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1596 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1597 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1598 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1599 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1600 &:= ((C(C((-1 - 2 + 3))) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1601 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1602 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1603 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1604 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1605 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1606 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((C(4) - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1607 &:= (-1 + 2^3 - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1608 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (4 - 5 - 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1609 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1610 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1611 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1612 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1613 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1614 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1615 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1616 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1617 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1618 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1619 &:= 1 \times 2 - C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1620 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1621 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1622 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1623 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1624 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1625 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1626 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1627 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1628 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1629 &:= (-1 + ((C((2 + 3) \times 4) / 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1590 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1591 &:= (9 - (8 \times (C(7) + 6))) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1592 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1593 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1594 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1595 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1596 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1597 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7) \times 6) / 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1598 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1599 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1600 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1601 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1602 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - C(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1603 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1604 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1605 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1606 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1607 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1608 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + C(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1609 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (C(6) - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1610 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1611 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1612 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1613 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1614 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1615 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1616 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1617 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1618 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1619 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1620 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1621 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1622 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1623 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + 6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1624 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1625 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1626 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1627 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1628 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1629 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + C(5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1630 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1631 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1632 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1633 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1634 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1635 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1636 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1637 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1638 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1639 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1640 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1641 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4) \times (C(5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1642 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1643 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1644 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1645 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1646 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1647 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1648 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1649 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1650 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1651 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1652 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1653 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1654 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1655 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1656 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1657 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1658 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1659 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3 + C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8) - 9)) \\
1660 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (C(4) \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1661 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1662 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1663 &:= 1 \times 2 + C(3 \times 4) + C(5) - C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1664 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1665 &:= (((C(-1 + 2^3) - 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1666 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1667 &:= 1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4) - C(5) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1668 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1669 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1630 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - C(6)) / 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1631 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1632 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1633 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1634 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1635 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1636 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1637 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1638 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1639 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) / 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1640 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1641 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1642 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1643 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1644 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1645 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1646 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1647 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times C(6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1648 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1649 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1650 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1651 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1652 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1653 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1654 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1655 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1656 &:= (-9 \times 8 + C((C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1657 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1658 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1659 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1660 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1661 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1662 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1663 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1664 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1665 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1666 &:= 9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1667 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1668 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1669 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1670 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1671 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1672 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1673 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1674 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1675 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1676 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1677 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1678 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1679 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1680 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1681 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1682 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1683 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1684 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((C(4) - (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1685 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1686 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1687 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1688 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
1689 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1690 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1691 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1692 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1693 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1694 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1695 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1696 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1697 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1698 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1699 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1700 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1701 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1702 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1703 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1704 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1705 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1706 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times 5) - (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1707 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1708 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1709 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1670 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1671 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1672 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6) / 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1673 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1674 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1675 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1676 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1677 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1678 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1679 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1680 &:= (((-9 + C((8 - 7 + 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1681 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1682 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1683 &:= 9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1684 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1685 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((C(7) - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1686 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1687 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6 - (5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1688 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5))) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1689 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1690 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (C(7) - 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1691 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1692 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1693 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1694 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1695 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1696 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1697 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1698 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (C((6 + 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1699 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1700 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1701 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1702 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1703 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1704 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) - (C(6) - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1705 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1706 &:= (-9 - (C((8 - 7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1707 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1708 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1709 &:= ((-9 + C((8 - (7 - 6 - 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1710 &:= (((-1+2-3) + C(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
1711 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1712 &:= (-1-2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
1713 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
1714 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
1715 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1716 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1717 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
1718 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3+4)) \times 5) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
1719 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1720 &:= ((-1+2 + C(3+4+5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
1721 &:= (-1-2 \times 3 + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1722 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1723 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1724 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1725 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1726 &:= (-1 \times 2 + C((3 - ((4+5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1727 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1728 &:= C(((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1729 &:= (-1+2 + C((3 - ((4+5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1730 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3+4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1731 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1732 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1733 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + (4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)) \\
1734 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3+4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1735 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3+4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1736 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times ((4 \times (5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
1737 &:= (-1-2 - (((3+C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1738 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3+C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1739 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) + C(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1740 &:= ((-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4) - 5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1741 &:= (-1+2 - (((3+C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1742 &:= (-1-2 + ((C(3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1743 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1744 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1745 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1746 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1747 &:= 1 \times 2 + (C(3+4) \times 5 + 6+7+8+9) \\
1748 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4^5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
1749 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1710 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - 6 - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1711 &:= (-9 - 8 + C((C(7) - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1712 &:= (((-9+8+7+6) \times C(5)) - (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
1713 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1714 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
1715 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7-6)) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1716 &:= (-9 - (((8 + C(7)) - 6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1717 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1718 &:= (C(((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1719 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + (C(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1720 &:= (-9 + (C((8 + ((7-6)^5))) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1721 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + C(6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1722 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5+4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
1723 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1724 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1725 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7-6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1726 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1727 &:= (-9+8 + C((C(7) - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1728 &:= C((-9 + ((8-7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1729 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - (7-6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1730 &:= (((-9+8 + (C(7)+6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1731 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1732 &:= (-9+8-7 + ((6 \times 5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
1733 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1734 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7+6 - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1735 &:= ((-9 + C((8+7 - (6-5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1736 &:= (-9+8 - (C(7) - ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1737 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1738 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1739 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) + (6+5 - C(4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
1740 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7+6 - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1741 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) \times 6) \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1742 &:= (-9+8-7 + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1743 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
1744 &:= (-9+8 - ((C(7)+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1745 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((C(7)+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1746 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)) - C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1747 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
1748 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
1749 &:= (-9+8 - (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1750 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1750 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1751 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1751 &:= 9 - 8 - (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1752 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1752 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1753 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1753 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1754 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1754 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1755 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1755 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1756 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1756 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1757 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1757 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1758 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1758 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1759 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1759 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1760 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1760 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1761 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1761 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1762 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1762 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1763 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1763 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1764 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1764 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1765 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1765 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1766 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 1766 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1767 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1767 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1768 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1768 &:= (((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) - 5) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1769 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1769 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1770 &:= ((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1770 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1771 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1771 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1772 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1772 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1773 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1773 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1774 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1774 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1775 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1775 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (C(6) + C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1776 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1776 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1777 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1777 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1778 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1778 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1779 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1779 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1780 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1780 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1781 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1781 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1782 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times 4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1782 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C((7 - (6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1783 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1783 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1784 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1784 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1785 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1785 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1786 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1786 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1787 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 1787 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1788 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1788 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1789 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + ((5 \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1789 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1790 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (C(3) - C(4))) - C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 1790 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1791 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 \times (C(4) + C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1791 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1792 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - ((C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1792 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1793 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + ((C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1793 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (6 - C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1794 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1794 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1795 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1795 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6 + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1796 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1796 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1797 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1797 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1798 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1798 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1799 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C((7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1800 &:= ((1 - 2)^3 - C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1800 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1801 &:= 1 + (2^3 + C(4)) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1801 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1802 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1802 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1803 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1803 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1804 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1804 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1805 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1805 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7))/6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1806 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1806 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1807 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1807 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1808 &:= (-1 - (C((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1808 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1809 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1809 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1810 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 1810 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1811 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1811 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1812 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1812 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1813 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + 4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 1813 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (C(6) + 5))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1814 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1814 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1815 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1815 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1816 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - ((5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1816 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times (6 - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1817 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1817 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1818 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1818 &:= 9 \times ((8 - 7 + C(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1819 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 1819 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1820 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times C(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1820 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1821 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1821 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1822 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1822 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1823 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1823 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1824 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1824 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1825 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1825 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1826 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1826 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1827 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1827 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1828 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1828 &:= (9 \times (8 + C(7))) - C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1829 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1829 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1830 &:= (-C(-1-2+3+4) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
1831 &:= (((-1+2)^3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1832 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3+4) + ((5 \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
1833 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1834 &:= (-1+2+3 - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1835 &:= (-1+2 \times 3 - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1836 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times (4+5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
1837 &:= (-1+2^3 - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1838 &:= (-1-2 - (C(3+4) + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1839 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) \times (4+5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1840 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1841 &:= (-1-2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
1842 &:= (-1 + (((2+C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
1843 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (((4+5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
1844 &:= (((-1-2+C(3+4)) \times 5) + 6 \times (7+8+9)) \\
1845 &:= (1+2 \times (3+4)) \times C(5) - (6+7+8+9) \\
1846 &:= 1 + (2+3) \times (4 + (C(5) + C(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1847 &:= (-1 - (2^3 \times (4+5 - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
1848 &:= (1-2+3+C(4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9) \\
1849 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1850 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) \times (4+5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1851 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1852 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
1853 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1854 &:= ((-1-2+C(3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1855 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1856 &:= (C(-1+2+3) \times (C(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1857 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1858 &:= ((-1+2+C(3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1859 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3 - (4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1860 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + 4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1861 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1862 &:= ((-1+C(2^3)) - (4 - (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1863 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1864 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((C(4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1865 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (((4+5) \times C(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
1866 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4)) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
1867 &:= (C((-1+2+3+4)) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
1868 &:= ((-1 + ((2+C(3)) \times C(4))) - (5+6 - (7+8+9))) \\
1869 &:= (-1-2 + ((3 + (C(4) + 5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
1830 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1831 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + C(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1832 &:= (-9 - (C(8+7) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1833 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1834 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) + C((((7-6)^5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1835 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6+5 - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1836 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1837 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1838 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6))) - (C(5+4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
1839 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
1840 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1841 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))) \\
1842 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7+6 - C(5+4)))) + 3+2+1) \\
1843 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) + (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1844 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1845 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7-6) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1846 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1847 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1848 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (6 - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1849 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6+5) \times (C(4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
1850 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1851 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1852 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (C(6+5) + (4 \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
1853 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (C(6) + 5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
1854 &:= ((-9 - C(8+7+6)) / (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1855 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1856 &:= (((-9-8-7) \times (6 - C(5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1857 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1858 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times (5+4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
1859 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - C(6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1860 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + (6 + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1861 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (C(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1862 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1863 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times C(6)) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1864 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1865 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6+5) + (4 \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
1866 &:= (-9 - (C(8+7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1867 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - ((C(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1868 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7+6+5))) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
1869 &:= (((-9 + C(((8-7) \times 6))) \times (5+4)) + 3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1870 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1871 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + (C(4) - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1872 &:= 1 + C(2^3) + 4 + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1873 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1874 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1875 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - C(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1876 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1877 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1878 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1879 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1880 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1881 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1882 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1883 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1884 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1885 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1886 &:= 1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1887 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1888 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1889 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3)/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1890 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1891 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1892 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1893 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1894 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1895 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1896 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1897 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1898 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1899 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1900 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1901 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4) \times 5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1902 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1903 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((C(4) - (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1904 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1905 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1906 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1907 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (C(4 + 5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1908 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4 + 5) + C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1909 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5) - C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1870 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1871 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1872 &:= (-9 \times (8 - C((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1873 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1874 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1875 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1876 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1877 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1878 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1879 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
1880 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1881 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1882 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C((7 - (6 - 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1883 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1884 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1885 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1886 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1887 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1888 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1889 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1890 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1891 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 - 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1892 &:= (((-9 + 8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) / (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1893 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1894 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1896 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1897 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) / (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1898 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times (C(5) \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1899 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1900 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1901 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1902 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1903 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 - 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1904 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1905 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1906 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1907 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1908 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1909 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C((7 \times (6 + 5) - C(4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1910 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) \times 5))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) & 1910 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1911 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times C(6))) - (7+8+9) & 1911 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) - (6+5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
1912 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (((4+5) \times C(6)) - (7+8+9)))) & 1912 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5)) - (C(4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
1913 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1913 &:= ((-9 \times C((8-7+6))) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1914 &:= (((-1-2-3) + ((4+5) \times C(6))) - (7+8+9)) & 1914 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6-C(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1915 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4+5) \times C(6))) - (7+8+9)) & 1915 &:= ((((-9+8+7) \times C(6)) + (5^4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
1916 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3+4)) \times 5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1916 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1917 &:= (-1-2 + (C((3-(4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1917 &:= (((-9+8+C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1918 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C((3-(4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1918 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (5+4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
1919 &:= (-1 + (C(((2+3+4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1919 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7+C(6) - (5+4))) + C(3+2+1))) \\
1920 &:= (C((-1 \times (2+3-4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 1920 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-C(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1921 &:= (-1+2 + (C((3-(4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1921 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7+6) + (5 - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
1922 &:= (-1 - (((2+3+4) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9))) & 1922 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1923 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times C(6))) - (7+8+9) & 1923 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (C((6+5-4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
1924 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + ((C(4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 1924 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7-C(6))) + (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1925 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) & 1925 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1926 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) & 1926 &:= (-9 - ((8+7) \times (6 - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1927 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3+4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1927 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1928 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3+4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) + C(5))) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1929 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 1929 &:= (((-9-8 + C(7)) \times 6) - C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
1930 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) & 1930 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-C(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1931 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 1931 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7+6)) + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1))) \\
1932 &:= (((-1+2 \times 3)^4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) & 1932 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1933 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1933 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) \times 5 - (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
1934 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1934 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + C(5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1935 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (C((4+5-6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 1935 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1936 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - ((C(4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7+8+9))) & 1936 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7+6) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
1937 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((C(3!) \times 4) + 5!))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1937 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1938 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4+5))) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 1938 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7-6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1939 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (((4+5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) & 1939 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C((6+5-4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
1940 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3+4)) \times 5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 1940 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-C(6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1941 &:= ((-1-2) \times (((3-C(4)) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) & 1941 &:= (((-9-8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1942 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1942 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1943 &:= (C(-1+2^3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1943 &:= ((-9/(8+7-6)) + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1))) \\
1944 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1944 &:= (-9 \times (C(8+7) - (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1945 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1945 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1946 &:= 1 - C(2+3) + (C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9) & 1946 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times (6 + C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1947 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1947 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(((7-6) \times (5+4)))))) - (3+2+1)) \\
1948 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times C(4+5))) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 1948 &:= (C(((9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + C(5))) + (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
1949 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3 + C(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1949 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + ((C(6+5) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1950 &:= (1 + C(2 + 3 + 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1951 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1952 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1953 &:= ((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1954 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1955 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1956 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1957 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1958 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((4^5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1959 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1960 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1961 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1962 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1963 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - (4^5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1964 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1965 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1966 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1967 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1968 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1969 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1970 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1971 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1972 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1973 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1974 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1975 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1976 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1977 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1978 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1979 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1980 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3 - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1981 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1982 &:= 1 \times 2 + (-3 + C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1983 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1984 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1985 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1986 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1987 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1988 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1989 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1950 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1951 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1952 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1953 &:= (-9 \times ((8 / (7 - (6 + 5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1954 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1955 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times C(7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1956 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1957 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1958 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1959 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1960 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1961 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1962 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C((7 - (6 - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1963 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1964 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1965 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1966 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1967 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1968 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1969 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1970 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1971 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1972 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1973 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1974 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1975 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1976 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1977 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1978 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1979 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C((6 + 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1980 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1981 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1982 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1983 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1984 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1985 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1986 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1987 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1988 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1989 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1990 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1991 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
1992 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4+5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
1993 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3+4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8) - 9) \\
1994 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - 4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1995 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1996 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4+5))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
1997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4+5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
1998 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
1999 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3+4) - C(5+6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
2000 &:= 1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6) - (7+8) - 9) \\
2001 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2002 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2003 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2004 &:= (((C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) - 5) \times 6) - (7+8+9)) \\
2005 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2006 &:= -C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
2007 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2008 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2009 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2010 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2011 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2012 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2013 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3+4+C(5)) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2014 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + (3+4+5)))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2015 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2016 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2017 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3+4+C(5)) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2018 &:= ((((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
2019 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2020 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2021 &:= (-1 - (C((2^3 + 4)) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2022 &:= (1 - 2) \times C(3 \times 4) + C(5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
2023 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2024 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2025 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
2026 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + C(4)) \times (5+6) + 7+8+9 \\
2027 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2028 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (C(4+5) - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2029 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1990 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7+6)) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1991 &:= (-9 - ((8/(7-6-5)) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1992 &:= ((((-9+8+7) + C(6)) \times (5+4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
1993 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C((6+5-4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
1994 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
1995 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1996 &:= (-9 - (((8+7-C(6)) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
1997 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1998 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7+6) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1999 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) + C(5))) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2000 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times C(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2001 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2002 &:= (((-9+8+C(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2003 &:= ((-9+8+(C(7) \times 6)) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2004 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2005 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - ((6+5) \times (4 + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
2006 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2007 &:= ((-9+8+(C(7) \times 6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2008 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2009 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6+5-4) \times C(3+2+1))) \\
2010 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7+6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2011 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7) + (C((6+5-4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
2012 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2013 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
2014 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6-5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2015 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2016 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2017 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)/5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2018 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6-5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2019 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times C(6)) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
2020 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2021 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2022 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2023 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2024 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6-5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2025 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2026 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2027 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 4) - C(3+2+1)))))) \\
2028 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2029 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2030 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2031 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) + (5+6-(7+8+9))) \\
2032 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (((4+5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2033 &:= ((-1 + (2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2034 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + (5+6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2035 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3+4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2036 &:= (C((-1-2+3 \times 4)) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2037 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3-C(4)) \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2038 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((C(4) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2039 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) + (C(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2040 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3+4))/5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2041 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2042 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2043 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times C(4+5)) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2044 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2045 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2046 &:= (-1-2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4)+5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2047 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2048 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (5+6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2049 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4)+5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2050 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4)+5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2051 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (C(3+4) + 5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
2052 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4)+5) + (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2053 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2054 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2055 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6)))) + 7+8+9) \\
2056 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2057 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) - (5+6-(7+8+9))) \\
2058 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2059 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3+4) \times (5 \times 6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2060 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - (5+6-(7+8+9))) \\
2061 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2062 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2063 &:= (-1-2 \times 3 + ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2064 &:= (-1 - ((2+3 - C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2065 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2066 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2067 &:= ((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2068 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2069 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3+4))/5) \times (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2030 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2031 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2032 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2033 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7+6))/5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2034 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2035 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2036 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (C(6) + C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2037 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2038 &:= ((-9-8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5+4-(3+2+1))) \\
2039 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2040 &:= (((-9+8-7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2041 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6) + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
2042 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2043 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2044 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7-6) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2045 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2046 &:= ((-9-8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2047 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2048 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (6 + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2049 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times (7-6-5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2050 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) - 6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2051 &:= (-9 - ((8+7 - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2052 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2053 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(((7-6) \times 5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2054 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5+4-(3+2+1))) \\
2055 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2056 &:= (-9-8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2057 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2058 &:= (C((-9+8 - (7 - (6+5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
2059 &:= (-9-8 + ((C(7) - (6 - (5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2060 &:= (((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2061 &:= ((-9+8 + C(7+6)) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2062 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2063 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 - (6-5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2064 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2065 &:= ((-9-8 + C(7+6)) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2066 &:= (-9 - (((8-7 - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2067 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
2068 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2069 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2070 &:= ((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2071 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2072 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times 4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2073 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2074 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2075 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + (C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2076 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2077 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2078 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2079 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2080 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2081 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2082 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2083 &:= C(1 \times 2^3) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2084 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2085 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2086 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2087 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2088 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2089 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2090 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2091 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (((4 + C(5)) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2092 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 + 3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2093 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2094 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2095 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2096 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2097 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2098 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2099 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2100 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2101 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3! \times (C(4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2102 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2103 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2104 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2105 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2106 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2107 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2108 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2109 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2070 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2071 &:= (-9 - ((8 - C((7 - (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2072 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2073 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2074 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2075 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2076 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2077 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2078 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2079 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2080 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2081 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2082 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2083 &:= 9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2084 &:= ((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2085 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2086 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2087 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2088 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2089 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2090 &:= 9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2091 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2092 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2093 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2094 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2095 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2096 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2097 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (((C(7) + 6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2098 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2099 &:= 9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2100 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2101 &:= (-9 + ((C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2102 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2103 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2104 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2105 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2106 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2107 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2108 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2109 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2110 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3+4) + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2111 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2112 &:= C(1 \times 2^3) + C(4) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2113 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2114 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2115 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2116 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2117 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 - C(4) - (C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2118 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3+4) + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2119 &:= (-1 - ((2+3)! - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2120 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2121 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3+4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2122 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3+4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2123 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2124 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2125 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2126 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3+4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2127 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (C(4) \times (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2128 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2129 &:= (-1 - (((C(2 \times 3)/4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2130 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2131 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + 4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2132 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2133 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2134 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2135 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2136 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2137 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2138 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2139 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2140 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2141 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2142 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2143 &:= C(1 \times 2^3) \times 4 + C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2144 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2145 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4+5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2146 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4+5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2147 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2148 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4+5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2149 &:= (-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2110 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7+6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2111 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7 + C(6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2112 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2113 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6+5)))/4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
2114 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2115 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7)))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2116 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2117 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + (7 + 6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2118 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2119 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (6 + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2120 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2121 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2122 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2123 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2124 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2125 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2126 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7+6)) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2127 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2128 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
2129 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - ((6+5) + C(4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
2130 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7+6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2131 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2132 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2133 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) \times C(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2134 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2135 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2136 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2137 &:= ((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (5^4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
2138 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2139 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2140 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2141 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times 6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2142 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 + 5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2143 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2144 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2145 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (C(6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2146 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7+6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2147 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2148 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 - (C(6+5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2149 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2150 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2151 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4 + 5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2152 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2153 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2154 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2155 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2156 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2157 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2158 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2159 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2160 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2161 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2162 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2163 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2164 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2165 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2166 &:= ((-1 + C(((C(2^3)/C(4)) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2167 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2168 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2169 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2170 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2171 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2172 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2173 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2174 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2175 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2176 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4 + 5))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2177 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2178 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4 + 5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2179 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2180 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2181 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2182 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2183 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2184 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2185 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2186 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2187 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2188 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2189 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2150 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2151 &:= (-9 + (C(((8 - 7)^6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2152 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)/(7 - 6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2153 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2154 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2155 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2156 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2157 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2158 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2159 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2160 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2161 &:= (((-9 \times C(8) - 7) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2162 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + 5 - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2163 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2164 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2165 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2166 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2167 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2168 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + (6 - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2169 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times C(7)) + C(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2170 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2171 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2172 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2173 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2174 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2175 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2176 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2177 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C(((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
2178 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2179 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2180 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2181 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2182 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2183 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2184 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2185 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2186 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2187 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2188 &:= (-9 + C((8 - ((7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2189 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2190 &:= ((C(-1+2+3)+4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2191 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (C(4+5) - 6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2192 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + C(4+5))) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2193 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4+5) - 6)) + 7+8+9 \\
2194 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2195 &:= (-1 \times 2 + C((3 - ((4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2196 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2197 &:= C((-1+2 - (C(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2198 &:= (-1+2 + C((3 - ((4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2199 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times 4) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2200 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times (4 + (5 \times 6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2201 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (5 - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2202 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2203 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4+5))) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
2204 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2205 &:= ((-1 - ((2-3) \times C(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2206 &:= 1 + (2 - 3 + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2207 &:= (-1 - ((C(2+3) + ((4-5) - C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2208 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2209 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2^3) - C(4)) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2210 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2211 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2212 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4+5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2213 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2214 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2215 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2216 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3+4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2217 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times C(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9 \\
2218 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times C(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2219 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2220 &:= (((-1+2 \times 3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2221 &:= (C((-1+2 - (3 - (4+5+6)))) + 7+8+9) \\
2222 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2223 &:= (-1 \times (C(2-3+4) + (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2224 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2225 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2226 &:= (-1 + (C(((C(2^3)/C(4)) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2227 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2228 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2229 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2190 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2191 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7+6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2192 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2193 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7+6)) - (5+4 - (3+2+1))) \\
2194 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2195 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2196 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2197 &:= C((-9+8 - (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2198 &:= (-9 + (C((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2199 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2200 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2201 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7+6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2202 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2203 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2204 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) + C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))))) \\
2205 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2206 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2207 &:= (C((-9 + (((8 \times C(7)) + 6)/C(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2208 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2209 &:= 9 + 8 + (C(7+6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2210 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2211 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2212 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2213 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) - ((6+5) \times (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2214 &:= (((-9+8+7) + C(6)) \times (5+4)) + C(3+2+1) \\
2215 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (6 \times C(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2216 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2217 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(((7+6+5) - 4)) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2218 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2219 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - ((5 \times 4) \times C(3+2+1))) \\
2220 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2221 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
2222 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + C(6)) \times (5+4)) + C(3+2+1))) \\
2223 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (6 - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2224 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7+6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2225 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 \times ((5+4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2226 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times C(6))) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2227 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + ((C(5) \times 4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2228 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6 - (5+4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
2229 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(((7+6+5) - 4)) + 3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2230 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2231 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2232 &:= (C((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2233 &:= (-1-2 \times 3 + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2234 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2235 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2236 &:= ((-1+2-C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2237 &:= (((-1+(2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5)-6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2238 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2239 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2240 &:= (C((-1-(2-(3+4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2241 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2242 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times (C(4+5) - (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2243 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2244 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2245 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2246 &:= (((-1+2^3)^4) - (C(5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
2247 &:= (-1+(2^3 + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2248 &:= (C((-1-(2-(3+4)))) - ((C(5)-C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2249 &:= (-1+((2 \times 3 + (C(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2250 &:= ((-1+2-(C(3)+C(4))) \times (5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2251 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3 + C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
2252 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (4 - ((C(5)-C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2253 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 \times C(4) - C(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
2254 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) - C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2255 &:= 1 - (2 \times (3 \times C(4) - C(5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2256 &:= (((-1-2+(C(3) \times 4)) - 5-6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2257 &:= ((-1+2) \times (3+4) - (C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2258 &:= ((-1+2+3+4) - (C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2259 &:= ((((-1+2+3) \times C(4)) - 5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2260 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((C(4) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2261 &:= (-1 + ((2+C(3)) \times (((4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2262 &:= (((((-1+2+3) \times C(4)) + C(5)) \times 6) - (7+8+9)) \\
2263 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (((4+5) \times C(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
2264 &:= (-1-2+(C(3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2265 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2266 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2267 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2268 &:= (-1+2+(C(3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2269 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) - C(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2230 &:= (-9-8+(C(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2231 &:= (-9+(C(8) + C(((C(7) - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2232 &:= (-9+(((8+C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2233 &:= ((-9-8+C(7+6)) - (5 - (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2234 &:= ((-9+(C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2235 &:= ((-9+C(8+7)) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2236 &:= (-9+(((8+7) \times C(6)) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2237 &:= (-9+(C(8) + ((C(7) - (6 \times (5+4))) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2238 &:= (-9+(C(8) + (((C(7)+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2239 &:= (-9+8+((C(7) + (6 - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2240 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2241 &:= (-9 \times ((8-7+(6 \times C(5))) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2242 &:= ((-9+(C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6+5) - (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
2243 &:= (-9+(C(8) + ((C(7) + (6+5 - C(4))) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2244 &:= ((-9+(C(8) \times 7)) - C(((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2245 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2246 &:= (-9+8+(C(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2247 &:= (-9+(C(8+7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2248 &:= (-9+C(8) - ((C(7)+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2249 &:= ((-9+8+C(7+6)) - (5 - (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2250 &:= (9-8+7-6) \times (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2251 &:= (-9+(((8+7) + C(6)) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2252 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2253 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2254 &:= ((-9+(C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2255 &:= (-9+(((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2256 &:= 9 + (C(8) + (((C(7)+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2257 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) + ((C(6)+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2258 &:= (-9+(C(8) + ((7+6) \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2259 &:= (-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2260 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2261 &:= ((-9-8) \times (((C(7) - 6 - 5)/4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
2262 &:= 9 + ((C(8) \times 7) - C(((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2263 &:= (-9-8+((7+(C(6)+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2264 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7)+C(6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2265 &:= ((-9-8 \times 7 + C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2266 &:= (-9-8 \times 7 + (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2267 &:= 9+8+(C(7+6) - (5 - (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2268 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) - (C(6) - C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
2269 &:= ((-9+((C(8+7+6) - C(5))/4)) - (3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2270 &:= (((-1+2^3) \times (C(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2271 &:= ((((-1+2+C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2272 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3)+C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2273 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3)+C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2274 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) - C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2275 &:= ((((-1+2)^3) + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2276 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3)+C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2277 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2278 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2279 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times 4 \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2280 &:= 1+2+3 \times (C(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2281 &:= 1+2 \times 3 \times 4 \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2282 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2283 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3+4) - ((5 \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
2284 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + ((4+5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2285 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((C(4)+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2286 &:= ((-1 - (C(2+3) - (4-5))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
2287 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (5 \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2288 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2289 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2290 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) + (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2291 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) + (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2292 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2293 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2294 &:= (((-1+2^3)^4) - (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2295 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2296 &:= ((-1+2^3) \times (C(4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2297 &:= ((((-1+C(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2298 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - C(4+5))) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2299 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2+3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2300 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2301 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 \times C(4) - C(5+6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
2302 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) - C(5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2303 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) - (C(4) + 5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2304 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2305 &:= (-1+2 + ((3+4+5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2306 &:= (((-1+2^3)^4) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2307 &:= (C((-1 \times (2-3 \times 4))) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2308 &:= (((-1+C(2^3)) \times 4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2309 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2270 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2271 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1))) \\
2272 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
2273 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6)))) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2274 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2275 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2276 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - ((C(6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2277 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2278 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2279 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2280 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
2281 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7+6)) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2282 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7+6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2283 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7+6)) - (C(5) + (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2284 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2285 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 \times 5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2286 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2287 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2288 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2289 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) \times (7+6+5))/4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
2290 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
2291 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2292 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
2293 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + ((7+6) \times 5)) \times 4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
2294 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + ((5+4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2295 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2296 &:= (C(-9+8+7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2297 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times (5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
2298 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2299 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) \times 6) - (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2300 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2301 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2302 &:= ((-9 \times C(8) - (7 - 6 - 5))/(4 - (3+2+1))) \\
2303 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2304 &:= (-9 \times C(8)/(7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2305 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2306 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times (C(6) + 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2307 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - C(7))) \times 6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2308 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) - ((6+5) \times (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2309 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times (5+4)))) + 3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2310 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2311 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2312 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2313 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2314 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2315 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2316 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2317 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2318 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 2319 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 2320 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 2321 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2322 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2323 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 2324 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2325 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((C(3) + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2326 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2327 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2328 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times 4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2329 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2330 &:= 1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times 4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2331 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2332 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2333 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 \times 4)) - (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2334 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2335 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2336 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2337 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4 + C(5)) \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2338 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 2339 &:= 1 - 2 \times (C(3) + 4 - 5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2340 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - 4)) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2341 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2342 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2343 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2344 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 - (C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2345 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2346 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2347 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2348 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times C(6))/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 2349 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 2310 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2311 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2312 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2313 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2314 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - C(7))) \times (6 + 5 - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2315 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2316 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2317 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (6 + 5 - C(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2318 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2319 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2320 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2321 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2322 &:= (-9 + (C(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2323 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2324 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2325 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2326 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2327 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6 + C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2328 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 - C(5))) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2329 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((C(6)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2330 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) + 6 + 5)/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2331 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2332 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2333 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2334 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) - (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2335 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - 7)) - ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2336 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2337 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2338 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2339 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2340 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2341 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2342 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 2343 &:= 9 - ((8 - (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2344 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) + C(6 + 5))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 2345 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2346 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2347 &:= ((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (5^4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 2348 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 2349 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2350 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) + C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2351 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2352 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2353 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + 4) - (C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2354 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3 + 4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2355 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2356 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2357 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2358 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2359 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2360 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2361 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2362 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2363 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2364 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2365 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2366 &:= 1 + C(2 + 3) + C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2367 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + C(5)))) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2368 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2369 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (C(3) - 4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2370 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2371 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (((C(4) \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2372 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2373 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + 4 + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2374 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2375 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2376 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2377 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2378 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2379 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + C(4)))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2380 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2381 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2382 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) + (C(5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2383 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4)))) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2384 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2385 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2386 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2387 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2388 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + C(4 + 5)) + C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2389 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2350 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2351 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2352 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2353 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2354 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2355 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2356 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2357 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - C((6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2358 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C((6 + 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2359 &:= ((-9 - C((8 - (7 - 6 - 5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
2360 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2361 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2362 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2364 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2365 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2366 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2367 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2368 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times 5) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2369 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2370 &:= (9 - ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2371 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C((6 + 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2372 &:= (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6)) \times 5) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2373 &:= ((((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2374 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2375 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6 + 5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2376 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2377 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2378 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2379 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2380 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2381 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2382 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times 6)) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2384 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2385 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 \times (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2386 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2387 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2388 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2389 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2390 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2391 &:= (((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2392 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2393 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times (C(4) + 5 + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2394 &:= (-1 + C(2+3) + 4 + 5) \times (-6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2395 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2396 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2397 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2398 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2399 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2400 &:= (1 + 2 - C(3)) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2401 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2402 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 + 4) - C((5 + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2403 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2404 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2405 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2406 &:= 1 + 2 + C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2407 &:= (1 + C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2408 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2409 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2410 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2411 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2412 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2413 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2414 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2415 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2416 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2417 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2418 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2419 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2420 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2421 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2422 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2423 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2424 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times 4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2425 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2426 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8) + 9 \\
2427 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2428 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2429 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2390 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2391 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2392 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2393 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2394 &:= (-9 \times (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2395 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2396 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2397 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2398 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2399 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2400 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2401 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 + 6 - (C(5) \times 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2402 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2403 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2404 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2405 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2406 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2407 &:= (((9 - 8) \times 7) \times C((6 + 5 - 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2408 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2409 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((C(5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2410 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2411 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2412 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2413 &:= (C(((9 - 8) + (7 + 6 + 5))) - 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2414 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2415 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2416 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2417 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - (C(6)/(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2418 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2419 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2420 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 + C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2421 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2422 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2423 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2424 &:= 9 + ((8 + 7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2425 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + C(6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2426 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2427 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2428 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2429 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2430 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) \times ((4-5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2431 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2432 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2433 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
2434 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times (3+4)) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2435 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times (3+4)) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2436 &:= (1+2) \times (3 + C(4+5)) + C(6) + 7+8+9 \\
2437 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + (3+4+5)))) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
2438 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2439 &:= (-1 - (C((2 + (3+4+5))) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2440 &:= (-1 \times (C((2 + (3+4+5))) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2441 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3+4) \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2442 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (5 + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2443 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2444 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4+5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2445 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2446 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2447 &:= 1 - 2 + (C(3) + C(4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2448 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) + 5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2449 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 + C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2450 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2451 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3^4 - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2452 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2453 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2454 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2455 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2456 &:= (-1 - ((C(2+3) + C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2457 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2+3) + C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2458 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2459 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2460 &:= ((1+2) \times C(3) - 4+5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
2461 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2462 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4 \times 5) + (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
2463 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2464 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - ((5-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2465 &:= (((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2466 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2467 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2468 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) - (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2469 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4 \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2430 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 + C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2431 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2432 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7+6) + ((5 \times 4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2433 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 \times (6+5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2434 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7+6 - ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
2435 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2436 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2437 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2438 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) - (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
2439 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2440 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2441 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2442 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C((6+5-4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
2443 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) - 7)) - (C(6) + C(5)))/(4 - (3+2+1))) \\
2444 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2445 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2446 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2447 &:= (9 - 8) \times (C(7+6) - (C(5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
2448 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C((7 - (6 - 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2449 &:= 9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2450 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2451 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) \times 5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2452 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2453 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7+6 - (5 \times C(4)))) - (3+2+1))) \\
2454 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times (6+5-4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
2455 &:= (9 - (C(8) \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2456 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2457 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2458 &:= (((-9 - ((8-7-6) \times C(5))) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
2459 &:= (((((-9+8) \times 7) \times C(6)) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
2460 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2461 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - (C(7+6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2462 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - ((5+4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
2463 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2464 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6+5) - (4 + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2465 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2466 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2467 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((6+5) \times (4 + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2468 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - (C(6) - 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2469 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2470 &:= ((-1 + C(2 - 3 + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2471 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4 \times 5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2472 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2473 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) - (C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2474 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2475 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2476 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2477 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2478 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4) \times C(5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2479 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2480 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2481 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2482 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2483 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2484 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2485 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 + C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2486 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2487 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2488 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C((4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2489 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2490 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2491 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2492 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2493 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2494 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2495 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2496 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2497 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2498 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2499 &:= (-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2500 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2501 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 + 4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2502 &:= (((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2503 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + C(4)) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2504 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + C(4)) - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2505 &:= ((((-1 + C(2^3)) - 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2506 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2507 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2508 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2509 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2^3) - 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2470 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 - C(6)))) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2471 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - (6 + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2472 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2473 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2474 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2475 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2476 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2477 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2478 &:= 9 - 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2479 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2480 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2481 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2482 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2483 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - ((5 - 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2484 &:= (-9 \times (C(8 + 7 - 6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2485 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2486 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2487 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2488 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (5 \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2489 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6 + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2490 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2491 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2492 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2493 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2494 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((5 \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2495 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2496 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2497 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2498 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2499 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2500 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2501 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2502 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2503 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2504 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2505 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2506 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2507 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2508 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(6))) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2509 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2510 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2511 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2512 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2513 &:= (((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4)) \times 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2514 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3+4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2515 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 - (C(4) - C(5+6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2516 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2517 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4 \times 5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2518 &:= (-1 - ((2+3)^4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2519 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2520 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2521 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2522 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2523 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3^4 - C(5+6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2524 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - C(5+6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2525 &:= (((-1 + (C(2+3) \times 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2526 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2527 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2528 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2529 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) \times 4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2530 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2531 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4 - (5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2532 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times 4)) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2533 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (C(4) + (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2534 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + C(4)))) \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2535 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2536 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2537 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2538 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2539 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2540 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4+5) - C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2541 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4+5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2542 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2543 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - 4 - 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2544 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2545 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2546 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2547 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3^4 - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2548 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - (C(5+6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2549 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2^3) + 4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2510 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2511 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2512 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - ((6 + 5 - 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2513 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2514 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2515 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2516 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2517 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2518 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2519 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2520 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2521 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2522 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2523 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2524 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2525 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2526 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2527 &:= (9 - 8) \times (C(7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2528 &:= (C(((((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - C(6))/(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2529 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2530 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 - 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2531 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2532 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2533 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2534 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2535 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2536 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7 + 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2537 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6)/(5 + 4)))))) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2538 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2539 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C((6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2540 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - 7 - 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2541 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2542 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2543 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2544 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(6))) + (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2545 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2546 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2547 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2548 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2549 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2550 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2551 &:= 1 + (C(2^3) + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2552 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2553 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2554 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2555 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - C(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2556 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2557 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 \times 4) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2558 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2559 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2560 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) - ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2561 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2562 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2563 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 - (C(4) - C(5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2564 &:= (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2565 &:= (C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2566 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2567 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2568 &:= ((((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2569 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) - 4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2570 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2571 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 + 4) - (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2572 &:= (((-1 - C(2 - 3 + 4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2573 &:= (((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) \times 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2574 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (C(5) + C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2575 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + C(4)) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2576 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + C(4)) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2577 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2578 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2579 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - (C(4) - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2580 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2581 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2582 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2583 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2584 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + 4)) \times 5) + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2585 &:= (((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2586 &:= (1 - 2^3) \times (C(4) - C(5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2587 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2588 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2589 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2550 &:= ((9 + (C(8) - 7 - 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2551 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2552 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2553 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2554 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2555 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (C(6) + C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2556 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2557 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C((7 + 6 - 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2558 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2559 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2560 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - (7 - C(6))) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2561 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2562 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) + C(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2563 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2564 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2565 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2566 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2568 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) - C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2569 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2570 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2571 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) + C(7))) / (6 - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2572 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2573 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2574 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2575 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2576 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2577 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2578 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2579 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - (6 - (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2580 &:= ((((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2581 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2582 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2583 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2584 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C((7 + 6 - (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2585 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2586 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2587 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2588 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2589 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2590 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2591 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - (4 + C(5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2592 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2593 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2594 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (C(3) - 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2595 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2596 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2597 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2598 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) + ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2599 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2600 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2601 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times ((4 \times (5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2602 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2603 &:= (-1 - (((C(2^3) + 4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2604 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2605 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2606 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2607 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2608 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2609 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (4 + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2610 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - 4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2612 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2613 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2614 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2615 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2616 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2617 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + 4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2618 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2619 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2620 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2621 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (((C(4) \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2622 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (4 + C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))))))) \\
2623 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2624 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2625 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2626 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (5 + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2627 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2628 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3 + 4)) / 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2629 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (5 + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2590 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2591 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - (6 \times C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2592 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2593 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) \times 5) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2594 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2595 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2596 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2597 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2598 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + C(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2599 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2600 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2601 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2602 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2603 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2604 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2605 &:= ((-9 - C(8)) \times ((7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2606 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2607 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) \times (6 + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2608 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2609 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2610 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (7 - 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2611 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2612 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2613 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((C(7) - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2614 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2615 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2616 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2617 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) - 5)^4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2618 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2619 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2620 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2621 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2622 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - (7 \times 6 + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2623 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2624 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2625 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2626 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2627 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2628 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2629 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2630 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times (4-C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2631 &:= (1+2) \times ((3+4) \times C(5)-6) + 7+8+9 \\
2632 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times C(4)) - ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2633 &:= ((-1+(2 \times 3 \times C(4))) - (C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2634 &:= (((-1+(2 \times (C(3+4)-C(5)))) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
2635 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (3-4+C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2636 &:= ((-1+C(2 \times (3+4))) - (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2637 &:= (-1-2+((C(3)-(C(4)-C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2638 &:= (-1 \times 2+((C(3)-(C(4)-C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2639 &:= ((-1 \times 2-C(3)) \times (C(4)-(C(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
2640 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) - (C(4)-C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2641 &:= (-1+2+((C(3)-(C(4)-C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2642 &:= (-1-(C(2+3)-(C(((4 \times 5)-6))+7+8+9))) \\
2643 &:= (-1+((C(2+3) \times 4 \times 5)+6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2644 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2+3) \times 4) - ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2645 &:= (-1+(2 \times (C(3)+((4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2646 &:= ((-1-C(2+3)) \times (4+5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2647 &:= (-1-(2 \times (C(3)+(4-(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2648 &:= ((-1+C(2 \times (3+4))) - (C(5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2649 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (4 \times C(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
2650 &:= ((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times ((4 \times 5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
2651 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (3+4+C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2652 &:= ((((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times C(5))) \times 6) - (7+8+9)) \\
2653 &:= (-1+(C(2 \times (3+4)) + (5 \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2654 &:= (-1-(((2-(C(3)-4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2655 &:= ((((-1 \times 2+C(3))-4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2656 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times (C(4)+(5 \times 6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2657 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4)-(C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2658 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5+C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2659 &:= (-1+(2 \times (C(3)-(4-(C(5+6)-(7+8+9)))))) \\
2660 &:= ((-1-2+(C(3)+4)) \times (C(5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2661 &:= ((-1+(2 \times ((3 \times 4)+C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2662 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times 4)-C(5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2663 &:= (-1-(2 \times (C(3)-(4+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2664 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3)-(4+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2665 &:= 1-2 \times (C(3)-(4+(C(5+6)+7+8+9))) \\
2666 &:= (-1-(C(2+3)+(C(4)-((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2667 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3)+(C(4)-((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2668 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3)-4) \times (C(5)-(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2669 &:= (-1+2+((C(3)-4) \times (C(5)-(C(6)/(7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2670 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2671 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2672 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2673 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2674 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2675 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2676 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2677 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (5 + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2678 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2679 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2680 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2681 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4) - C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2682 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2683 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 - 4 + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2684 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2685 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2686 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3 + 4) \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2687 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - 4 - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2688 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2689 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4) - (C(5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2690 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2691 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2692 &:= ((((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2693 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + C(5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2694 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(((4 \times 5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2695 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2696 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2697 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2698 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2699 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2700 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times 4))) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2701 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2702 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2703 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2704 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2705 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) - C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2706 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2707 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2708 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2709 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2670 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2671 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2672 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2673 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2674 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2675 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2676 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2677 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + 7 - (6 - 5)))) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2678 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2679 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2680 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2681 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2682 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2683 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2684 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2685 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2686 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) - C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
2687 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2688 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2689 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2690 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2691 &:= 9 + 8 + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2692 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2693 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2694 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2695 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + C(6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2696 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2697 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2698 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5)) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2699 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + C(7 + 6))) - ((5 - 4)^{321})) \\
2700 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2701 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2702 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2703 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2704 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6 - 5))) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2705 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2706 &:= (-9 + ((C((8 - 7 + 6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2707 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2708 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2709 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2710 &:= ((-1+2-3+4) \times (C(5+6)+7+8+9)) \\
2711 &:= (-1-(2 \times (3-4-(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2712 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3-4-(C(5+6)+7+8+9))) \\
2713 &:= ((-1+C((2+(3+4+5))))-(6+7+8+9)) \\
2714 &:= (C((-1+(2 \times 3+4+5)))-(6+7+8+9)) \\
2715 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3))+C(((4 \times 5)-6)))-(7+8+9)) \\
2716 &:= (-1-(C(2-3+4)-C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2717 &:= ((-1+(2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5)-(6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2718 &:= (-1+(C(2 \times (3+4))+(5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2719 &:= ((-1+C((2-(3-(4+5+6)))))-(7+8+9)) \\
2720 &:= (C((-1-((2-3) \times (4+5+6))))-(7+8+9)) \\
2721 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3+4))+(C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2722 &:= (-1+2-(C(3)-(4+C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9))))))) \\
2723 &:= (-1+(2 \times (3+4+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2724 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times C(4+5))-(C(6)-(7+8+9))) \\
2725 &:= (-1+(C((2+(3+4+5)))+(6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2726 &:= ((-1+(2 \times C(3+4+5)))-C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2727 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4)+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)) \\
2728 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4})-(C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2729 &:= (-1+(((2 \times (C(3) \times 4))-C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2730 &:= (1+2+(C(3)-C(4)+C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2731 &:= (-1+((2 \times (C(3)-(4-C(5+6))))+7+8+9)) \\
2732 &:= ((-1+2+((C(3)-4) \times C(5)))-(6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
2733 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((3 \times 4)+(C(5+6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2734 &:= ((-1+C((2+(3+4+5))))-(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2735 &:= (-1-(2 \times (3-(C(4)+(C(5+6)-(7+8+9)))))) \\
2736 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2-(3+4))))-5-6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2737 &:= ((-1+C(2 \times (3+4)))-(5 \times 6-(7+8+9))) \\
2738 &:= ((-1+2-(3+4))+C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2739 &:= (-1+(C(2 \times (3+4))+(5-(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2740 &:= ((-1+(2^{3 \times 4}))-(C(5+6)+7+8+9)) \\
2741 &:= (C(((1+2+3) \times 4))-(C(5+6)+7+8+9)) \\
2742 &:= ((-1-(2+3-4))+C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2743 &:= (-1+C((2-(C(3)-(4+5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2744 &:= C(((1+2 \times C(3))-(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2745 &:= (((-1+2)^{34})+C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2746 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times 4)-(C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
2747 &:= (-1+((2 \times (C(3)+(4+C(5+6))))+7+8+9)) \\
2748 &:= ((-1-(2-(3+4)))+C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2749 &:= (-1-((2+(C(3) \times 4)) \times (5-(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2750 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2751 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2752 &:= (-1 + (C((2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2753 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2754 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2755 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2756 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2757 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2758 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((4 - (C(5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2759 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) + (4 - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2760 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (4 - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2761 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2762 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2763 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2764 &:= 1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) - C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2765 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6) - (7 + 8) - 9) \\
2766 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2767 &:= (-1 + (C((2 - (3 - (4 + 5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2768 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2769 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2770 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2771 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2772 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2773 &:= (-1 + (C((2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2774 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2775 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2776 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))) \\
2777 &:= (((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2778 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2779 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2780 &:= 1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2781 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((C(3 + 4) + C(5)) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2782 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((C(3 + 4) + C(5)) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2783 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2784 &:= (1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4 + 5))/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2785 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2786 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2787 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2788 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2789 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2750 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2751 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2752 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2753 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2754 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2755 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2756 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2757 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 \times 6 + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2758 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
2759 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2760 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2761 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2762 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2763 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - C((7 + 6 + 5)))/C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2764 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6) - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2765 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2766 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2767 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2768 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2769 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) + (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2770 &:= ((9 + 8 + (C(7) - 6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2771 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2772 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2773 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2774 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times C(6)) + C(5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2775 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2776 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2777 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2778 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2779 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2780 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C(6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2781 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2782 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2783 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2784 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2785 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (C(6) + C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2786 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7 + 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2787 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2788 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2789 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + C(((5 \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2790 &:= ((-1-2+(C(3)+(C(4)+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2791 &:= (-1+2-(((C(3)+4) \times (5 \times (6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
2792 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2793 &:= (((-1+2)^3) - (C(4) - ((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2794 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4) + ((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
2795 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
2796 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (C(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2797 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3+4)) + ((5 \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2798 &:= (-1-2-(C(3+4) - ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2799 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) \times 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2800 &:= ((C((-1+2+3+4)) \times 5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
2801 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2802 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4+5) + C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2803 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2804 &:= (C(-1+2+3) - (4 - C((5 + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2805 &:= (-1-2 - (((C(3) - C(4+5))/6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2806 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((C(3) - C(4+5))/6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2807 &:= 1-2 - ((C(3) - C(4+5))/6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2808 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2809 &:= (-1+2 - (((C(3) - C(4+5))/6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2810 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3+4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2811 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4+5) + C(6))) - (7+8+9) \\
2812 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times (C(4+5) + C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2813 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2814 &:= (((-1-2 + (C(3+4) + C(5))) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
2815 &:= ((-1 + C(((2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5))) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2816 &:= (C(((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times 5)) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2817 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3) + (4 - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2818 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) + (4 - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2819 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2820 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 - C(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2821 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) + (4 - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2822 &:= (-1-2 + ((3^4) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
2823 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times C(4)) - ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2824 &:= (C(-1+2+3) - ((4 - (C(5) - 6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2825 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2826 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
2827 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2828 &:= ((-1+2 + C(3)) \times (C((4 - (5 - 6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
2829 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2830 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3+4) + C(5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2831 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) + (4-5-6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2832 &:= (1 \times 2 \times C(3) + C(4)) \times (5!/(6+7+8+9))! \\
2833 &:= 1 + (C(2+3) + 4-5-6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2834 &:= (-1 - ((2+3 - (C(4) \times 5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2833 &:= 1 + (C(2+3) + 4-5-6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2836 &:= (1-2-3) \times (4 \times 5 - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2837 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2838 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3+4)) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2839 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C(4+5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2840 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
2841 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2842 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2843 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2844 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (C(4+5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2845 &:= (((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2846 &:= ((-1+2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2847 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3^4) + C(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
2848 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2849 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + (4 - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2850 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2851 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((4 \times (C(5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2852 &:= (-1 + ((2+3+4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))))) \\
2853 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2854 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2855 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - C(4+5))/6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2856 &:= (1 + C(2+3) + 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2857 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2858 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3+4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
2859 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2860 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2861 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
2862 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4+5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2863 &:= ((-1+2) \times (3+4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2864 &:= ((-1+2+3+4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2865 &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2866 &:= (((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2867 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + C(5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
2868 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (C(4+5) - 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2869 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2830 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
2831 &:= (((-9-8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2832 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1))) \\
2833 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2834 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2835 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2836 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 + C(5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2837 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2838 &:= ((((-9+8-7) \times 6) \times (5 - C(4))) + 3+2+1) \\
2839 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6+5 - (4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
2840 &:= (((-9-8+7) \times C(6)) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2841 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7+6 - C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2842 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - ((6+5) \times (4 - C(3+2+1))))) \\
2843 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2844 &:= (-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6+5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2845 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2846 &:= (((-9-8-7) \times (6 - C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2847 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (6 + C(5+4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
2848 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
2849 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2850 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2851 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + ((C(5) - 4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2852 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times (6+5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
2853 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7-6) - C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2854 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C(((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2855 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7-6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2856 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 + C(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2857 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) + (5 - (C(4) - C(3+2+1))))) \\
2858 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 - (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))))) \\
2859 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (6 - (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1))))) \\
2860 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
2861 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2862 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 \times 6 - C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2863 &:= ((((-9 + C(8+7))/6) \times 5) + (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
2864 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2865 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2866 &:= (((-9-8-7) \times (6 - C(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2867 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7+6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2868 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
2869 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - C(6))) - (5 \times (4 - C(3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2870 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + (C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2871 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3^4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2872 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2873 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2874 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2875 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2876 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - (4 - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2877 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2878 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2879 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) + (4 - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2880 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2881 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2882 &:= (((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2883 &:= 1 + 2 + (C(3) + C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2884 &:= 1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2885 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2886 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2887 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2888 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2889 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3 + (C(4) \times 5)) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2890 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2891 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2892 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 + 4) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2893 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2894 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2895 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2896 &:= (1 + 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2897 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2898 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2899 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2900 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2901 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2902 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2903 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2904 &:= 1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2905 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2906 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2907 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2908 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2909 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) + C(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2870 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - C((7 - (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2871 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2872 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C((7 - (6 - 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2873 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - C((C(6) / C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
2874 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2875 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2876 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2877 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2878 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2879 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2880 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2881 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2882 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2883 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2884 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2885 &:= (-9 - (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2886 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2887 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2888 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2889 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2890 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2891 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2892 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2893 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2894 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2896 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2897 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2898 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2899 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2900 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2901 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2902 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2903 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2904 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2905 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2906 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2907 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2908 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2909 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2910 &:= ((-1+2+(C(3)+(C(4)+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2911 &:= (((-1+C(2+3+4)) \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2912 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((C(4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
2913 &:= (-1-2+((3 \times C(4+5)) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2914 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4+5)) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2915 &:= (-1 - ((2+3-4-5) \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2916 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (C(4+5)+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
2917 &:= (-1+2+((3 \times C(4+5)) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2918 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (C(4) + ((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2919 &:= 1+2+3 \times C(4+5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
2920 &:= ((-1+2+3+4) \times (C(5) + (C(6)+7+8+9))) \\
2921 &:= (-1+(2 \times (3+(C(4+5)+C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
2922 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) + ((4 - (C(5)+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2923 &:= (C((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))) + ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2924 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4+5) - (6 \times (7+8+9))))) \\
2925 &:= ((-1 - ((2+C(3)) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2926 &:= (C((-1+(2+(3+4+5)))) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
2927 &:= (-1+(2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2928 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - C(4))) + 5+6) \times (7+8+9) \\
2929 &:= (-1+2+(((3+C(4+5))/6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2930 &:= (((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
2931 &:= (C((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))) + (5 + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
2932 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3)^4) \times 5)) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2933 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4+5) - (C(6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2934 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times C(4+5)) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
2935 &:= (-1 + (C((2+(3+4+5))) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
2936 &:= (C((-1+(2 \times 3+4+5))) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
2937 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3)^4) + ((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
2938 &:= (-1+2+((3^4) + ((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2939 &:= (-1 - ((C(2-3+4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2940 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2-3+4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2941 &:= (-1+2+((3 \times 4) \times (5 + (C(6)+7+8+9)))) \\
2942 &:= (-1-2+((C(3)+4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2943 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3)+4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2944 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
2945 &:= ((-1+(2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
2946 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times C(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2947 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (((4+C(5))-6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2948 &:= (-1+2+(C(3)+(C(4)+((C(5)-6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2949 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2910 &:= ((-9+C(8)-(C(7)-(6+C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2911 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2912 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + ((5+4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
2913 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2914 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2915 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7+6) + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1))) \\
2916 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
2917 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 \times (C(5+4) + C(3+2+1))))) \\
2918 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2919 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2920 &:= ((((-9-8) \times C(7))/(6-C(5))) \times C(4)) - C(3+2+1) \\
2921 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) + C(6))) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2922 &:= (((-9+C(8)-7) \times 6) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2923 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) - (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
2924 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2925 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2926 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6 - 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2927 &:= (((-9+8+C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2928 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (((6+5) \times C(4)) - C(3+2+1))) \\
2929 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
2930 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2931 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 + C(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2932 &:= ((-9+8+(C(7) \times 6)) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2933 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6)/(5+4)))) + 3+2+1)) \\
2934 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
2935 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) \times 5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2936 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2937 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times (6 - (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
2938 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (C(7) \times ((6+5) \times (4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
2939 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times (6 + ((5+C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
2940 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2941 &:= (-9+8 - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2942 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2943 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) - C(7+6))/5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2944 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + C(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2945 &:= (((-9-8) \times C(7)) + ((6^5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
2946 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2947 &:= ((-9+C((8+7-(6-5)))) - (4-C(3+2+1))) \\
2948 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
2949 &:= (((-9+C(8)-7) \times 6) - C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2950 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2951 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3 + C(4))) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2952 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2953 &:= 1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4)) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2954 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2955 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2956 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2957 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2958 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2959 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2960 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2961 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2962 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2963 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2964 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2965 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2966 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) + 4) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2967 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2968 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times ((C(5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2969 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times 4 \times C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2970 &:= (1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2971 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2972 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) - C(6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
2973 &:= (1 - 2) \times C(3) + C(4 - 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2974 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 + 4) - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2975 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2976 &:= (1 + 2) \times C(3 - 4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2977 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4) - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2978 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3 + 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2979 &:= (1 + 2) \times (C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2980 &:= 1 + C(2 + 3 + 4) + C(5) \times (-6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2981 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3! \times C(4))) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2982 &:= C(1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) - 5 + C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2983 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times C(5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2984 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2985 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2986 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2987 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2988 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2989 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2950 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times C(6)))/5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2951 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - C((7 - (6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2952 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2953 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - C(4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2954 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2955 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - 7)) + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2956 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2957 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2958 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2959 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2960 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2961 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2962 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2963 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7 + 6))/5)) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2964 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2965 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2966 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2967 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2968 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2969 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) - (5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2970 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2971 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2972 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2973 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6)))) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2974 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6 - 5))) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2975 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2976 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2977 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2978 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2979 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2980 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2981 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2982 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2984 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2985 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2986 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2987 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 - ((C(6 + 5) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2988 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2989 &:= (-9 + ((8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2990 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2991 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2992 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((5 \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2993 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2^3) - 4 - 5) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2994 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2995 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2996 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2998 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2999 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 \times C(4) + C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3000 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2990 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6)))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2991 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2992 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2993 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2994 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2995 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2996 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 - 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2997 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2998 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (C(5) + C(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2999 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
3000 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5)) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3002 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3003 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C((4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3004 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C((4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3005 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times C(5))) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3006 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) - 4 - 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3007 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3008 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times 4 \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3009 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3010 &:= (((-1 + C(2 - 3 + 4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3011 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (((3 \times 4) \times C(5)) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3012 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3013 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - C(5)))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3014 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (4 - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3015 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) - 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3016 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3017 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times 4 \times C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3018 &:= (((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - 5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3019 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3020 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3 + 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3021 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3 + 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3022 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) + C(4 + 5))/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3023 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 + 4)) + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3024 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3025 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3026 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3027 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C((4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3028 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 \times (C(5) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3002 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3003 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3004 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3005 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3006 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3007 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3008 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3009 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3010 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3011 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3012 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3013 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3014 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3015 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3016 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3017 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3018 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3019 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3020 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3021 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3022 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((C(6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3023 &:= (-9 - (C((8 - 7 + 6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3024 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3025 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3026 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3027 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3028 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3069 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times C(4) + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3070 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3071 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3072 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3073 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + C((4 - (5 - 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3074 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3075 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 - C(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3076 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3077 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (C(3) - 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3078 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3079 &:= (1 - 2)^3 - C(4) + (C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3080 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3081 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3082 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3083 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3084 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3085 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3086 &:= (-1 + (C(((2 \times 3) - (4 - 5))) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3087 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3088 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3089 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) + 4 - 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3090 &:= 1 + 2 + C(3 + 4) + C(5 + C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3091 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3092 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3093 &:= 1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3094 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3095 &:= C(1 \times 2 + 3) \times 4! + C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3096 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3097 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3098 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - 4)) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3099 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3100 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3101 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3102 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3103 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) - C(6)) + 7 + 8) + 9 \\
3104 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times C(5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3105 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3106 &:= 1 + (2 + 3 + C(4)) \times 5 \times C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
3107 &:= -C(-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3108 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3069 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3070 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3071 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7 + 6)) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3072 &:= (C(((9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3073 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3074 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3075 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3076 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3077 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3078 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times ((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3079 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3080 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3081 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3082 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(6))) - (C(5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3083 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + C(5)) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3085 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 - 5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3086 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3087 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3088 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - ((C(5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3089 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3090 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3091 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3092 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times 6)) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3093 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3094 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3095 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C(6) \times 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3096 &:= ((-9 + 8 - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3097 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3098 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3099 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) \times (5 + C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3100 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3101 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3102 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3103 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3104 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3105 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3106 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3107 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
3108 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - C(5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3109 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3110 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3111 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3112 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((4 - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3113 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3 + 4) + 5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3114 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3115 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3116 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3117 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3118 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3119 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3120 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3121 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 - 4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3122 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (4 + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3123 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3124 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3125 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3126 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3127 &:= 1 + 2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3128 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3129 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3 + 4) + 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3130 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3131 &:= (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3132 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3133 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3 + 4) + 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3134 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3135 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3136 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3137 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3138 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3139 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times C(5))) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3140 &:= ((-1 - (2 - 3 + 4)) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3141 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + 5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3142 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (5 \times C(3 + 4) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3143 &:= (-1 + (((C((2 + (C(3)/(4 + 5)))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3144 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3145 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3146 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3147 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3148 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3109 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7 + 6))) + (5^4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3110 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times 6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3111 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3112 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3113 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3114 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3115 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3116 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3117 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3118 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3119 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3120 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3121 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3122 &:= (9 \times (C((8 - 7 + 6) + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3123 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) - C(7 + 6))/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3124 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3125 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3126 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3127 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - (C(7 + 6) - ((C(5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3128 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3129 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3130 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3131 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (5 - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3132 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3133 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3134 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3135 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3136 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3137 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3138 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3139 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - ((5 + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3140 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3141 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3142 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C((6 + 5 - 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3143 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6)/(5 + 4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3144 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3145 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3146 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3147 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3148 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3149 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3150 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3151 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3152 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3153 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + (C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3154 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + (C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3155 &:= C(1 \times 2 + 3) \times 4! + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3156 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3157 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3158 &:= (((-1 - (C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9))) \\
 3159 &:= (1 + 2) \times C(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3160 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3161 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3162 &:= (1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C(5)) - C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 3163 &:= (1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 3164 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3165 &:= 1 + 2 - C(3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 3166 &:= 1 - 2 + (C(3) - 4 + (C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3167 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) - (4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3168 &:= (C(1 \times 2 + 3) - 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3169 &:= 1 + (C(2 + 3) - 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3170 &:= (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3171 &:= (C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3172 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - ((4 - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3173 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3174 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3175 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3176 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3177 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3178 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3179 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3180 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - C(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3181 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3182 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3183 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3184 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (C(4) - (C(5) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3185 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3186 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3187 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 3188 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3149 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3150 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3151 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3152 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3153 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3154 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3155 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3156 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3157 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3158 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3159 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3160 &:= (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3161 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3162 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7 - 6) + C(5)) \times 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3163 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + C((7 + 6 + 5))) / (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3164 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3165 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3166 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3167 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3168 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) / 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3169 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times (C(6 + 5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3170 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3171 &:= ((-9 \times C(8) - 7) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3172 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3173 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3174 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((C(6) / (5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3175 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3176 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3177 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3178 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3179 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3180 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3181 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3182 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3183 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 3184 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3185 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3186 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3187 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (((6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3188 &:= (-9 + (C((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3229 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3230 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3231 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3232 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3233 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3234 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3235 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3236 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3237 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3238 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3239 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C((4 + 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3240 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3241 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3242 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3243 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3244 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3245 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3246 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3247 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3248 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3249 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3250 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 + 3) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3251 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (C(3) \times 4 \times 5)) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3252 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3253 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3254 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3255 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3256 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3257 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3258 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3259 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3260 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3261 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times C(4)) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3262 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3263 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3264 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3265 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3266 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4))) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3267 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3268 &:= (1 + 2 + C(3) - 4) \times C(5) - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3229 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - C(4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3230 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3231 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3232 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3233 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3234 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3235 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3236 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3237 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3238 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3239 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3240 &:= ((-9 - 8 - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3241 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3242 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3243 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3244 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3245 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3246 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3247 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3248 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3249 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + (C(6)/(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3250 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3251 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7 - (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3252 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3253 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 + 6 + 5) - 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3254 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3255 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3256 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3257 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3258 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3259 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((C(5) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3260 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3261 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3262 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3263 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3264 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7 + 6)))/5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3265 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3266 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3267 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3268 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3269 &:= (-1 - ((2+3)! \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3270 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) + (C(4+5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
3271 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
3272 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (C(4) + ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
3273 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4+5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
3274 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4+5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
3275 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3276 &:= ((-1 - C(2+3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3277 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3278 &:= (((-1+2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5)+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3279 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times (4+5)) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
3280 &:= (((-1 + C(2-3+4)) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
3281 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3+4))) \times 5) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
3282 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3283 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3284 &:= (-1 + ((2+3+4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
3285 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) \times 5))) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
3286 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3287 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3288 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - 6)) \times (7+8+9) \\
3289 &:= ((C((-1+2+3+4)) \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
3290 &:= ((-1+2^3) \times (4 \times C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3291 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - ((5 \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
3292 &:= ((-1+2 + (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
3293 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
3294 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3295 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3296 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (C(4+5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
3297 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3298 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3299 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3+4) + (C(5)+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
3300 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
3301 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3302 &:= (((-1-2 \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3303 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3+4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
3304 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((4 + (C(5)+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
3305 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 \times 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3306 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3307 &:= ((-1 + (2+3) \times 4) - ((C(5) \times (6+7)) - C((8+9)))) \\
3308 &:= (((-1-2 + (C(3)+4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3269 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + 7 + 6)) + (C((5 \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3270 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3271 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3272 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3273 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3274 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3275 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3276 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3277 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3278 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3279 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3280 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) - C(7 + 6))/5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3281 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3282 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((C(7 + 6) - 5)/4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3283 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3284 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3285 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3286 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) \times 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3287 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3288 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3289 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3290 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3291 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3292 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3293 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - 7 - 6)) + (C((5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3294 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3295 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3296 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3297 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5) + C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3298 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3299 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3300 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3301 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - 7)) + (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3302 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3303 &:= (-9 \times 8 + C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3304 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3305 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3306 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3307 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3308 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3309 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3310 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3311 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3312 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3 + 4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3313 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4 + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3314 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3315 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3316 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3317 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3318 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3319 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) + (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3320 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
3321 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3322 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3323 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3324 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3325 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3326 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3327 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3328 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3329 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3330 &:= (((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3331 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3332 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3333 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 \times 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3334 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 \times 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3335 &:= -C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3336 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3337 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 \times 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3338 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3339 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3340 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3341 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3 + 4)) - C(5)) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3342 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4 + 5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3343 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3344 &:= ((-1 + C((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3345 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3346 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4 + 5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3347 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3348 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3309 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3310 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3311 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6)/(5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3312 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3313 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7 + 6))/5)) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3314 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3315 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3316 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3317 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3318 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3319 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3320 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3321 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3322 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3323 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3324 &:= 9 + (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3325 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3326 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3327 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3328 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3329 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + 7)) + C(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3330 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3331 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) - (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3332 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3333 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3334 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3335 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3336 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3337 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3338 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3339 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3340 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3341 &:= (-9 - ((8 - C(7)) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3342 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + C(5 + 4))))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3343 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3344 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3345 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3346 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3347 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3348 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3389 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 + (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3390 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3391 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3392 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3393 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3394 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3395 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3396 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3397 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3398 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3399 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3400 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3401 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 3402 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3403 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3404 &:= (-1 + (C((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3405 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3406 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3407 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C((C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3408 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 + 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3409 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - 5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3410 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 3411 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) \times 5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3412 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3413 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3414 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 3415 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3416 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - 5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3417 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3418 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
 3419 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 3420 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3421 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3422 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 + (C(4 + 5) + (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
 3423 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3424 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3425 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 3426 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 3427 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 3428 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3389 &:= ((((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) / (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3390 &:= ((-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3391 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3392 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + 6 - 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3393 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + C(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3394 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3395 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 - ((C(6 + 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3396 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3397 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3398 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3399 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 + C(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3400 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3401 &:= (-9 + ((C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3402 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3403 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3404 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3405 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3406 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3407 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3408 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3409 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3410 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3411 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3412 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3413 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3414 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3415 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3416 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3417 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 3418 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3419 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3420 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 3421 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3422 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3423 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3424 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(((6 - 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 3425 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3426 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 3427 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times C(6))) - ((5 \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 3428 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3469 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3470 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3471 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3472 &:= (-1 + (C((2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3473 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3474 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3475 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3476 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3477 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3478 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3479 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 + 3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3480 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3481 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3482 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3483 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3484 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3485 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3486 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3487 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3488 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3489 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3 + 4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3490 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3491 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3492 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3493 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3494 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3495 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3496 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3497 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3498 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3499 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3500 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3501 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3502 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3503 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C((C(3) - (4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3504 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3505 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3506 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
3507 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3508 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3469 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3470 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3471 &:= (-9 + ((C((8 - 7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3472 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3473 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3474 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3475 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3476 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3477 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3478 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - 6 - 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3480 &:= ((-9 \times (C((8 - 7 + 6)) - C(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3481 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3482 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3483 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7 \times 6) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3484 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3485 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3486 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3487 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3488 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times C(6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3489 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3490 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + 5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3491 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3492 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3493 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C((6 + 5 - 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3494 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3495 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3496 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5)) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3497 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C((6 - (5 - 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3498 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
3499 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3500 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3501 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3502 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3503 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3504 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3505 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3506 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3507 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3508 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3509 &:= (-1 - (((C(2^3)/C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3509 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3510 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3510 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3511 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3511 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3512 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3512 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3513 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3513 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3514 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3514 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3515 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3515 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3516 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3516 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7)))/6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3517 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3517 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6)/((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3518 &:= (-1 + (C((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3518 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3519 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 3519 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3520 &:= 1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 3520 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3521 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 3521 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3522 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3522 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3523 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3523 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3524 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3524 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3525 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3525 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times C(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3526 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3526 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3527 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3 + 4))/5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 3527 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + C((C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3528 &:= ((((-1 \times 2 - C(3 + 4))/5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 3528 &:= 9 \times ((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3529 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3529 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3530 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3530 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3531 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3531 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3532 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3532 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3533 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3533 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3534 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3534 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3535 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3535 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3536 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3536 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C((7 + 6 - 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3537 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3537 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3538 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3538 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3539 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3539 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3540 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3540 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3541 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3541 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3542 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3542 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3543 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3543 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3544 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3544 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3545 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3545 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3546 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3546 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 + 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3547 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3547 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times ((6 - C(5)) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3548 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3548 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3549 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) - ((4-C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3549 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((C(7) - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3550 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 \times 4)) + (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3550 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) / 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3551 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) + (C(4) + (5 - C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) & 3551 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3552 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)) & 3552 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) \times (6+5))) - (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
3553 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) & 3553 &:= 9 + ((C(8) \times 7) - ((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3554 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4+5) + (6 - (7+8+9))))) & 3554 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3555 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times C(4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3555 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3556 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times C(4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3556 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + (7-6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3557 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (5-6))) + 7+8+9))) & 3557 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
3558 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4) + (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))))) & 3558 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3559 &:= (-1+2 - (3 \times C(4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3559 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
3560 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))) & 3560 &:= ((-9-8 + (C(7) + (6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3561 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))) & 3561 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3562 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 3562 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6))) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3563 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 3563 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6+5-4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
3564 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) & 3564 &:= (-9 \times (C(8+7-6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3565 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 3565 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3566 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 3566 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3567 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3567 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3568 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3568 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - C(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
3569 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3+4))) \times 5) + 6 \times (7+8+9)) & 3569 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
3570 &:= (((-1+2 - (3+4)) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 3570 &:= (9 + (C((8-7+6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3571 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4 \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) & 3571 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6)/((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
3572 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - (C(4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) & 3572 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
3573 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3+4) \times 5)) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) & 3573 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6/(5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
3574 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7+8+9))))) & 3574 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3575 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3575 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
3576 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3576 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3577 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3 \times 4) - ((5 + C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3577 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
3578 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))))) & 3578 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
3579 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - (5 \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) & 3579 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
3580 &:= 1 - 2 - C(3 \times 4) + C(5) + C(6) \times (7+8+9) & 3580 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7+6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
3581 &:= (C((-1+2^3+4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 3581 &:= ((-9-8+7) + (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3582 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 3582 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3583 &:= (-1 - (((C((2+3) \times 4)/5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3583 &:= (-9+8-7 + (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3584 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3+4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3584 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3585 &:= (-1+2+3 - (C(4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) & 3585 &:= (C(-9+8+7) - (6 - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3586 &:= (-1+2 \times 3 - (C(4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) & 3586 &:= ((-9-8 + C(7)) \times (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3587 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3587 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
3588 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3^4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3588 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3589 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3590 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3591 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3592 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3593 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3594 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3595 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3596 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3597 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3598 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3599 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 + 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3600 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3601 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3602 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3603 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 \times C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3604 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3605 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3606 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3607 &:= (-1 - ((C(2^3) \times (4 - 5 - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3608 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2^3) \times (4 - 5 - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3609 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((C(5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3610 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3611 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + C(4)) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3612 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3613 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3614 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3615 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times C(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3616 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 + C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3617 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4))) \times 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3618 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3619 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3620 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3621 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3622 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3623 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3624 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3625 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3626 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3627 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3628 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3589 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5 - 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3590 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3591 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3592 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3593 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3594 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) - (C(5) - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3595 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3596 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3597 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3598 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3599 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3600 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3601 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) \times 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3602 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3603 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3604 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3605 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3606 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - (7 - C(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3607 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3608 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - C(7)) \times 6)/5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3609 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3610 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3611 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3612 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3613 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3614 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3615 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3616 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3617 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3618 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3619 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3620 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3621 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times ((C(5) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3622 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3623 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3624 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3625 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3626 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3627 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3628 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3669 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3670 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3 + 4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3671 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3672 &:= 1 + 2 - 3^4 + C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3673 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3674 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3675 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3676 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3677 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3678 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3679 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3680 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3681 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3682 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3683 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3684 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3685 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3686 &:= (C(C(C(C(C((-1 - 2 + 3)))))) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3687 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3688 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3689 &:= -C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + C(4) + C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3690 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3691 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3692 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3693 &:= (-1 + 2^3 - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3694 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3695 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3)/4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3696 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3697 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3698 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3699 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3700 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3701 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3702 &:= (((((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + C(5)) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3703 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3704 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3705 &:= (((C(-1 + 2^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3706 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (C(5) \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3707 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3708 &:= (((-1 + 2^3)^4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3669 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3670 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3671 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (C(6)/(5 + 4))) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3672 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times C(7)) + C(6))/5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3673 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times C(7)) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3674 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3675 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((C(5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3676 &:= (-9 - ((8 - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3677 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3678 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3679 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3680 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) \times 6))/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3681 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3682 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - 6)) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3683 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3684 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3685 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3686 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3687 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3688 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3689 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6 - 5)/4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3690 &:= ((-9 - C(8 + 7 - 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3691 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3692 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3693 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3694 &:= (-9 + ((C(8 + 7 - 6) \times 5) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3695 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3696 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3697 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3698 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5))) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3699 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3700 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) \times 6))/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3701 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3702 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3703 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 + C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3704 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3705 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3706 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3707 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3708 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - C(7)) \times 6)/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3909 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3910 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3911 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3912 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 + C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3913 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) - 4 - 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3914 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3915 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3916 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3917 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + ((4 + 5) \times C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3918 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3 + 4)) \times 5) - (C(6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
3919 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3920 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3921 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3922 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3923 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3924 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3925 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3926 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3927 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3928 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3 + 4) - (C(5) - (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
3929 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3930 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3931 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3932 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3933 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - C(4))) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3934 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3935 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3936 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3937 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) - (5 - (C(6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
3938 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3939 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3940 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3941 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3942 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3943 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3944 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) - (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3945 &:= 1 + 2 - C(3) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3946 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3947 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3948 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3949 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
3950 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
3951 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
3952 &:= (C(((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
3953 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3954 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 - C(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
3955 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - C(5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
3956 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3957 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3+4+C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3958 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4+C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3959 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3960 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
3961 &:= (-1+2 + ((3+4+C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3962 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3963 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3+4) \times C(5)) + (C(6+7) + 8+9))) \\
3964 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3965 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3966 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3))/4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3967 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times ((4+C(5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
3968 &:= ((-1 + ((2-3+4) \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3969 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3970 &:= (((-1+2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3971 &:= ((-1 \times C(2+3)) + (4^{5 \times 6 - (7+8+9)})) \\
3972 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3-4 - C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3973 &:= (C(-1+2^3) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3974 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3975 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3976 &:= 1 - (2 - C(3)) \times (4 + C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3977 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4))) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3978 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3979 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4 + C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3980 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
3981 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4 + C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3982 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times (4 + C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3983 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
3984 &:= ((((-1 - (2+3+4)) \times 5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
3985 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3+4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
3986 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3+4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
3987 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (4 \times (C(5) + C(6)))))) - (7+8+9)) \\
3988 &:= (C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3949 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + ((C(6+5) + (4+3)) \times (2+1))) \\
3950 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3951 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3952 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times (C(6) \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3953 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
3954 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3955 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6)))) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
3956 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3957 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((C(7) - C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
3958 &:= ((-9+8) \times (((C(7) - C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
3959 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
3960 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 + C(5)))))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3961 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7 + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3962 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) + ((5+4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
3963 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - C(6)) \times 5 \times 4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
3964 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3965 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (6 + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
3966 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3967 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
3968 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (C(6)/C((5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
3969 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + C(7+6))/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3970 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) + (C(4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
3971 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3972 &:= 9 + (((8+7) \times C(6)) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
3973 &:= ((-9+8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
3974 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) - (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
3975 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3976 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times (6+5)) + (4 + C(3+2+1)))) \\
3977 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3978 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
3979 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3980 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) \times (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3981 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
3982 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) + (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
3983 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3984 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times 6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
3985 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
3986 &:= 9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times (6+5)) - (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
3987 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3988 &:= (9 \times (8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) + (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3989 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} - C(5) - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3990 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3991 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3992 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3993 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(((4 \times 5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3994 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3995 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3996 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3997 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3998 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3^4) + (C(5) - C(6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9))) \\
3999 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4000 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4001 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4002 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 - C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4003 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4004 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4005 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4006 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4007 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3 + 4) - 5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4008 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4 + C(5)) - C(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4009 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4010 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4011 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4 \times (C(5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4012 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4013 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4014 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + C(4)))) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4015 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4016 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3 + 4) \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4017 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4018 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4019 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4020 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4021 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4022 &:= (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4023 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C((4 - (5 - 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4024 &:= 1 + C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4025 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4026 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4027 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4028 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3989 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3990 &:= ((C(((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))/5)) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3991 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3992 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3993 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7 + 6) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3994 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3995 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3996 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3997 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3998 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((C(7) - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3999 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4000 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4001 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4002 &:= (9 \times (C(8) + 7 + 6)) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4003 &:= ((-9 + (C(8 + 7) + 6)) + ((5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4004 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4005 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4006 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 - 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4007 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4008 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4009 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (((6 + 5) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4010 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (C(7) \times 6))/5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4011 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4012 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4013 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (6 + (5 \times C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4014 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4015 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4016 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4017 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 + 7 + 6) - 5))) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4018 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4019 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4020 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4021 &:= (-9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4022 &:= (-9 - (C((8 - 7 + 6)) - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4023 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times C(7))) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4024 &:= (-9 \times 8 + C(((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4025 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4026 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4027 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5)))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4028 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4029 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4030 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4031 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 + 4 + C(5)) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4032 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4033 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - (4 - 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4034 &:= ((-1 - C(2 + 3)) - ((4^5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4035 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3 + 4)) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4036 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
4037 &:= ((((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4038 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4039 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4040 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) \times 4) - ((5 - (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
4041 &:= ((1 + 2) \times C(3) \times 4 + C(5)) \times C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
4042 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) - ((5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4043 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4044 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4045 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) \times 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4046 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4047 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4048 &:= C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-C(4) + C(5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4049 &:= -C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4050 &:= (1 + C(2 + 3) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4051 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4052 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4053 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) + ((4 \times 5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4054 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4055 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4056 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4057 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) + ((4 \times 5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4058 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4059 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4060 &:= (1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4061 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4062 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 - 4 - C(5))) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
4063 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4064 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4065 &:= ((1 - 2)^3 + 4) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4066 &:= (C((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4067 &:= ((((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4068 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4029 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4030 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6))))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4031 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
4032 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times ((7 - C((6 + 5 - 4)))/(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4033 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7 + 6))/5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4034 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4035 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - C(6)))) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4036 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4037 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4038 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4039 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times C(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4040 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4041 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (7 \times (6 + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4042 &:= (9 \times (C((8 - 7 + 6) - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4043 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4044 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + C((6 + 5 - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4045 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4046 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4047 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4048 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + 7))/(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4049 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) \times 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4050 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4051 &:= (((-9 - C(((8 - 7) \times 6)))/5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4052 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4053 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4054 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C((7 + 6 - 5)))) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4055 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4056 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4057 &:= 9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4058 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (((6 - C(5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4059 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4060 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4061 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 \times 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4062 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4063 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4064 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4065 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4066 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4067 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4068 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (C(6 + 5) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4109 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 + (4 + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4110 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4111 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4112 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((C(3) + 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4113 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4114 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4115 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4116 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 + 4) \times (5 - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4117 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4118 &:= 1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4) \times C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8) + 9 \\
4119 &:= (-1 + ((2^{C(3)-(4+5+6)} + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4120 &:= 1 \times 2^{C(3)-(4+5+6)} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4121 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4122 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4123 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4^{5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)})) \\
4124 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) + (4^{5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)})) \\
4125 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4126 &:= (C((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4127 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4128 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) + C(5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4129 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4130 &:= (1 \times 2 \times C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4131 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4132 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times ((4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4133 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4134 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4135 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4136 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (5 - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4137 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4138 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4139 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4140 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4141 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4142 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4143 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (4 \times C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4144 &:= C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-C(4) + C(5)) + C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4145 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4146 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + 5))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4147 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4148 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4109 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6 \times C(5)) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4110 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4111 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (((6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4112 &:= (9 + (C(8) - 7)) \times (C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4113 &:= 9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4114 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4115 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4116 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4117 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4118 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4119 &:= ((((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4120 &:= (C((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4121 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times 6 - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4122 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4123 &:= (C((-9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4124 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4125 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4126 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4127 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4128 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7) \times (((6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4129 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4130 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4131 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + (6 \times C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4132 &:= (9 \times (C((8 - 7 + 6) + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4133 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (((6 \times C(5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4134 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4135 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6 - 5) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4136 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4137 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4138 &:= (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6)/5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4139 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4140 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4141 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4142 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4143 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + C((C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4144 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((C(7 + 6) - C(5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4145 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4146 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4147 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times ((4 + 3) - C((2 + 1)))))) \\
4148 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + (6 \times C(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4229 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4 + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4230 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4231 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4232 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4233 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4234 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4235 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4236 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) + ((4 \times (C(5) + (6 + 7))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
4237 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4238 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4239 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (4 \times C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4240 &:= (C((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4241 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4242 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4243 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 - C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4244 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4245 &:= (1 + 2) \times (4 \times C(3) + C(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4246 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4247 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4248 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4249 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4250 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4251 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4252 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4253 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3 \times ((4 \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4254 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4255 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4256 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4257 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4258 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4259 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4260 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4261 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4262 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4263 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4264 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4265 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4266 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4267 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4268 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4229 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times C(5)))))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4230 &:= (9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - 6)) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4231 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4232 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4233 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4234 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4235 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4236 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4237 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4238 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4239 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 + 6) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4240 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4241 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4242 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4243 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times 5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4244 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4245 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4246 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4247 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4248 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5) - C(4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4249 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4250 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4251 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4252 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4253 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4254 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4255 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + C(6) - C(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4256 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4257 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4258 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + 6))) \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4259 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4260 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4261 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4262 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7 - 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4263 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times (C(6)/(5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4264 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4265 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4266 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4267 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4268 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4269 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4270 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4271 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) + (C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4272 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4))) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4273 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4274 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4275 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4276 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
4277 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4278 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
4279 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4280 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4281 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4282 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4283 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4284 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4285 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4286 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4287 &:= (-1 + (2^{3+4+5} + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4288 &:= (C(((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4289 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4290 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4291 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4292 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4293 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4294 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4295 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times C(4) - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4296 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4))) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4297 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4298 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4299 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times (5 + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4300 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4301 &:= (-1 - (((2^3 - C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4302 &:= (-1 \times (((2^3 - C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4303 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4304 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4305 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (4 + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4306 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + 4) \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4307 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 + 4) \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4308 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4269 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4270 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4271 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4272 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4273 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4274 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4275 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4276 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4277 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4278 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4279 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6 - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4280 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4281 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6 - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4282 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5)))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4283 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6)) - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4284 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
4285 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 \times 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4286 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4287 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4288 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4289 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4290 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4291 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4292 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4293 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4294 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4295 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4296 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4297 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - (C(6) \times 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4298 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4299 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 + 7 + 6) - 5))) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4300 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4301 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4302 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4303 &:= (-9 + (C(((8 - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4304 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4305 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4306 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (C(6) + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4307 &:= (-9 + (C(((8 + 7 + 6) - 5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4308 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 - 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4309 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9))) & 4309 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4310 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3+4) \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 4310 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (C(7) - C(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4311 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) & 4311 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7+6+5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4312 &:= ((-1+2+C(3)) \times (4+(5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 4312 &:= (C((-9+8-7+(C(6)/(5+4)))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
4313 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4313 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6+5) - (C(4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
4314 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) - (7+8+9) & 4314 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + (6 \times (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
4315 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) & 4315 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4316 &:= ((-1+2+C(3)) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) & 4316 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
4317 &:= (-1-2 + ((C(3) - 4-5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 4317 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (6 + (C(5+4) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
4318 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4-5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 4318 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5+4)) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
4319 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 4319 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4320 &:= ((-1 + (C(2+3) + (4 \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 4320 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7+6-5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4321 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3) - 4-5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 4321 &:= ((9+8) \times (C(7) - 6 \times 5)) - C(4+3+2+1) \\
4322 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - 4 - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 4322 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C(6+5) - (4 \times (3+2+1)))) \\
4323 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) - (7+8+9))) & 4323 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4324 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - ((C(4+5) \times 6) - (7+8+9)))) & 4324 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 \times (6 - C(5+4))) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
4325 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) & 4325 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4326 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3 \times (4 - C(5)))) \times 6) - (7+8+9)) & 4326 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4327 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7)))) + C((8+9))) & 4327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((C(7+6) - 5)/4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
4328 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 4328 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4329 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) + (C(4+5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) & 4329 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4330 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) \times 4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) & 4330 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4331 &:= (C(((-1+2+3) \times 4) - (5 - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) & 4331 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4332 &:= (((-1-2-3) \times ((4 - C(5)) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 4332 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7 \times 6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4333 &:= (-1+2 - (((3 - C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) & 4333 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6 + (C(5) \times 4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
4334 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3+4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 4334 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times (6+5)) + (C(4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
4335 &:= (-1 + (2^{3+4+5} + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 4335 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4336 &:= (C(((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 4336 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4337 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4+5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))) & 4337 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 + (C(6) + (C(5) \times 4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4338 &:= (((-1+2-3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) - (7+8+9) & 4338 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 - (6-5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4339 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9)) & 4339 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4340 &:= ((-1-2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 4340 &:= (((-9+8 + C(7))/6) + 5) \times (C(4) + 3+2+1) \\
4341 &:= (-1-2 + ((3 \times C(4) - 5-6) \times (7+8+9))) & 4341 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4342 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - 5-6) \times (7+8+9))) & 4342 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6+5)))) + (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
4343 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4343 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4344 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) - C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 4344 &:= ((-9 - (8+7+6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4345 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) \times 4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) & 4345 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5+4) + 3+2+1))) \\
4346 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7+8+9)))))) & 4346 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + C((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4347 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9)) & 4347 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (((7-6) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4348 &:= (((-1+2-3) + (C(4+5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 4348 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4349 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4350 &:= (((-1-2+C(3)) - (4-C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4351 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4352 &:= (C(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4353 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4+5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9) \\
4354 &:= (((-1+2+3) + (C(4+5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
4355 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times C(4+5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
4356 &:= ((-1+2 - (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
4357 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + ((C(4+5) \times 6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
4358 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4+5))) + (C(6+7) - (8+9))) \\
4359 &:= (1+2) \times 3 + (C(4+5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4360 &:= (C((-1+2+3) \times 4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4361 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4+5) - 6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
4362 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9 \\
4363 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4364 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4+5) + 6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4365 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (C(4+5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
4366 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + C(4+5)) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
4367 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times ((C(4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
4368 &:= ((-1+2 - C(3)) \times ((4-5-6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4369 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4370 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
4371 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times ((4+5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
4372 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
4373 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times C(4+5)) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
4374 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4375 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4376 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
4377 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4378 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
4379 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4380 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4381 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4 + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4382 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times C(4+5)) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
4383 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4384 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
4385 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4+5) + 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
4386 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times (C(4) + 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4387 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((C(4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4388 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times (C(4+5) - C(6+7))) + 8+9)) \\
4349 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (6 - (C(5) + (4 \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
4350 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + 6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4351 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7-6) - C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4352 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4353 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + C(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4354 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) + (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4355 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (6+5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
4356 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7-6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4357 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(((7-6) \times (5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4358 &:= ((-9 - (8-7+6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4359 &:= ((-9 - ((8-7) \times 6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4360 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7+6))/5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4361 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7+6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4362 &:= (((-9+8-7+6) + C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
4363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7-6) + C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4364 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4365 &:= ((-9 + C(8+7)) - (6 - 5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
4366 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4367 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + ((6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4368 &:= (((-9/(8+7-6)) + C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
4369 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4370 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4371 &:= ((-9 + ((8-7) \times 6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4372 &:= ((-9+8-7+6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4373 &:= ((-9/(8+7-6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4374 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4375 &:= (((-9+8+7)/6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4376 &:= (C((-9 - (8-7-6) \times 5)) + (C(4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
4377 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4378 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + 6+5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4379 &:= (-9+8 + (((7-6) + C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4380 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4381 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((C(7+6) - 5)/4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
4382 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4383 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8) + ((7-6)^5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
4384 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - (6+5+4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
4385 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4386 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4387 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6+5 - (4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
4388 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6) \times 5 - (C(4) - (3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4389 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4390 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
4391 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times C(4))) - 5 - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4392 &:= (1+2) \times (C(3 \times 4) - (5+6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
4393 &:= (-1 + (2 \times C((3 - ((4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4394 &:= (((-1-2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + 6 \times (7+8+9)) \\
4395 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3) \times 4) \times (5 + C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
4396 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4397 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
4398 &:= ((C((-1 - (2 - (3+4+5)))) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
4399 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4400 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - C((4 - (5+6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
4401 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - C((4 - (5+6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
4402 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4403 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times C(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4404 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4405 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
4406 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - 4)) \times (5 - C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
4407 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4+5)) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4408 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
4409 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4410 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
4411 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times ((5 \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
4412 &:= ((-1 + C(2+3)) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
4413 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4414 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4415 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + C(4+5)) \times 6 + 7+8+9 \\
4416 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4+5))) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4417 &:= (-1+2 + (((3 + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
4418 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 \times C(4)) - ((5 + (6+7)) + C((8+9)))))) \\
4419 &:= ((((-1 + C(2+3)) \times 4) - 5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
4420 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (4 \times ((5 \times C(6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
4421 &:= (C(-1+2 \times 3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
4422 &:= ((((-1+2+3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
4423 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
4424 &:= (-1-2 - (((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
4425 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4426 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4427 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
4428 &:= ((-1-2 - (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
4389 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + C(6))) \times (5+4)) + 3+2+1) \\
4390 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 + C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
4391 &:= (-9 - (((8 + C(7+6)) - 5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
4392 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C((7 + ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4393 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + C(4))) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
4394 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6+5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
4395 &:= (-9 - (((8-7-6) - C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4396 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + ((6 \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4397 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (5+4)))) + 3+2+1)) \\
4398 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C((7 - (6 - (5+4)))))) + 3+2+1) \\
4399 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4400 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C((7+6-5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4401 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7+6))/5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4402 &:= ((-9 - C(8+7)) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4403 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (C(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4404 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
4405 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + (7-6)) \times (5 - C(4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
4406 &:= ((-9+8 - (C(7+6) + 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
4407 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - C(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4408 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times (6+5+4)) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
4409 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4410 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (7 - C(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4411 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4412 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5+4)) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
4413 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4414 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) + (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
4415 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times 6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4416 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4)) + 3+2+1) \\
4417 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (C(6+5) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
4418 &:= ((-9-8 - (C(7+6) - 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
4419 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
4420 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) + C(((5 \times 4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
4421 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) \times 7))/(6+5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4422 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - ((7+6) \times C(5)))) \times 4) + 3+2+1) \\
4423 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4424 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4425 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7-6) - (C(5) \times 4)) + 3+2+1) \\
4426 &:= (-9 + (C(8+7) + (((C(6) - 5) \times 4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
4427 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + C(6)) \times 5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
4428 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7-6-5) - C(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4429 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4430 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4431 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4432 &:= (-1 + ((2 - C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4433 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4434 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4435 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4436 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4437 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4438 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4439 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4440 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4441 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4442 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4443 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4444 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times ((5 \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4445 &:= 1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5 + C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4446 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4447 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 + (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4448 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4449 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4450 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4451 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4452 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4453 &:= (((C(-1 + 2^3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4454 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4455 &:= (C(C(C(C(C((-1 - 2 + 3)))))) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4456 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4457 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4458 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4459 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4460 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4461 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4462 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4463 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4464 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4465 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4466 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) \times (5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4467 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4468 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (((4 \times 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4429 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4430 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4431 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4432 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4433 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4434 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) - C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4435 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4436 &:= (((-9 - C(8 + 7)) / 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4437 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4438 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (C(7 + 6) + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4439 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4440 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4441 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4442 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4443 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + ((C(6 + 5) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4444 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4445 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) - ((C(6) \times 5) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4446 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - C(6)))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4447 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4448 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4449 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4450 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4451 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4452 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4453 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + C(6)) \times 5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4454 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4455 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4456 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4457 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4458 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4459 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) / 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4460 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4461 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4462 &:= ((-9 - C(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4463 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4464 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times C(7)) - (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4465 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4466 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + 6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4467 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4468 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4469 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3 \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4470 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4471 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (4 \times (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4472 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4473 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4474 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4475 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4476 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4477 &:= (-1 - (((C(2 + 3) \times 4) - ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
4478 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4479 &:= C(1 \times 2 + 3 + 4) + C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4480 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4481 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4482 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4483 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4484 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4485 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4486 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4487 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4488 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4489 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4490 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4491 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4492 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4493 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3 + 4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4494 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4495 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4496 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((5 \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4497 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4498 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4499 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4500 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + C(4 + 5))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4501 &:= (((C(-1 + 2^3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4502 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) - (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4503 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4504 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4505 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4506 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4507 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) - 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4508 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4469 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4470 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 - (C(5) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4471 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (C(6) \times 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4472 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (6 + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4473 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - C((C(6)/C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4474 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - C(((7 - 6) \times 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4475 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) - C(5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4476 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4477 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4478 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 - 6) \times 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4480 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4481 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4482 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - 6)) \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4483 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6)))/5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4484 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4485 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4486 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4487 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4488 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4489 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6 + 5)) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4490 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4491 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4492 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4493 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4494 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C((7 + 6 - 5)) - 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4495 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4496 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4497 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4498 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4499 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4500 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) - (7 \times C(6))) \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4501 &:= (9 \times (C(8) - 7)) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4502 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4503 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4504 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4505 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4506 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4507 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - (C(6) \times 5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4508 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) \times 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4549 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4550 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4551 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4552 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4553 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4554 &:= (-1 \times (((2^{3+4}) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4555 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4556 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4557 &:= (((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4558 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4559 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 - 3 + 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4560 &:= ((C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4561 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4562 &:= (-1 + (((2^3 \times C(4)) - 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4563 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) - 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4564 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4565 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4566 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4567 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4568 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7))) - C((8 + 9))) \\
4569 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4570 &:= (-1 \times (C(((2 + C(3)) - (4 + (5 + (6 + 7)))))) - C((8 + 9))) \\
4571 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (C(3) + C(4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4572 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) + C(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4573 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4574 &:= (-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4575 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + C(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4576 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4577 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4578 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4579 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4580 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4581 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4582 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4583 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) \times (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4584 &:= (((-1 - (C(2^3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4585 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4586 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4587 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4588 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4549 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4550 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4551 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4552 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - ((6 \times 5) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4553 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - (C(7) - (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4554 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4555 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4556 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4557 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4558 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4559 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (((7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4560 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4561 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4562 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4563 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4564 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4565 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4566 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4567 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 + C(5))) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4568 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4569 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4570 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4571 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (7 + 6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4572 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((C(7) + (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4573 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((C(7) - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4574 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4575 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4576 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4577 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4578 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4579 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4580 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4581 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4582 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4584 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4585 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4586 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4587 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4588 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4669 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9))) \\
4670 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4671 &:= (-1 - (C((2 - (3 - 4 - 5))) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4672 &:= (-1 \times (C((2 - (3 - 4 - 5))) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4673 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4674 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((C(4) + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4675 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4676 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 \times C(4)) - (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4677 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (4 + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4678 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (4 + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4679 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4680 &:= ((((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4681 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (4 + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4682 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4683 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4684 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4685 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4686 &:= (((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4687 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4688 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) + 4 + 5) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4689 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4690 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4691 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - ((4 \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4692 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - ((4 \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4693 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4694 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4695 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4696 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4697 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4698 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4699 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4700 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4701 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4702 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4703 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) - ((4 + 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4704 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((4 + 5) + C(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4705 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4706 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4707 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4708 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4669 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4670 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4671 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4672 &:= ((-9 - C(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4673 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4674 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4675 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times (C(6 + 5) - 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4676 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4677 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - C(6)) \times 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4678 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4679 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
4680 &:= 9 - ((C(8) + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4681 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times C(6)) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4682 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4683 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4684 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7 + 6) + C(5))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4685 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4686 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4687 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4688 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4689 &:= (-9 \times (C(8 + 7 - 6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4690 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) \times 6))/5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4691 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) - (6 - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4692 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4693 &:= (C((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4694 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4695 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4696 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C((C(7) - (6 + (5 \times C(4)))))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4697 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4698 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4699 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4700 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4701 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4702 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4703 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4704 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4705 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4706 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4707 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4708 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4709 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4710 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4711 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4712 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4713 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4714 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4715 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4716 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4717 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4718 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 + 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4719 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4720 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4721 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4722 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 + 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4723 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
4724 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4725 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4726 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4727 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 + 4) + 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4728 &:= (1 - 2 - C(3) + 4 + 5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4729 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times C(5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4730 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4731 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4732 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4733 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4734 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4735 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4736 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 \times (4 + (5 + (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
4737 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - (4 \times C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4738 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4739 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + (4 + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4740 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4741 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + ((C(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4742 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4743 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4744 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) + (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4745 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (C(5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4746 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4747 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4748 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4709 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4710 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4711 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4712 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4713 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4714 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4715 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4716 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - 7)) + C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4717 &:= ((9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4718 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4719 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4720 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4721 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4722 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4723 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (6 + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4724 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - C(6 + 5))) - (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4725 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4726 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4727 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4728 &:= (C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4729 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C((6 - (5 - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4730 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4731 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4732 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4733 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6 + 5)) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4734 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4735 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4736 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4737 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7 + 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4738 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times (C(5) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4739 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (6 + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4740 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + C(6)))) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4741 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4742 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4743 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4744 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4745 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) - (C((5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4746 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4747 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4748 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4749 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4750 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 + 3) + C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4751 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4752 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5)) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4753 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - ((4 + 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4754 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4755 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4756 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4757 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4758 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4759 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4760 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4761 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (C(3) \times 4)) \times 5)) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4762 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4763 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 + 7)))))) + C((8 + 9))) \\
4764 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4765 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 + (6 + 7))) - C((8 + 9)))))) \\
4766 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4767 &:= (1 + 2) \times (C(3 \times 4) + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4768 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4769 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times ((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4770 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4771 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4772 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3^4) + C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4773 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4774 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4775 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4776 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4777 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 - (4 \times 5)) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4778 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times ((4 \times 5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4779 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4780 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4781 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4782 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4 + 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4783 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4784 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4785 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C((C(3) - (4 + (5 + (6 + 7)))))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
4786 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + C(4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4787 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4788 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4749 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 \times C(5)) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4750 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4751 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + (C(7) - C(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4752 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4753 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4754 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4755 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4756 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4757 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((C(5) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4758 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4759 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4760 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4761 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4762 &:= (((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4763 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4764 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4765 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4766 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times ((6 - C(5)) \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4767 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4768 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6) / 5) + (4^{3+2+1}) \\
4769 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - ((C(6) / (5 + 4)) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4770 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4771 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4772 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4773 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times (6 - C(5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4774 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4775 &:= (-9 - (C(((8 - 7) \times 6)) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4776 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4777 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4778 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4779 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4780 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times C(5)) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4781 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (((7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4782 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4783 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (6 + C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4784 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - (((6 + C(5)) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4785 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) \times (5 - C(4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4786 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4787 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 - C(6)) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4788 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8) - C((7 + 6 + 5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4789 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 \times C(4) + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4790 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 \times C(4) + 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4791 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4792 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times C(4)) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4793 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4794 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4795 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4796 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (4 + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4797 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4798 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4799 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times C(4) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 4800 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4801 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4802 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4803 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4804 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4805 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 4806 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4807 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4808 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) \times 4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4809 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 + 3) \times 4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4810 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4811 &:= 1 \times 2 \times C(3 \times 4) + C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 4812 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 + C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4813 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4814 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((C(3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4815 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4816 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3 + 4)) \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4817 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4818 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((C(3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4819 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 4820 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 4821 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4822 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + ((C(5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4823 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4824 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 4825 &:= (C(((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4826 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((C(3) - 4) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 4827 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4828 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (((4 \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 4789 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((C(7) - ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4790 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4791 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4792 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4793 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (C((6 + 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4794 &:= ((9 + 8 - 7) - C(6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4795 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4796 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 4797 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4798 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4799 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4800 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4801 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 4802 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4803 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4804 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + (C(6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4805 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) - ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4806 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4807 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 - C(6)) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 4808 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((C(7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4809 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times C(4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4810 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 4811 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4812 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4813 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4814 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4815 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4816 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 4817 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4818 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (((6 \times C(5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4819 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4820 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4821 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 4822 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + (6 \times C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
 4823 &:= ((-9 + C((((8 + 7) \times 6)/5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4824 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 4825 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 4826 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4827 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + C(6)) \times 5 \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 4828 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4829 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4830 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4831 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4832 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4833 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4834 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4835 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4836 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4837 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4838 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4839 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4840 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times ((C(4) \times (5 - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4841 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + C(5)) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4842 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4843 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4844 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4845 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4846 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 + C(4)) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4847 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4848 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4849 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4850 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4851 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4852 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (4 - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4853 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times C(4 + 5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4854 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3 - C(4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4855 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4856 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4857 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4858 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4859 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4860 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4861 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4862 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4863 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4 + 5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4864 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4865 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4866 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((C(3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4867 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4868 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4829 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4830 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times ((C(5) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4831 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4832 &:= (C(((-9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4833 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) \times (5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4834 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4835 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4836 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4837 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4838 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - (6 + (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4839 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4840 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4841 &:= (-9 \times 8 + C((7 + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4842 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4843 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) + (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4844 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4845 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4846 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4847 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4848 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4849 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4850 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4851 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7 \times 6) + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4852 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4853 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + (6 + (C((5 \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4854 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4855 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4856 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4857 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4858 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4859 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4860 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4861 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4862 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4863 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4864 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4865 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4866 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4867 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4868 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (C(5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4869 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4870 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4871 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times ((4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4872 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4873 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4874 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4875 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4876 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4877 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) \times 4 \times 5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4878 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4879 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4^5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4880 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4881 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4882 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4883 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times ((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4884 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4885 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4886 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(((3 + (4 \times 5)) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4887 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4888 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4889 &:= (C((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (4 - 5 - 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4890 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4891 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4892 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - ((C(4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4893 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4894 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 + 4 + 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4895 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4896 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4897 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4 + 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4898 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4899 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4900 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4901 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4902 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4903 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2^3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4904 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4905 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4906 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4907 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4908 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4869 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4870 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4871 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4872 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4873 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4874 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (((6 \times C(5)) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4875 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4876 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4877 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4878 &:= ((-9 + C(8 + 7 + 6)) - (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4879 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4880 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - ((C(5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4881 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4882 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4883 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4884 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4885 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4886 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4887 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4888 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5)) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4889 &:= (C((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4890 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4891 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4892 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4893 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4894 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (C(6) + C(5))) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4895 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 - (6 - (5 + 4))))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4896 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4897 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times (C(6 + 5) - 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4898 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4899 &:= ((((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4900 &:= (((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - C(5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4901 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4902 &:= ((((-9 \times C(8)) + C((7 + 6 + 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4903 &:= (C((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4904 &:= (-9 + C(((C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4905 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4906 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4907 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4908 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4909 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((C(4+5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4910 &:= (-1 - 2 + C((C(3) + ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4911 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4912 &:= (-1 + C((((2 - 3) - C(4))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4913 &:= C((-1 + ((2 \times (3 - 4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4914 &:= (-1 + 2 + C((C(3) + ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4915 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + C(4)) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4916 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4917 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4918 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4919 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4920 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4921 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4 + 5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4922 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4923 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4924 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4925 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4926 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4927 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4928 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4929 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4930 &:= ((-1 + C((2^3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4931 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4932 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(((3 \times 4) + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4933 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4934 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3 - 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4935 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4936 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4937 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4938 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4939 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 + 5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4940 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(((3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4941 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(((3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4942 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4943 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times ((3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4944 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(((3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4945 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4946 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4947 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4948 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times 4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4909 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4910 &:= (-9 + (C((8 + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4911 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4912 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4913 &:= C((C((-9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4914 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4915 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4916 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4917 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4918 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C((C(7) - (6 + (5 \times C(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4919 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4920 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4921 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4922 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4923 &:= (C((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4924 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4925 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4926 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4927 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4929 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4930 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + C(6) - (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4931 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4932 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4933 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4934 &:= ((((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4935 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4936 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (C(5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4937 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4938 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4939 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (6 + ((C(5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4940 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4941 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4942 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C((6 - (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
4943 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - 5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4944 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4945 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4946 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4947 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4948 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4949 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4950 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4951 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4952 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4953 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4954 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4955 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times 4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4956 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4957 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times 4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4958 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + (4 + 5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4959 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (4 \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4960 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4961 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4962 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4963 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4964 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3 + 4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4965 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4966 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4967 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) \times (4 + 5)) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4968 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3 - 4 - 5))) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4969 &:= 1 + ((2 - 3) \times (4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4970 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4971 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - C(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4972 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4973 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4974 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4975 &:= (-1 + 2^3 - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4976 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4977 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C((4 - (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4978 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times (C(4) + 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4979 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3^4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4980 &:= (1 + (2 + C(3) + 4) \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4981 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3 + 4) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4982 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4983 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) - ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4984 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4^5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4985 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4986 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4987 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4988 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4949 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - C(6)) \times 5)) - (4^{3+2+1})) \\
4950 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C((7 + 6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4951 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4952 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4953 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4954 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4955 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 + 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4956 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4957 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4958 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4959 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4960 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4961 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4962 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4963 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (C(6) \times 5)))) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4964 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4965 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6)))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4966 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4967 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4968 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4969 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4970 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4971 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4972 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4973 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (C(6 + 5) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4974 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4975 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4976 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4977 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4978 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4979 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(6)))) \times 5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4980 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4981 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (C(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4982 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 - 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4983 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4984 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4985 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4986 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4987 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4988 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4989 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4990 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4991 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4992 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4993 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4994 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4995 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4996 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4997 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4998 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4999 &:= (-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5000 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) \times ((C(4) \times (5 - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5001 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5002 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5003 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5004 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (C(4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5005 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5006 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5007 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5008 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times (C(4) - 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5009 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 - C(4) + (-5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5010 &:= (((-1 \times C(2 \times 3))/4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5011 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5012 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5013 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) \times 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5014 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5015 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + (4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5016 &:= (C(1 \times 2 \times 3) + 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5017 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - ((4 \times 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5018 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5019 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5020 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5021 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) - ((4 + 5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5022 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5023 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5024 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (((4 + 5) + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5025 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5026 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5027 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (C(4) + ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4989 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4990 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (7 - 6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4991 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4992 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4993 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4994 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4995 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times (6 - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4996 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + (C(7) + C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4997 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4998 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4999 &:= ((-9 / (8 + 7 - 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5000 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5001 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5002 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5003 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 \times C(4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5004 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5005 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5006 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5007 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5008 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5009 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5010 &:= ((-9 + C((8 - 7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5011 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - C(6)))) \times 5) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5012 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5013 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times C(7))) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5014 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5015 &:= (((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5016 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5017 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5018 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5019 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5020 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6)^5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5021 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - C(4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5022 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5023 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5024 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5025 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5026 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5027 &:= (((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5068 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((4+5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5069 &:= (-1+2 - ((3+4) \times (5 - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
 5070 &:= ((-1-2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 5071 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 5072 &:= ((-1+2+3+4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5073 &:= (((-1+2^3) \times C(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 5074 &:= ((-1+2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 5075 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
 5076 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) + 4+5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5077 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5078 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - ((4 \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5079 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3+4) \times 5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5080 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
 5081 &:= (C((-1+2^3+4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 5082 &:= ((-1+2) \times (3+4) \times ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
 5083 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((4 \times C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
 5084 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - ((4 \times C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
 5085 &:= (((-1+2^3) \times C(4+5)) + (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
 5086 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3+4) - (C(5)+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5087 &:= (-1 + (((2+3-4-5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5088 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((C(4) - 5-6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5089 &:= (1+2) \times C(3 \times 4) - C(5) + 6+7+8+9 \\
 5090 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 3)) \times 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 5091 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3) + (4 - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5092 &:= ((-1 + C(2+3)) - ((4+5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5093 &:= (C(-1+2 \times 3) - ((4+5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5094 &:= (((-1 + (C(2+3) + C(4+5))) \times 6) - (7+8+9)) \\
 5095 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3))/4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 5096 &:= ((-1+2^3) \times ((C(4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
 5097 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5098 &:= (-1-2 - (C(3) - (C(4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5099 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2+3) + C(4+5)) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
 5100 &:= ((-1-2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 5101 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C((C(3) - 4-5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
 5102 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (4 \times (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5103 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (4 \times (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
 5104 &:= ((-1+2 + C((C(3) - 4-5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
 5105 &:= (C(((-1+2) \times ((3 \times 4) + 5))) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
 5106 &:= (-1+2 + (C(((3 \times 4) + 5)) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
 5107 &:= (((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4) \times (5 + C(6))) + 7+8+9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5068 &:= ((((-9-8+7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
 5069 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (5 - (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
 5070 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7-6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 5071 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7-6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 5072 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 5073 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (5+4 - (3+2+1))) \\
 5074 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
 5075 &:= ((-9+8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
 5076 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) \times (C(6) \times 5/(4+3+2+1))) \\
 5077 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 5078 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
 5079 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times (6+5+4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
 5080 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + ((7-6) \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 5081 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
 5082 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (6 + ((5^4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
 5083 &:= ((-9+8 - (C(7) - C(6+5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
 5084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
 5085 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 \times (6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 5086 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (6 - C(5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
 5087 &:= (-9 + (C(((8+7+6) - 5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
 5088 &:= ((-9 + ((8-7+6) \times C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
 5089 &:= 9 + ((C(8) + (7-6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 5090 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (6-5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 5091 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
 5092 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7 - C(6)) \times 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
 5093 &:= ((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6+5)) + (C(4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
 5094 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 5095 &:= ((-9+8 \times (7+6)) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
 5096 &:= (C((-9 - (8-7-6) \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
 5097 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 5098 &:= (((-9-8+7) + (C(6+5) \times 4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
 5099 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7+6+5)) + (4 - C(3+2+1)))))) \\
 5100 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 5101 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - ((7-6)^5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 5102 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times C(((6+5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
 5103 &:= (C((-9+8+7+6)) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 5104 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times (C(6) + C(5))) + (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
 5105 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 - (6 - (5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
 5106 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 5107 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + ((7 - (C(6) + C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5228 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5229 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5230 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) - 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5231 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5232 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5233 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5234 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5235 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5236 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (((4 - 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5237 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5238 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5239 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 + 5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5240 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5241 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5242 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5243 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5244 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 + C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5245 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5246 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5247 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5248 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 + 3 - 4 - 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5249 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) - C(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5250 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5251 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5252 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5253 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5254 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3)/(4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5255 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5256 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5257 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5258 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5259 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5260 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5261 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4) \times C(5)) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5262 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5263 &:= 1 + (-2 + (3 + 4) \times C(5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5264 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5265 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (4 - 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5266 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times ((4 \times 5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5267 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5228 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) + C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5229 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5230 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5231 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5232 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5233 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C((6 - (5 - 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5234 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5235 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5236 &:= 9 - 8 + ((C(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5237 &:= (((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5238 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5239 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5240 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5241 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5242 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5243 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5244 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5245 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5246 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5247 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5248 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5249 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5250 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5251 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5252 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C(6)))) \times 5) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5253 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5254 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5255 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5256 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5257 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - ((C(6 + 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5258 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) + C(5)))) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5259 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5260 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5261 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5262 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5263 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5264 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5265 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5266 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5267 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5268 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((4 \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5269 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^4 + 5 + C(6) \times (7+8+9) \\
5270 &:= ((-1-2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5271 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((4 \times C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5272 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3+4) \times (C(5) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5273 &:= ((-1+2 + C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5274 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - ((4 \times C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5275 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (((4+5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5276 &:= (-1 - (C(2-3+4) - ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5277 &:= (-1-2 + (((3 - (4-5)) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5278 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 - (4-5)) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5279 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5280 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + C(4)))) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5281 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
5282 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - (4 + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5283 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5284 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (((4-5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5285 &:= (((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - C(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5286 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5287 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times 4) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5288 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5289 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5290 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5291 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5292 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + (4 \times (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5293 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3 + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5294 &:= (((-1-2-3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5295 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5296 &:= (C(((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5297 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times 4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5298 &:= (((-1+2-3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5299 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5300 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5301 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5302 &:= ((-1 - (2+3-4)) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5303 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5304 &:= (((-1+2+3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5305 &:= (((-1+2 \times 3) + (4 \times C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5306 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (4+5 - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
5307 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5268 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - ((C(6+5) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
5269 &:= (-9 + ((C(((8-7) \times 6)) - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
5270 &:= (-9+8-7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
5271 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
5272 &:= (-9 \times C(8) - ((C(7) - C(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5273 &:= (-9-8 - (((7 - C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5274 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7+C(6) - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5275 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7+C(6)) \times 5)) + (C(4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
5276 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) \times (6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5277 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
5278 &:= ((((-9-8+7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
5279 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - ((6+5 - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
5280 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + C(6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5281 &:= ((-9 + (C(8+7+6) + C(5))) - (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5282 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
5283 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (5+4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
5284 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - C(6+5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
5285 &:= (-9-8 - (((7 - C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
5286 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (6 - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5287 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7+6+5)) - (4 \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
5288 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7+6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + 3+2+1)))) \\
5289 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5290 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
5291 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7+6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5292 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + (6 - (C(5+4) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
5293 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) + ((5-4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
5294 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) - (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5295 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times 6) \times (5 - C(4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
5296 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + (C(7) + 6)) \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
5297 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5298 &:= ((-9+C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - C(5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
5299 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((C(7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
5300 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C(6)))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5301 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7+6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5302 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1 \\
5303 &:= (-9-8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
5304 &:= ((-9+C(8+7)) - (6 - ((5+4) \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
5305 &:= (-9 - (((8-7 - C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5306 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
5307 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - C(6+5)) \times 4) - C(3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5308 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5309 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) + C(4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5310 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5311 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5312 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5313 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5314 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5315 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5316 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5317 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5318 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5319 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5320 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5321 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4)))/5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5322 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5323 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5324 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5325 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5326 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 - 4 - 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5327 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5328 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5329 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - 4 - 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5330 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5331 &:= (C(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5332 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - (((4 - 5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5333 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (4 - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5334 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times (3 + 4))) - (C(5) + (C(6 + 7) - C((8 + 9))))) \\
5335 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3))/4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5336 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) \times (4 + 5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5337 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (4 + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5338 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5339 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5340 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5341 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5342 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5343 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5344 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5345 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (C(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5346 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5347 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5308 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5309 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5310 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5311 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C((7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5312 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C(6)))) \times 5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5313 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5314 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 + C(5)))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5315 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (((7 \times C(6)) - C(5)) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5316 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5317 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5318 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + C((6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5319 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5320 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5321 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5322 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5323 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5324 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5325 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5326 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5327 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5328 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times C(7)) + C(6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5329 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5330 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - 6 - 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5331 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5332 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5333 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5334 &:= (-9 + (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5335 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5336 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5337 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (((7 + C(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5338 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5339 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7 - C(6)) \times (5 - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5340 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - C(7))) \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5341 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5342 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5343 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + C(6)) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5344 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5345 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5346 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5347 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5348 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5349 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5350 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5351 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5352 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5353 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5354 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5355 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5356 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5357 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3)/4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5358 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5359 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4^5)) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5360 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 \times (C(5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5361 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5362 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5363 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5364 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5365 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5366 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5367 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5368 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5369 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3)/4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5370 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5371 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5372 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5373 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5374 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5375 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5376 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5377 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3 + 4) - (C(5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5378 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5379 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5380 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5381 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times C(4)) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5382 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5383 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5384 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4)))/5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5385 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5386 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5387 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5348 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5349 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 \times (5 + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5350 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5351 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times C(4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5352 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5353 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5)) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5354 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5355 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5356 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + (C(7) + C(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5357 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5358 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5359 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 - 5) + C(4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5360 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5361 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5362 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5363 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5))) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5364 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5365 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5366 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5367 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7 - (6 - 5)) \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5368 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (5^4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5369 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5370 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5371 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + C(7)) \times 6)) - (C(5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5372 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5373 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5374 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5375 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (6 - C(5))) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5376 &:= (-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5377 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5378 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (C((4 + 3)) + C((2 + 1))))) \\
5379 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5380 &:= (((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5381 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5382 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5384 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7 - C(6)) \times 5 \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5385 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (C(7) + ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5386 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5387 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) - 5) + (4^{3+2+1}))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5428 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (((4 + 5) + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5429 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5430 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (C(4) - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5431 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5432 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5433 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5434 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5435 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 + 3) - C(4 + 5)) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5436 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5437 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5438 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5439 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times ((C(4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5440 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) - ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5441 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))))) \\
5442 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 3 \times C(4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5443 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5444 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5445 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5446 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5447 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5448 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5449 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((C(3) \times 4) + C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5450 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5451 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5452 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (4 - (C(5) - (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
5453 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5454 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5455 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3)) - (C(4) - ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5456 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))))) \\
5457 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(((4 \times 5) - 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5458 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(((4 \times 5) - 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5459 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5460 &:= ((-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5461 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5462 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + C(5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5463 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))) \\
5464 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5465 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5466 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5467 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5428 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6 - C(5)) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5429 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + C(6)) \times 5))) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5430 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7 + 6) \times (C(5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5431 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5432 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5433 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5434 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5435 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5436 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5437 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + C(6)) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5438 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5439 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5440 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5441 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5442 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5443 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + ((C(5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5444 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5445 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5446 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5447 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5448 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5449 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times C(5)))) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5450 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5451 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5452 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5453 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5454 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) - 7) \times 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5455 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5456 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5457 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times C(7)) - 6 - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5458 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + C(6)))) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5459 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (6 - ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5460 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5461 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5462 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + C(6)))) \times 5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5463 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times C(7)) - C((6 + 5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5464 &:= ((((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5)) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5465 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5))))) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5466 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5467 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) + ((4 + 3) - 2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5468 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5469 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + 4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5470 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5471 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 - 4 - 5)) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5472 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5473 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5474 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5475 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5476 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5477 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3 + 4)) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5478 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5479 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5480 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5481 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5482 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5483 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5484 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5485 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5486 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5487 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5488 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 \times ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5489 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5490 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5491 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5492 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5493 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times C(4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5494 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5495 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5496 &:= (((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5497 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5498 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5499 &:= (-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5500 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5501 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + C((5 + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5502 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5503 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (((4 - 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5504 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5505 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (C(4) \times 5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5506 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(((4 \times 5) - 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5507 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times 5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5468 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5469 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5470 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5471 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((C(7) - 6) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5472 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5473 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5474 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5475 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5476 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5477 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times (6 + C(5))) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5478 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5480 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5481 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5482 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5483 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 + 7) \times 6) / 5)) - (C((4 + 3)) - 2 - 1)) \\
5484 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - 6 - 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5485 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C((6 + 5 - 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5486 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5487 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5488 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - C((6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5489 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - C((6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5490 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5491 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times C(7)) + 6) / 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5492 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5493 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6 - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5494 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5495 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5496 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C((6 + 5 - 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5497 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5498 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5499 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5500 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5501 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times C(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5502 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5503 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 - 6) \times 5) \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5504 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5505 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (C(5) + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5506 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5507 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1}))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5548 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5549 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (C(4) - C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5550 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5551 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5552 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5553 &:= (((-1 + C(2^3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5554 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5555 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5556 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5557 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5558 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5559 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5560 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5561 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5562 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 + 5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5563 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5564 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5565 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5566 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 + 5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5567 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5568 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5569 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5570 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5571 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 \times (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5572 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5573 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5574 &:= (-1 - (((C(2 + 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5575 &:= (-1 \times (((C(2 + 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5576 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5577 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5578 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5579 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) - (C(4) - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5580 &:= ((-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5581 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5582 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) + (5 - (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
5583 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (((4 \times 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5584 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5585 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9))) \\
5586 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + C(5)))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5587 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5548 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5549 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5550 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5551 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5552 &:= (C(((9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5))) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5553 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5554 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3))) \times C((2 + 1)))) \\
5555 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5556 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5557 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + ((C(5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5558 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5559 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6 - (C(5) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5560 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5561 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7)) / 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5562 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5563 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + C((6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5564 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5565 &:= (-9 + (((C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + C(5))) / 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5566 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 \times 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5568 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5569 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5570 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5571 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5572 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5573 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times C(6 + 5))) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5574 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5575 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 - (C(6) - C(5))) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5576 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5577 &:= (9 \times (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5578 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) + (C(5) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5579 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C((6 + 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5580 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5581 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5582 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5583 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5584 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5585 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) + 6)) + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5586 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5587 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5588 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5589 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5590 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5591 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5592 &:= (C((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - 4 - 5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5593 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5594 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5595 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5596 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5597 &:= (((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5598 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) + 4) \times 5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5599 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5600 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5601 &:= ((((-1 + C(2^3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5602 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5603 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5604 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5605 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5606 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
5607 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5608 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5609 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) + 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5610 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5611 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times C(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5612 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
5613 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - (4 + 5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5614 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (4 + 5 - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5615 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5616 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5617 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - (4 + 5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5618 &:= (((-1 - (C(2 + 3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5619 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5620 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times C(4) - (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)))) \\
5621 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5622 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4 + 5)) - ((6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
5623 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times C(4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5624 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (C(5) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5625 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times ((5 \times C(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5626 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C((4 \times 5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5627 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5588 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5589 &:= ((-9 + C(((8 - 7) \times 6))) \times C((5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5590 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5591 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5592 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5593 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5594 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5595 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C((7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5596 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5597 &:= (-9 - ((8 + ((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5598 &:= (9 \times C(8)) - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5599 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - C(5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5600 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5601 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5602 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6))) - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5603 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5604 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5605 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5606 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5607 &:= ((9 \times C(8)) - ((7 - 6)^5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5608 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5609 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5610 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5611 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5612 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5613 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5614 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5615 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5616 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5617 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + ((6^5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5618 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + (C(6 + 5) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5619 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5620 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5621 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - C(6 + 5)) / 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5622 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5623 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5624 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5625 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5626 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) + (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5627 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) + (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

5668 := $((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5669 := $-(-1 + 2)^3 + (C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
5670 := $((C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5671 := $((-1 + 2)^3 + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5672 := $(-1 - ((C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5673 := $((-1 + 2) \times 3 + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5674 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5675 := $((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5676 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5677 := $(-1 + (2^3 + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5678 := $((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5679 := $((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5680 := $((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5681 := $((-1 \times 2 \times (3 + C(4))) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)))$
5682 := $((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5683 := $((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5684 := $((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
5685 := $((-1 - 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
5686 := $((-1 \times 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
5687 := $(-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4 + 5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5688 := $((-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) + 5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
5689 := $(-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5690 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$
5691 := $(C(-1 + 2^3) + ((4 \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5692 := $(-1 + 2 + (C(3) + (((4 \times 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5693 := $(-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (C(4 + 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5694 := $(-1 - 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5695 := $(-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5696 := $(C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5697 := $(C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5698 := $(-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5699 := $(-1 - (((2 - 3) - (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5700 := $((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5701 := $(C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5702 := $((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) - ((5 + 6 - C(7)) \times (8 + 9))$
5703 := $(-1 - 2 - ((3 \times C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5704 := $(-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5705 := $(-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5706 := $(-1 - (C(2 + 3) - C(((4 + 5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5707 := $(-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - C(((4 + 5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))$

5668 := $(-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) - C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5669 := $(-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5670 := $(-9 - 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5671 := $((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
5672 := $(-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5673 := $((-9 \times ((8 \times C(7)) - C((6 + 5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
5674 := $(((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + C(5)))) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
5675 := $((-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((C(6) - 5) \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))$
5676 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
5677 := $((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
5678 := $((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + C(5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
5679 := $(-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5680 := $((-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5681 := $(((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
5682 := $((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$
5683 := $(-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5684 := $(((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6)/5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
5685 := $(-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + ((C(6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5686 := $(-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5687 := $((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5688 := $(((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
5689 := $(-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) \times 6) + (5 + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))))$
5690 := $((-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5691 := $((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5692 := $(-9 \times 8 + (((7 \times C(6)) - C(5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))$
5693 := $((-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2 - 1)$
5694 := $(-9 + (C(8) + (7 + ((C(6)/(5 + 4)) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
5695 := $(-9 - 8 + ((7 + (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$
5696 := $(-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
5697 := $(-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5698 := $((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
5699 := $((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1}))$
5700 := $(-9 + ((C(8) + 7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5701 := $((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6)) \times (C(5) - C(4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1))$
5702 := $((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
5703 := $(-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6 - C(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
5704 := $(((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) - C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
5705 := $((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + C(6))) + (C((5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
5706 := $(-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5707 := $((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + C(6)) \times 5)) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
5708 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5709 &:= (((((-1+2)^3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5710 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) + 5) - (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
5711 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) \times 4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5712 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5713 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5714 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5715 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times ((5 \times C(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5716 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5717 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (C(4) + 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5718 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times 5))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5719 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5720 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5721 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5722 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) + ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5723 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5724 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4 \times 5) + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5725 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5726 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 - C(4))) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9))) \\
5727 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5728 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (((4 \times 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5729 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5730 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5731 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5732 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5733 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5734 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5735 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5736 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5737 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times (5 \times 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5738 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 \times (5 - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5739 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 \times (C(5) + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5740 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5741 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) + (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5742 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5743 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (((4 + 5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5744 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times C(3 + 4))) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5745 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5746 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times 5) - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5747 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (C(4) \times 5))) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5708 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + ((C(6) - (5 - (4 + 3))) \times C((2 + 1)))))) \\
5709 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + (7 \times C(6 + 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5710 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5711 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5712 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5713 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + C(6))) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5714 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times C(5)) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5715 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5716 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5717 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5718 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + C((6 + 5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5719 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + 5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5720 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5721 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5722 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1) \\
5723 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5724 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5725 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5726 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5727 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5728 &:= ((((-9 + 8 \times 7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5729 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5730 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5731 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((C(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5732 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5733 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5734 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - ((C(7) + C(6)) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5735 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6) + ((5 + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5736 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5737 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7 + 6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5738 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5739 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times C(5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5740 &:= (((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5741 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5742 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5743 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5744 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times C(7)) - (6 - C(5)))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5745 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5746 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (6 \times (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5747 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times C(6)) - C(5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5788 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - (C(4+5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
5789 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5790 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) + (4 + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5791 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
5792 &:= (-1-2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5793 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5794 &:= (-1 + ((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5795 &:= ((C(-1+2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5796 &:= (-1+2 - ((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5797 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) \times 4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5798 &:= (-1+2-3 - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
5799 &:= ((-1-2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5800 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5801 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5802 &:= (C((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4 - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5803 &:= ((-1+2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5804 &:= (-1+2+3 - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
5805 &:= ((-1-2 + C((3 + (4+5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5806 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C((3 + (4+5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5807 &:= ((-1 + C(((2 \times (3+4+5)) - 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5808 &:= (C(((-1+2) \times (3 + (4+5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
5809 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5810 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (5+6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5811 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4 \times C(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5812 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C((C(3) - 4 - 5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
5813 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 \times C(4+5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
5814 &:= (C((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4 - 5)) + (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
5815 &:= (-1+2 + (C((C(3) - 4 - 5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
5816 &:= (C((-1+2+3+4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5817 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
5818 &:= (-1-2 - (C(3) + ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5819 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5820 &:= (((-1 + (2+3) \times C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5821 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C((C(3) - 4 - 5))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
5822 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4+5))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
5823 &:= (-1 - ((C(2^3) - C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
5824 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3) \times (C(4) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
5825 &:= (-1-2 \times 3 + C(((4+5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
5826 &:= ((-1-2-3) + C(((4+5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
5827 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + C(((4+5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5788 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7+6)) + (5 - (4 \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
5789 &:= (((-9+8 \times (7+6)) \times (C(5) - C(4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
5790 &:= (((-9+8-7) \times (6 - C(5+4))) + 3+2+1) \\
5791 &:= ((-9-8 + C((7+6+5))) - (4 \times (3+2+1))) \\
5792 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5793 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (((7 - C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5794 &:= ((-9-8-7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
5795 &:= ((-9-8 + (((7 \times C(6)) - 5) \times 4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
5796 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) + (C(6) + (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5797 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 - C(6)) \times 5))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
5798 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
5799 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) + (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
5800 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + 7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5801 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5802 &:= ((-9-8 - (C(7) - (C(6+5) - 4))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
5803 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7+6) - C((5 \times ((4+3) - 2 - 1)))))) \\
5804 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5805 &:= ((-9-8 + C((7+6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5806 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7+6))) - ((5^4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
5807 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) \times 5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5808 &:= (-9-8-7 + C((6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
5809 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7-6) - C(5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
5810 &:= (((-9+8-7 + C(6)) - C(5)) \times (C(4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5811 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)) \\
5812 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + C(7)) - 6) \times 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5813 &:= ((-9 + C((((8+7) \times 6)/5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5814 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
5815 &:= (-9-8 + C((7+6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5816 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
5817 &:= ((-9 + C((8+7 - (6 - (5+4)))))) - (3+2+1)) \\
5818 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7+6+5)) + (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
5819 &:= ((C((-9+8+7+6)) - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
5820 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6 - (5-4))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
5821 &:= ((-9+8 + C((7+6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5822 &:= (C(((-9 \times 8)/(7-6-5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5823 &:= (-9 + C((((C(8) - (C(7) - 6 - 5))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5824 &:= (-9+8-7 + C((6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
5825 &:= (-9-8 + (C((7+6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5826 &:= (C((-9 \times (8 - (7 - (6 - (5+4)))))) - (3+2+1)) \\
5827 &:= (-9-8 + (((C(7) + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5868 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5869 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C((C(3) - (4 \times 5)))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5870 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (C(4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 5871 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times C(4) + C((5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 5872 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5873 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5874 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5875 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5876 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5877 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) \times 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5878 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 5879 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5880 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 + (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5881 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) \times ((4 - 5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5882 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 5883 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5884 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5885 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5886 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5887 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5888 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5889 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5890 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5891 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - 3) \times C(4))) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5892 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 5893 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) - 4) \times C(5))) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5894 &:= ((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - ((5 + (6 + 7)) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
 5895 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5896 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + C(((4 + 5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5897 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5898 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (((4 + C(5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5899 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5900 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4 + 5)))) - ((6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
 5901 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5902 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5903 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times ((4 + 5) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5904 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5905 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5906 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 5907 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times C(4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 5868 &:= (-9 \times (C((8 - 7 + 6)) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5869 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5870 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5871 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5872 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - C(5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
 5873 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5874 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - C(5))) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5875 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5876 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5877 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - C(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5878 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5879 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5880 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) + C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5881 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5882 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5883 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times ((C(6) + 5) \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5884 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
 5885 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5886 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6 - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5887 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5888 &:= (-9 - (C(8 + 7) - ((6 + 5) + C(((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 5889 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5890 &:= (C(((9 \times 8)/(7 - 6 - 5))) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5891 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5892 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5893 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5894 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5895 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5896 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5897 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5898 &:= ((-9 - 8 + C((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5899 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5900 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + C(5)) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5901 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5902 &:= (C(((9 \times 8)/(7 - 6 - 5))) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5903 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5904 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (C(6) + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 5905 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - (6 \times (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5906 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 5907 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

6028 := $(-1 \times 2 - ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6029 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((3 + C(4)) \times ((5 \times C(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6030 := $(((-1 + 2 - 3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
6031 := $(-1 + 2 - ((3 + C(4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6032 := $(-1 + (C(2 + 3 + 4) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6033 := $(C((-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6034 := $(-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 + C((5 + (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9))))$
6035 := $C(1 \times 2 \times 3) + 4 + C(5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$
6036 := $(-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - ((C(4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9))))$
6037 := $(-1 + (C(2 + 3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6038 := $(C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6039 := $((((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
6040 := $((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (C(5) - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6041 := $(-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + ((4 - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6042 := $((-1 - C(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6043 := $((-1 \times C(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6044 := $(-1 + ((2 - (C(3) - C(4))) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
6045 := $(-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + ((4 + 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6046 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + ((4 + 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6047 := $(-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + C(((4 + 5) + (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))))))$
6048 := $((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
6049 := $(-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + ((4 + 5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6050 := $(-1 - 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6051 := $(-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6052 := $((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
6053 := $(-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C((4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6054 := $(-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6055 := $(-1 + ((2^3 \times (4 + (C(5) \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6056 := $(-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6057 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6058 := $((-1 + C(2 \times 3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6059 := $(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6060 := $(-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6061 := $(((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times 4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9))$
6062 := $(-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 + (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9))))$
6063 := $(((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6064 := $(C((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4))) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
6065 := $(-1 - ((C(2 \times 3) - (4 - C(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
6066 := $((-1 - 2) \times (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6067 := $((C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)$

6028 := $((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - (C(6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6029 := $(-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6030 := $(-9 \times ((8 - C(7)) \times (6 / (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6031 := $(-9 + ((C(8 + 7 - 6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6032 := $(-9 - (C(8) + (C(7 + 6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6033 := $(-9 + (((8 \times (C(7) - C(6))) - (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$
6034 := $(C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
6035 := $(((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - C(6)))) \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6036 := $((-9 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6037 := $((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6038 := $((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6039 := $(-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (C(6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6040 := $(-9 \times 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6041 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - 5 - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6042 := $(((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6 - (5 - 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)$
6043 := $(-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6044 := $(C(((9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5))) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
6045 := $((-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6)))) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
6046 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) + (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
6047 := $(-9 + ((8 \times ((7 - 6) + C(5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
6048 := $(C(-9 + 8 + 7) + C((6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6049 := $((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) \times 5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6050 := $(-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6051 := $(-9 + (((C(8) - 7) \times 6) / 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6052 := $(-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6053 := $(-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6054 := $((-9 + C(8) - (7 + C(6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$
6055 := $(-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
6056 := $((((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) / 5) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))$
6057 := $(-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6058 := $((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
6059 := $(-9 - ((C(8 + 7) - (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6060 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) \times 5 - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6061 := $(-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6062 := $(-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6063 := $(-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times C(6))) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6064 := $((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)) \times (5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
6065 := $((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
6066 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6067 := $(-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
6068 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((C(4) \times (5 + (6+7))) + C((8+9)))) & 6068 &:= ((-9 - (((C(8) - 7) \times 6) - 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6069 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6069 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6) - (5-4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6070 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6070 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6071 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 6071 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6072 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6072 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (C(7) \times (6 - (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6073 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6073 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times C(6) + 5) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
6074 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6074 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6075 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6075 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6076 &:= ((-1 + C(2+3)) \times (4 + ((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))) & 6076 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) + 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6077 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + C(6))) + 7+8+9)) & 6077 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6078 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6078 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) - C(4)))))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6079 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7+6) \times C(5)) - (4 \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6080 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 6080 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times (((6+5) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
6081 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6081 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7))) \times 6) + (5 + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6082 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3+4) - 5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 6082 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times ((6 + C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6083 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6083 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6084 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6085 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6085 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 \times C(5)) + 4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6086 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3+4) + (5 + (6+7)))) \times (8+9)) & 6086 &:= (((-9 - (8+7+6)) + C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3+2+1 \\
6087 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6087 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (C(6) - C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6088 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - ((C(4) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6088 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6089 &:= (1+2) \times 3 + C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 6089 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((C(6) \times 5 - C(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6090 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3^4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 6090 &:= ((-9 + (((8+7+6) - 5) \times C(4))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6091 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 6091 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6092 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + ((C(4) \times (5 + (6+7))) + C((8+9)))) & 6092 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6093 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + C(5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) & 6093 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6094 &:= (((-1+2 - C(3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 6094 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))))) + 4+3+2+1 \\
6095 &:= ((((-1+2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 6095 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6096 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) & 6096 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6097 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times ((4+5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9)) & 6097 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + (4 \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
6098 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) & 6098 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5) + (C((4+3)) - C((2+1)))))) \\
6099 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((4+5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9) & 6099 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 + C(6) - C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6100 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times ((4+5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9)) & 6100 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5+4))) + 3+2+1))) \\
6101 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4 - (C(5) + 6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6101 &:= (-9 - (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
6102 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((C(3) \times 4) + 5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 6102 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + C(7))) + C(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6103 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 + (2 + C(5)) \times (7+8+9)) & 6103 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + C((6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
6104 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6104 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6105 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6105 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6106 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6106 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times (C(6) + C(5))) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6107 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6107 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times ((C(6) - 5) \times 4)) + C(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6147 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 6147 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (6+C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6148 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) & 6148 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7+6) \times (C(5+4) - C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6149 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (C(4)+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6149 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7+C(6))) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6150 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (C(4)+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 6150 &:= ((-9+C(8) - (7+6-C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6151 &:= (((-1+2^3)^4) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6151 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7+6)) \times (5-C(4)))) + (3+2+1) \\
6152 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times (4^5)) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 6152 &:= (((-9+8-C(7)) \times 6) + (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3+2+1))) \\
6153 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6153 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 + C(5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6154 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6154 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))))) + (C(4) + 3+2+1) \\
6155 &:= ((((-1+2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 6155 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (6+C(5))) + (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6156 &:= ((-1+2 - C((C(3) - (4 \times 5)))) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) & 6156 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6157 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) + C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) & 6157 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) \times (6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
6158 &:= (C((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9))) & 6158 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7)+6)) + C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6159 &:= (1+2+3 \times C(4)) \times 5 + C(6) \times (7+8+9) & 6159 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (C((7+6-5)) + 4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6160 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (C(4) - ((C(5)+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6160 &:= ((-9 - ((8-7-6) \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6161 &:= (1+2) \times C(3) + C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 6161 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) - (((C(6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6162 &:= (-1-2 + ((3+4)! + (C(5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) & 6162 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) \times (7 - (6-5)))) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6163 &:= (C(((-1+2+C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (6! - (7+8+9))) & 6163 &:= (-9 + (C((((8+7) \times 6)/5)) + (C((4+3)) - 2 - 1))) \\
6164 &:= (((-1-2 + (C(3)+4)) \times (5+C(6))) - (7+8+9)) & 6164 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((C(6+5) \times 4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
6165 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) & 6165 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 - ((6-C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6166 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + C(5+6) + 7+8+9) & 6166 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (6 - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6167 &:= 1+2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + C(5+6) + 7+8+9) & 6167 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (6+C(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6168 &:= (1+2^{C(3+4+5)/C(6)}) \times (7+8+9) & 6168 &:= (((-9+C(8+7+6))/(5+4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6169 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) - (4 \times C(5) - C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) & 6169 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6170 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3)+4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))))) & 6170 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1))))))) \\
6171 &:= 1+2 + (-C(3) + 4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9) & 6171 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7 \times (C(6) - C(5))) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6172 &:= (1+C(2 \times 3)) \times 4 + (5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9) & 6172 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
6173 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 \times 4^5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 6173 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
6174 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6174 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (C(6) - C(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6175 &:= ((((-1+2)^3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 6175 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (C(6) \times 5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
6176 &:= (-1 + ((2+C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5+6 \times (7+8+9)))))) & 6176 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((C(6+5) \times 4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
6177 &:= (-1-2 + (((3^4) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6177 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) + (C(6) \times 5)) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6178 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6178 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6179 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) \times 4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 6179 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) \times (7+6))) - C(5)) - ((4+3)^{2+1})) \\
6180 &:= (((-1+C(2 \times 3)) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 6180 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times ((6 \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6181 &:= (-1+2 + (((3^4) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6181 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1))) \\
6182 &:= ((-1+2 - C(3)) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6182 &:= (((C(-9+8+7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
6183 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) + (((4+C(5)) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6183 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - C(6))) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6184 &:= (C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4+5)))) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) & 6184 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times (7+6)) + 5)) \times C(4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6185 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 6185 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) + ((5-C(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6186 &:= (((-1-2 - C(3)) \times (4+5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) & 6186 &:= (C(-9+8+7) - (6 \times (5 - C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6187 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
6188 &:= (-1+2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6189 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + (5+C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6190 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + (5+C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6191 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3+4+C(5))) - 6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6192 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times (4+5)) + 6) \times (7+8+9) \\
6193 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) - (C(4) + (5+C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6194 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C((4 \times 5)) + ((6+7) - C((8+9)))))) \\
6195 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6196 &:= ((-1+2+C(3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6197 &:= 1 \times 2 + C(3) + 4^5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6198 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) \times 6))) + 7+8+9) \\
6199 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6200 &:= ((-1+C(2+3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6201 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6202 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6203 &:= 1 - 2 \times 3 + 4^5 + C(6) \times (7+8+9) \\
6204 &:= (-1 + (C(2+3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6205 &:= (-1 + ((2+C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6206 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
6207 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6208 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6209 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6210 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6211 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6212 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6213 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6214 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
6215 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
6216 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
6217 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times C(4)) - ((C(5) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))))) \\
6218 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3+4)) + 5) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6219 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6220 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) - ((5 \times (6+7)) - C((8+9)))) \\
6221 &:= ((-1+2 \times C(3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
6222 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4) + (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9)))) \\
6223 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times ((4^5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
6224 &:= (-1 - ((2-C(3)) \times ((4+5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6225 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times ((4+5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6187 &:= (-9+8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4+C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6188 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (C(6) - (5 \times (4+C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6189 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) \times 6)) \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
6190 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (5+C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6191 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(((5-4) \times (3+2+1))))))) \\
6192 &:= ((-9+8 - C(7)) \times ((6 - (5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6193 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 \times ((C(6) + 5) \times 4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
6194 &:= (((C(-9+8+7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1) \\
6195 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - ((6+5) \times C(4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6196 &:= (((C((-9+8+7+6)) - C(5)) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6197 &:= (-9 + (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
6198 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) - C(5)))) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
6199 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6200 &:= ((-9-8 + (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6201 &:= (-9 \times (8-7 - (6 \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6202 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5) - (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
6203 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - 5)) \times 4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
6204 &:= (((-9-8) \times ((7-6) - C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6205 &:= ((-9-8) \times (((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6206 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times C(5))) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
6207 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
6208 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + C(6)) \times C(((5+(4+3))/(2+1))) \\
6209 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + C(6)))) + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6210 &:= (9 \times ((8-7) \times 6)) \times (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6211 &:= ((-9 \times ((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6212 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) \times 4))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6213 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (C(7) \times (6 - (5+4)))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6214 &:= (((C(-9+8+7) + (6 - C(5))) \times C(4)) + 3+2+1) \\
6215 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + (C(6) + C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6216 &:= (C(((9 \times 8)/(7-6-5))) + (C(4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6217 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5))) - (4 \times (3+2+1))) \\
6218 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times C(5))) \times 4) + 3+2+1) \\
6219 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + 6) - C(5+4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
6220 &:= (((-9 \times ((8+C(7)) - 6)) - 5) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6221 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times C(6)) - C(5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6222 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6223 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) - (7 \times 6))/5) \times C(4)) + C(3+2+1)) \\
6224 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + ((7+6) \times C(5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6225 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + ((6+5) \times C(4)))) \times (3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6266 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6267 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6268 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6269 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (C(4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6270 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) + 4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6271 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6272 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6273 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6274 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6275 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6276 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6277 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 + 3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6278 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9))) \\
6279 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6280 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6281 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) + (C(4) \times 5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6282 &:= (((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + 4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6283 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6284 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + 6) + (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\
6285 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6286 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6287 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6288 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (4 - 5)) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6289 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6290 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6291 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) - C(4 + 5))) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6292 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6293 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6294 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6295 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6296 &:= ((-1 + C(2^3)) - (C(4) - (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9))) \\
6297 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
6298 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (C(3) + C(4))) \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6299 &:= (-1 - (((2 + C(3)) - C(4 + 5)) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6300 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times 4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6301 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6302 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6303 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6304 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) + 4)) \times ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6266 &:= ((((-9 + C(8) - 7 - 6) / 5) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6267 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6268 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6269 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6270 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - ((7 - 6) - C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6271 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7 + 6)) - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6272 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6273 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6274 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 - ((C(6) + (5 - (4 + 3))) \times C((2 + 1))))) \\
6275 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) + (((C(7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6276 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6)))) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6277 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6278 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6279 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (C(6) + (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6280 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + C(((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6281 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6282 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6283 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5) \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6284 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6285 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) - C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6286 &:= ((((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - C(6 + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6287 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6288 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (C(6) / (5 + 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6289 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6290 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - 6) + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6291 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6292 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5)))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6293 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6294 &:= (((-9 - 8 + C(7)) - (6 - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6295 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6296 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times C(6)) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6297 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (C(7 + 6) + 5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6298 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6299 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) - (C(6) + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6300 &:= ((((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - C(6)) / 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6301 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6302 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (C(5) + (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6303 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times C(6)) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6304 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - C((5 - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6305 &:= (C((-1+2+3) \times 4) - (5 - (C(6+7) + 8+9))) & 6305 &:= (-9+8+(((7+C(6)) \times 5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6306 &:= (((-1+2 - (C(3)+4)) \times (5 - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) & 6306 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (C(6+5) - (C(4)+C(3+2+1)))) \\
6307 &:= ((-1+2 \times C(3)) \times (4 - (C(5) - (C(6)+7+8+9)))) & 6307 &:= ((-9+((8+((7+6) \times C(5))) \times 4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6308 &:= (-1+((C(2+3) \times (4+5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6308 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
6309 &:= ((C(-1+2 \times 3) \times (4+5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9))) & 6309 &:= (-9+((8+C(7)) \times (6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
6310 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times (C(4) - C(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) & 6310 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6311 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (C(4) - C(5+6))) - (7+8+9)) & 6311 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C((7+6+5)) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6312 &:= 1 - ((2+3) \times (C(4) - C(5+6)) + 7+8+9) & 6312 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (C(6) - (5+C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6313 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 6313 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) \times (6+5 - C(4))) + 3+2+1) \\
6314 &:= (-1+((C(2+3) \times 4) + (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9)))) & 6314 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) - ((5+4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
6315 &:= (-1-2 - ((C(3) - C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 6315 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (C(6) + (C(5) \times 4)))) + 3+2+1) \\
6316 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((C(3) - C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 6316 &:= (((-9 \times (8+C(7))) + (6-5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6317 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times ((4-5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9) & 6317 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7)+6))) + (C((5 \times 4)) - C(3+2+1))) \\
6318 &:= ((-1-2 - (C(3+4) + 5)) \times (6 - (7+8+9))) & 6318 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6) + (5+C(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6319 &:= (-1+2 - ((C(3) - C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 6319 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6320 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + (5 \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) & 6320 &:= (((-9+C(8) - 7) \times (6+5)) + (4 \times C(3+2+1))) \\
6321 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times (4 + (5+(6+7)))) + C((8+9))) & 6321 &:= (-9+(((8 \times (7+C(6))) - C(5+4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6322 &:= ((-1+C(2^3)) - (4 - (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9)))) & 6322 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) - ((5-4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
6323 &:= (1+C(2^3) + C(4)) \times (5+6) - 7-8-9 & 6323 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7 \times (6+5) - C(4))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6324 &:= ((-1+C(2+3)) \times (C(4) + (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) & 6324 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((C(7) - (6 - C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6325 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 6325 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7+6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6326 &:= (-1+((2^3 \times C(4)) + (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9)))) & 6326 &:= (-9+((8 \times C(7)) + (C(6) + C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6327 &:= ((-1+2 - (C(3) - C(4+5))) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) & 6327 &:= ((-9+((8 \times 7) \times (6+C(5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
6328 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 6328 &:= (-9+C(8) - (7 - C((6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
6329 &:= (-1+(((2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6329 &:= ((-9+((8 \times (7+6)) \times (C(5) - C(4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6330 &:= ((C((-1-2+C(3))/4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 6330 &:= (((-9-8+C(7)) \times 6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6331 &:= (-1+2+(((C(3)+4^5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) & 6331 &:= (-9+((C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6)+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6332 &:= ((-1+C(2+3)) + ((4^5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 6332 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) + (5+4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
6333 &:= (-1-2 - ((3^4 - C(5)) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 6333 &:= (-9-8+((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6334 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3^4 - C(5)) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 6334 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(((4+3) - 2 - 1))))) \\
6335 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (C(3) + C(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 6335 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + C((7+6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6336 &:= (C(-1+2+3) \times (C(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 6336 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) - 6))) + C(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6337 &:= (-1+2 - ((3^4 - C(5)) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 6337 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6338 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (C(4+5) - (6+7)))) - C((8+9)))) & 6338 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - C((C(7) - (6 \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))))) \\
6339 &:= (-1+(((2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) & 6339 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6340 &:= (((-1-2+C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) & 6340 &:= ((-9+8+((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6341 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) & 6341 &:= (-9+(((8 \times (7+6)) \times (C(5) - C(4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6342 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) & 6342 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 + C((6 \times (5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
6343 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + C(((4+5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9))))) & 6343 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) + ((5 \times 4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
6344 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - ((4+5) \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 6344 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5) + (C(4) + 3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6345 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6346 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6347 &:= (-1 \times (C(2^3) - C((C(4) - ((5 \times C(6))/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6348 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6349 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + C(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6350 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) + (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6351 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (C(4) + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6352 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - ((6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
6353 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - ((5 - (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6354 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (C(3) + 4)) \times (5 - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6355 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6356 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times ((4 \times (5 + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6357 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (C(4) + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6358 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6359 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6360 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((C(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6361 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (C(4) + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6362 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6363 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6364 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (4 + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)))) \\
6365 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6366 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6367 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + (C(5) - (C(6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6368 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6369 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6370 &:= ((-1 + C(2 - 3 + 4)) \times (5 + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6371 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3 \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6372 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times ((C(4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6373 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 + (C(4 + 5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6374 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6375 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6376 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6377 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - ((6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6378 &:= (((-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times 5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6379 &:= (-1 + ((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6380 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6381 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6382 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6383 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6384 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6345 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8) - (C(7) + C(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6346 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6347 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6348 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6349 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6350 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6351 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6352 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) - ((6 \times 5) \times (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6353 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6354 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6) - (5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6355 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6356 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6357 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6358 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (6 - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6359 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6360 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6361 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + C(((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6362 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6363 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6364 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6365 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (C(5) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6366 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) - C(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6367 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7 + 6) - (5 \times (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6368 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (((6 + 5) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6369 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6370 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (C(5) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6371 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + ((7 - 6) + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6372 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6373 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) - ((C(5) - C((4 + 3))) \times C((2 + 1)))))) \\
6374 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 + ((6 - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6375 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6376 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6377 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + ((5 \times 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6378 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) - C(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6379 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - (6 - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6380 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6381 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7 \times 6) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6382 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6383 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6384 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6385 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6386 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 - (C(4 + 5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6387 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7))) + 8 + 9) \\
6388 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6389 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6390 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6391 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (C(3) \times (4 - (5 + (6 + 7)))))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6392 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (5 + (6 + 7)))))) \times (8 + 9) \\
6393 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) \times ((4 \times 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6394 &:= ((((-1 - 2 - 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6395 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6396 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6397 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6398 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6399 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((4 + 5) \times (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6400 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6401 &:= ((-1 + ((C(2 \times 3)/4) \times (C(5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6402 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + (C(4 + 5) + (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6403 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (C(3 \times 4) - C(5))) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
6404 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - C(3)) \times C(4))) \times (5 - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6405 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - C(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6406 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - ((5 + (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6407 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6408 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times C(4)) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6409 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6410 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6411 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + C(4 + 5)))) - ((6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
6412 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6413 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3 + 4) + 5)) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6414 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) + 5)) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6415 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - C(5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6416 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (4 + ((C(5) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6417 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + C(4))) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6418 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (5 - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6419 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) + (C(4) + C(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6420 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6422 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3 + 4) \times 5) - ((6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6423 &:= (C(-1 + 2^3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6424 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6385 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((C(6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6386 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((C(6 + 5) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6387 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times ((C(6) + 5) \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6388 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6389 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (7 \times C(6) + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6390 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times C(6))/5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6391 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6392 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6 - 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6393 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6394 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6395 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) - (6 - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6396 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6397 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6398 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6399 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6400 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6401 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + C(5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6402 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6403 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 \times C(5)))) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6404 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6405 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6406 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6407 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6408 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6409 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6410 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6411 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + (6 + C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6412 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6413 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6414 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - (7 - C(6))) \times (5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6415 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6416 &:= (((-9 - 8 - C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6417 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6418 &:= (((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) - C(5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6419 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6420 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6421 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6422 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6423 &:= (-9 + ((C((8 - 7 + 6)) + C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6424 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6425 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6426 &:= ((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6427 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times ((4 - (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6428 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3 + 4)) - (5 + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
6429 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3 + 4)) + (5 + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6430 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
6431 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) + 4 - 5)) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6432 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6433 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6434 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6435 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6436 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6437 &:= ((((-1 - 2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6438 &:= ((((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) + 4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6439 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + C(4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6440 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
6441 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6442 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + ((C(5) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6443 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + (4 \times C(5))) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6444 &:= (C(1 \times 2 \times 3) + 4 \times C(5)) \times C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
6445 &:= 1 + (C(2 \times 3) + 4 \times C(5)) \times C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
6446 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 \times (C(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
6447 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6448 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7)) - C((8 + 9))) \\
6449 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6450 &:= ((-1 + C(((2 \times C(3))/(4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6451 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times ((4 - 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6452 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (4 \times C(5))) \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9) \\
6453 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6454 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6455 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6456 &:= ((((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - C(5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6457 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3 \times 4) - ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6458 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3^4 - ((C(5) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6459 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (4 + ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6460 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6461 &:= 1 + (2 - C(3) \times (4 - 5 - (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9) \\
6462 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times ((4 - C(5)) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6463 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - C(5))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6464 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C((4 - (5 - 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6425 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 - C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6426 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - C(((6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6427 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + C(6)) \times 5))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6428 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) - 7)) + C(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6429 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (C(6) + (C(5) \times 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6430 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 - 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6431 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (C(7) - (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6432 &:= (((-9 + 8 - C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6433 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6434 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6435 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) \times 6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6436 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + 6))) - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6437 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6438 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6439 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6440 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - C(6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6441 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6442 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6443 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) \times 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6444 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + 6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6445 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6446 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6447 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6448 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4)))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6449 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((C(6) \times 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6450 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) \times ((5 - 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6451 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + (6 + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6452 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6453 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - (C(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6454 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) + (6 - C(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6455 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((C(7) \times 6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6456 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6457 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((C(7) + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3))) - 2 - 1) \\
6458 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times C(5)))) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6459 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6460 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times ((C(5) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6461 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times C(6)) - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6462 &:= (-9 \times (((C(8) \times 7) + 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6463 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6464 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6465 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times 5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
6466 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
6467 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((5 + (6+7)) + C((8+9)))) \\
6468 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (C(4) - ((C(5) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))) \\
6469 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
6470 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
6471 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4+5) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6472 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3+4)) + C(5)) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9))) \\
6473 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6474 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6475 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((C(4) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6476 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - (C(4) + ((C(5) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))))) \\
6477 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6478 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6479 &:= (-1 + (C(((2 \times C(3))/(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6480 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6481 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6482 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3)^4) - C(5)) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)) \\
6483 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4 - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6484 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6485 &:= ((((-1 - 2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
6486 &:= (((-1 - 2 - C(3)) \times ((4-5) - C(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
6487 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 \times ((4^5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
6488 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 - C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6489 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 - C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6490 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - (((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7)) - C((8+9)))) \\
6491 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + 4^5) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
6492 &:= ((C(-1+2+3) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (C(6+7) - C((8+9)))) \\
6493 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times (3+4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6494 &:= (C((-1 + (2+3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
6495 &:= (-1 - ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6496 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6497 &:= -C(-1+2+3) + (4+5) \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
6498 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
6499 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
6500 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
6501 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) - (C(4) - ((C(5) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))) \\
6502 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) - ((C(5) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))) \\
6503 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
6504 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) \times (4 - C(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6465 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7+6) \times C(5))) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
6466 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 + (6 \times (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6467 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + (6 + C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6468 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) - 5))) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6469 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) + 7) \times 6) + C(5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6470 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6471 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times C(6))/5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6472 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - 5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6473 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times C(5)) + (C(4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
6474 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7-6) - C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6475 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
6476 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C(6+5))) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6477 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) \times 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6478 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times C(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6480 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) + C(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6481 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7+6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
6482 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) - (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
6483 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(((7-6) \times (5+4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6484 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (C(5) - (C(4) + 3+2+1))) \\
6485 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6486 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6-5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6487 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7+6+5)) - (C(4) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
6488 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
6489 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6490 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6491 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + ((7+6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6492 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7+6) - C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6493 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7+6) \times (C(5) \times 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6494 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times C(6)) + (C((5 \times 4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
6495 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6496 &:= ((((-9+8) \times (7+6)) + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
6497 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (((C(6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6498 &:= (-9 + ((8+7-6) \times (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6499 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7+6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6500 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7+6) + ((5 \times 4) \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
6501 &:= ((-9 \times (((8-7) \times 6) - C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6502 &:= (((-9+8 + ((7+6) \times C(5))) \times 4) + 3+2+1) \\
6503 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 - (6-5)) \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6504 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7+6) - C(5+4))) + 3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6625 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - C(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6626 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3 + 4 + 5)) - ((6 + 7) - C((8 + 9)))) \\
6627 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((C(4) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6628 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((C(4) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6629 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (C(3) \times 4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6630 &:= (((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6631 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6632 &:= (-1 + ((2^3 + C(4 + 5)) \times (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6633 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6634 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6635 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6636 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6637 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - C(5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6638 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
6639 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6640 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6641 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3) - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6642 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6643 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6644 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6645 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4)) - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6646 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - C(C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6647 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6648 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6649 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6650 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6651 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6652 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6653 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6654 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times C(((4 \times 5) - (C(6) / (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6655 &:= (((-1 + (C(2 \times 3) / 4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6656 &:= (-1 \times (2^3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6657 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) + (4 + (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6658 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (4 - C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6659 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6660 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) + (4 - C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6661 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6662 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((5 + C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6663 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) - ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6664 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((C(4) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6625 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6626 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6627 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6628 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6629 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times (C(5) - 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6630 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6631 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6632 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6633 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((7 - 6) - (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6634 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6635 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6)) \times C(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6636 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6637 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6638 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6639 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (((6 + 5) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6640 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6641 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6642 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6643 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((C(7) - C(6)) \times 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6644 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6645 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6646 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 - 4)^{321})) \\
6647 &:= (-9 - (C(8) \times (7 - ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6648 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 - 4)^{321})) \\
6649 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6650 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6651 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 - 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6652 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6653 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6654 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6655 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6656 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6657 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6658 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + C(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6659 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6660 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6661 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6662 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6663 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6664 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (C(5) + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6665 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times ((4 + C(5)) - 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6666 &:= ((-1 + C((2 \times (3 + 4) + 5))) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6667 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6668 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) \times 4 \times 5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6669 &:= ((-1 - (2^3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6670 &:= (((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6671 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6672 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - C(4 + 5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6673 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + C(4)) - (5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6674 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 + 4) - C(5))) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
6675 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6676 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6677 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6678 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times C(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6679 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times C(5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6680 &:= ((C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6681 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6682 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6683 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6684 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6685 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - C(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6686 &:= (C(-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6687 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - ((C(4) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6688 &:= (-1 \times (((2^3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6689 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times ((4 + C(5)) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6690 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6691 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6692 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6693 &:= (C(((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4)) - (C(5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6694 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6695 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6696 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6697 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + 4) \times C((5 \times 6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6698 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + C(5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6699 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6700 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6701 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C((3 \times (4 - (5 - 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6702 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + (C(6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
6703 &:= (-1 + (2^3 \times (C(4) + ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6704 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6665 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - C(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6666 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6 + 5) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6667 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4 + 3) - 2 - 1)))) \\
6668 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6669 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6670 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6671 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6672 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) \times 5 - 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6673 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((C(7) + C(6 + 5)) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6674 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6675 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (C(7) - (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6676 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6677 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6678 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + C(5)))) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6679 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + (C(6)/(5 + 4))) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6680 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) - (C(6) - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6681 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6682 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6683 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times C(5)))) - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6684 &:= (((C(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) \times 5) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6685 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6686 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6687 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((C(7) + C(6 + 5))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6688 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6689 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6690 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) - 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6691 &:= (-9 - ((8 - C(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6692 &:= ((C(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6693 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (((7 + 6) \times C(5)) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6694 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (C(5) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6695 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + (C(6)/(5 + 4))) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6696 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6697 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6698 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6699 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times (C(5) \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6700 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6701 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6702 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6703 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6704 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times C(6)) + (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6745 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 + C(4))) \times (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6745 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6746 &:= (((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + C(5)) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9))) & 6746 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6747 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 - C(5))) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) & 6747 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6748 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6748 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6749 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6749 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6750 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6750 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6751 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5 - C(6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) & 6751 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6752 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6752 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6753 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 + (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6753 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7 \times 6) \times C(5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6754 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6754 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - ((5 - 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6755 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6755 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5) - C(4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6756 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) & 6756 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6757 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6757 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6758 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6758 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) + (((6 - C(5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6759 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6759 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 + 6) + (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6760 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6760 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6761 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6761 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + (C(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6762 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6762 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6763 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6763 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6764 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) - (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6764 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6765 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6765 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 - 6) \times C(5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6766 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6766 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6767 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6767 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6768 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - C(4 + 5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6768 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6769 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) + (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6769 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6770 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6770 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6771 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times C(5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 6771 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + C(4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6772 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) - ((C(4) - (C(5) + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6772 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (C(6) + (C(5) + C(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6773 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6773 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6774 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6774 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6775 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (C(5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6775 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + C(6))) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6776 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6776 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + ((C(6) + C(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6777 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + C(4 + 5))) \times (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 6777 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) - ((C(5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6778 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6778 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (C(7) + 6)) \times 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6779 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6779 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + C(7)) - C(6))) + (C((5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6780 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3 \times 4) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6780 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + (6 \times ((C(5) + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6781 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6781 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times 6 + C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6782 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (C(4) + (5 + C(6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) & 6782 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6783 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (C(4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6783 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - 5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6784 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6784 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (C(7) - C(6))) \times (5 - (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6825 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((C(3)+C(4)) \times (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6826 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3-(4 \times (C(5)+C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
6827 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3)+C(4+5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
6828 &:= ((-1+C((2 \times (3+4)+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6829 &:= (C((-1+2+C(3))-4-5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6830 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6831 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((C(4)+(5+C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6832 &:= ((-1+2+3+4) \times (C(5)+C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
6833 &:= (-1+2-(C(3)-C((C(4)-((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))))) \\
6834 &:= (C((-1+(2+3) \times 4)) + (5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
6835 &:= (C((-1+(2+(3+(4+5+6)))))) - (7+8+9)) \\
6836 &:= (C((-1+(2+3) \times 4)) - (5-(6-(7+8+9)))) \\
6837 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times ((4-(C(5)-C(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
6838 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((C(4)+(5+C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6839 &:= (-1 + ((2^3+C(4)) \times (C(5)-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6840 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4! \times (C(5)-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6841 &:= (C(((C(4)-4-5)) + (6-(7+8+9)))) \\
6842 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (C(4) \times (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
6843 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (C(4) \times (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
6844 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((C(4)+(5+C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6845 &:= (((((-1-2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6846 &:= (C((-1+(2+3) \times 4)) + (5+6-(7+8+9))) \\
6847 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (C(4) \times (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
6848 &:= (C((-1-(2-(3+4)))) \times (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))) \\
6849 &:= ((-1+C((2 \times (3+4)+5))) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
6850 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times (3+4)+5) - C(6)/(7+8+9) \\
6851 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4+5+6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
6852 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (C(4) \times (C(5)+(6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
6853 &:= ((-1-2-3) + C((C(4)-((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))))) \\
6854 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
6855 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + (C(5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
6856 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times C(4)) - ((5-C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6857 &:= ((-1+2-3) + C((C(4)-((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))))) \\
6858 &:= (-1 + C(((C(2 \times 3)/4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6859 &:= C((-1+2 - ((3+4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6860 &:= (C(-1+2^3) \times (4 \times (5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
6861 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6-(7+8+9)))))) \\
6862 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + C((C(4)-((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))))) \\
6863 &:= (-1 - ((2-(C(3+4+5)/6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6864 &:= ((-1+C(2-3+4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6825 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7+6) \times (5 - C(4)))))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6826 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times ((7+6+5) - 4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6827 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - (6 \times C(5)))) - (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
6828 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times ((C(6) \times 5) + (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6829 &:= (((-9+C(8)) \times (7+6)) + (5 \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
6830 &:= ((-9+8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6831 &:= (-9+8 + (C((7+6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6832 &:= (C(((C(4)-9)/7) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
6833 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5+4)))))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6834 &:= ((-9-8) \times (C(7) - (6 - (C(5) - (4 \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6835 &:= (C(((C(4)-9)/5) - (4 \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6836 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6+5) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6837 &:= (-9 + ((8+7+6) \times ((5 \times C(4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
6838 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) + C(6)) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
6839 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) + (C(6) + C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6840 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7 - (C(6) - C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6841 &:= (-9-8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6842 &:= (-9-8 + C((C(7) - (6 \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
6843 &:= (-9-8 + (C(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6844 &:= (((-9-8 + (C(7) + C(6+5))) \times 4) + C(3+2+1)) \\
6845 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5+4)))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6846 &:= ((-9-8+C(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6847 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6-5) \times 4) \times C(3+2+1)))))) \\
6848 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + C((5 \times 4))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
6849 &:= (C(((C(4)-9)/5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6850 &:= (-9 + C((8 + (((7-6)^5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
6851 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6+5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6852 &:= ((-9+8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5+4))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
6853 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6854 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7+6))) - (5+4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
6855 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7+6+5) \times C(4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
6856 &:= (-9 + (C(((8+7) + ((6-5) \times 4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6857 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6858 &:= (9 \times ((8+7-6) + C(5+4))) + C(3+2+1) \\
6859 &:= C(((C(4)-9)/5) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6860 &:= ((((-9+C(8+7))/6) + C(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6861 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - C(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
6862 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7+6))) - ((5-4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
6863 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 \times (6+5) - C(4))) + C(3+2+1))) \\
6864 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7)) \times (6+5 - (4 \times (3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6905 &:= (((((-1-2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6905 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + ((C(5) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6906 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6906 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6907 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6907 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times ((C(6) + 5) \times 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6908 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3 + 4)) \times 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6908 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + C(6 + 5))) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6909 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6909 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6910 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6910 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6911 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 + 4 + 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6911 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6912 &:= (C(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6912 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (C(7) + (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6913 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6913 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + C(7))/6) \times C(5)) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6914 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6914 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) + C(7))) + (6^5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6915 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6915 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6916 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6916 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (6 - C(5)))) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6917 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 + 3) + 4^5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6917 &:= (C(((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))/5) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6918 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6918 &:= ((C(((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + C(5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6919 &:= ((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6919 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + 6 + 5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6920 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (5 - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6920 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - C(6)))) + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6921 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6921 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6922 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6922 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6923 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3) + C((C(4) - ((5 \times C(6))/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6923 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6924 &:= ((-1 - 2 - C(3 \times 4)) \times (5 - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6924 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6 + 5)))) - (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6925 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6925 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((C(5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6926 &:= ((((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6926 &:= (((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6927 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6927 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5) \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6928 &:= (((-1 + 2^3) \times (4^5)) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6928 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - C(6))) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6929 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((C(3) \times 4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6929 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6930 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + C(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6930 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6931 &:= (-1 - ((C((2^3 + 4)) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 6931 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6932 &:= (-1 \times ((C((2^3 + 4)) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 6932 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6933 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6933 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) - C(6)) \times C(5)) + (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6934 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((C(3) - (C(4) - 5)) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6934 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6) - 5))) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6935 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6935 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6936 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5)/6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6936 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6937 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3 + 4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6937 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6938 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3 + 4) \times 5) - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6938 &:= (((C((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6)) + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6939 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6939 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6940 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6940 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7 + 6) + 5))) \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6941 &:= (C((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6941 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6942 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6942 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6 + 5) + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6943 &:= ((-1 + C((2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((5 \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6943 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6944 &:= ((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6944 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times 7)) - (6 - C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6945 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (C(4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) + 8 + 9))) & 6945 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6946 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - (C(4) + (C(5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) & 6946 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + C(6) - 5))) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6947 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6947 &:= ((((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times 6) - C(5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
6948 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) - C(4 + 5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6948 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 + 5 - C(4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6949 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) - (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6949 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6950 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (C(4) + C(5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6950 &:= ((-9 - (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6951 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (C(4) + C(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6951 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6952 &:= (C(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + ((C(5) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6952 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6953 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6953 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 + C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6954 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) + (C(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6954 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + C(5))) + C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6955 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6955 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((C(7) - 6) \times 5 \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6956 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 6956 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (6 + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6957 &:= (((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 6957 &:= (-9 + (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6958 &:= ((-1 + 2^3) \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6958 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 - (C((4 + 3)) - C((2 + 1)))))) \\
6959 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3 + 4 + 5)/6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6959 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6960 &:= ((-1 - 2 + C(3)) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6960 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - C(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6961 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times C(3))) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6961 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6962 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 + (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9)))) & 6962 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) - C(5)))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6963 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6963 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times (C(5) + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6964 &:= (-1 + (C(2 + 3) + ((C(4) + (5 + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6964 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + (C(5) + (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6965 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6965 &:= (-9 + C(8) - ((7 - ((C(6) \times 5) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6966 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6966 &:= (C(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6967 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((4 + C(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6967 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times C(4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6968 &:= ((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (4 \times (C(5) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6968 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((C(7) - C(6)) \times (C(5) - (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6969 &:= (-1 - (((2^3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6969 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6970 &:= (-1 \times (((2^3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6970 &:= (((-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + 6) \times 5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6971 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) - (5 - (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6971 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((C(7) + (6 + C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6972 &:= ((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6972 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6973 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3 + 4) + ((C(5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6973 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6974 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) - (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6974 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + C((5 \times 4))) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6975 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - 4))) \times (C(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6975 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - ((7 \times C(6)) - ((5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6976 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (C(4) + ((5 \times C(6))/(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6976 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6977 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6977 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times ((5 \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6978 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) & 6978 &:= (((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6979 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) & 6979 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) - (6 - C(5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6980 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (C(3) - (C(4 + 5) - (6 + 7)))) + C((8 + 9))) & 6980 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - 7)) \times (6 - 5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6981 &:= (((-1 + 2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (5 + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6981 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6982 &:= (-1 \times (((2^3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6982 &:= (((-9 + 8 + ((C(7) + 6) \times 5)) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6983 &:= (-1 + ((C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 6983 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6984 &:= ((C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) - (5 + C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 6984 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + C((7 - (6 - 5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7024 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((4!+5) \times (C(6)+7+8+9))) \\
7025 &:= ((-1 - (C(2 \times 3) + C(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7026 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7))) - (8+9)))) \\
7027 &:= (-1+2 - (3 \times (4 - ((C(5) + (6+7)) \times (8+9)))) \\
7028 &:= ((-1+2+C(3)) \times (C(4) - (5 - (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7029 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7030 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7031 &:= (((((-1-2) \times C(3)) + 4) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
7032 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3 \times 4) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7033 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3 \times 4) + ((5+C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7034 &:= (-1-2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7035 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3 \times 4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7036 &:= (-1 + (C((2^3+4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7037 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3 \times 4) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7038 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + C(4+5))) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7039 &:= ((-1 + C((2+3) \times 4)) - (5 \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7040 &:= (C((-1-2+C(3)) - 4) - (5 \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7041 &:= (((-1 \times 2 - C(3+4))/5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7042 &:= (-1-2 + (C(3!) + (C((4! - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7043 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) - (C(5) - (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7044 &:= (-1 - (((2+3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
7045 &:= ((((-1 \times (2+3)) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) + 7+8+9) \\
7046 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4+5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7047 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (C(4) + ((5+C(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7048 &:= (-1+2 + (C(3) \times (C(4) + ((5+C(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7049 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((C(3) \times 4) + C(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7050 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3+4) - C(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7051 &:= (C((-1+2+C(3)) - 4 - 5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7052 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7053 &:= (((-1 - C(2^3))/(4+5)) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7054 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7055 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + (4 \times 5))) \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7056 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) - 4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7+8+9) \\
7057 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7058 &:= ((((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7059 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (C(4+5) - (6+7))) + C((8+9)))) \\
7060 &:= (((-1 - (2+3+4)) \times 5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7061 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - ((C(4) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7062 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times (C(4+5) - (6+7))) + C((8+9)))) \\
7063 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7024 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7025 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) \times ((6+5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7026 &:= (-9 - ((8 - C(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7027 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7028 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7029 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (C(6) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7030 &:= (((((-9+C(8)) \times 7) - 6)/5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7031 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4 + C(3+2+1)))) \\
7032 &:= (((-9 - 8 - 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times 4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7033 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) + ((C(5) \times 4) - (3+2+1))) \\
7034 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times ((6+5) \times 4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
7035 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times 6)) \times (5 - (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7036 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7+6+5) - 4)) - (3+2+1)) \\
7037 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times (C(6) \times 5)) + (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7038 &:= (-9 \times (C((8-7+6)) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7039 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (C(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7040 &:= (-9+8+7 - (C(6) - (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7041 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7042 &:= ((-9 + C(8)) \times ((7 \times 6)/(5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7043 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7+6)) + ((C(5) + (4+3)) \times (2+1)))) \\
7044 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5-4))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7045 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) + ((C(5) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
7046 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times ((6+5) \times 4)) + 3+2+1) \\
7047 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7048 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (C(6) - C(5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7049 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7050 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + C(7)))/6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7051 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - (C(6) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7052 &:= (((-9+8+C(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1))) \\
7053 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (((7+6) \times C(5)) + C(4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7054 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - (C((5 \times 4)) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
7055 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6) - C(5+4)))) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7056 &:= (-9 \times (C((((8-7)^6) + 5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7057 &:= (-9+8 + ((C(7) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7058 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + C((5 \times 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7059 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7+6) \times (C(5) - C(4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7060 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7061 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (C(7) - 6)) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7062 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7 - (C(6) - 5)) \times 4)) + 3+2+1) \\
7063 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (C(6) \times 5)) - C(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7064 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) \times (4+5))) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7064 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7+6 - C(5))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7065 &:= ((-1 \times ((2+3) \times (4+5))) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7065 &:= (-9 \times (((8+7) \times 6) + C(5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7066 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3)^4) - (C(5) - (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7066 &:= (-9 + (C(((8+7) + ((6-5) \times 4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7067 &:= (((((-1-2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7+8+9))) & 7067 &:= ((((-9+8+C(7))/6) \times C(5)) - (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
7068 &:= (((-1+2 + (C(3) \times 4)) \times (5 \times (6+7))) - (8+9)) & 7068 &:= (-9 + ((8+7+6) \times (C(5) - (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
7069 &:= ((-1+2 + C(3)) - (C(4) + (5 - (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))))) & 7069 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - (C(4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
7070 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7070 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7071 &:= (((-1-2) \times (C(3) \times ((4+C(5)) - C(6)))) + 7+8+9) & 7071 &:= (C(((9+8 \times (7+6))/5)) - (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
7072 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4+5) \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 7072 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (C(6) - (5+4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
7073 &:= (-1-2 - ((3-C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 7073 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 \times (C(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7074 &:= (-1 + (C(2 \times 3) + C((C(4) - ((5 \times C(6))/(7+8+9)))))) & 7074 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) + (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7075 &:= (C((-1 + (2+3) \times 4) + C((5 \times 6 - (7+8+9)))) & 7075 &:= (C(((9+8+7 \times (6+5))/4)) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7076 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 7076 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times ((6+5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7077 &:= (-1+2 - ((3-C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 7077 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times (6+5)) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
7078 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - C(4+5))) - ((6+7) - C((8+9)))) & 7078 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
7079 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7079 &:= (C(((9+8 \times (7+6))/5)) + (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
7080 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (((3+4) - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7080 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times ((C(6) \times 5) + C(4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7081 &:= (C(((9-2 + C(3)) - 4) - (C((5 + (6+7))) - C((8+9)))) & 7081 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7+6) \times ((C(5) \times 4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
7082 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times C(4)) - (C(5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 7082 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7083 &:= (-1 \times (C(((2^{3+4}) - C(5))) - (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7083 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - C(5+4))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7084 &:= ((-1+2 - (3 \times (4+5))) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7085 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4+5))) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7085 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times (6 - (C(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7086 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4+5))) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) & 7086 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7087 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times C(4+5)) - ((6+7) - C((8+9)))) & 7087 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((C(7) + C(6)) + (5^4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7088 &:= (((-1-2 \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5 \times C(6)))) - (7+8+9)) & 7088 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) - (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
7089 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) - 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9)))) & 7089 &:= ((-9-8) \times (C(7) - ((6 \times C(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7090 &:= (-1 + (((C(2+3) - 4) \times (5 + (6+7))) + C((8+9)))) & 7090 &:= ((-9 + (((C(8) \times 7) + 6)/5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7091 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times C(4) + 5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 7091 &:= (((-9-8 + (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) - (C(4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7092 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times C(4) + 5) \times (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 7092 &:= (-9+8 + (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7093 &:= (-1+2 - (C(3) - ((4+5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))))) & 7093 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times C(6)) - (5^4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
7094 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (C(4) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9)))) & 7094 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7+6) \times (5+4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7095 &:= (((-1-2 \times 3 + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 7095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7+6 - (C(5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7096 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 7096 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) + (4 - C(3+2+1))) \\
7097 &:= (-1 + (((C(2 \times 3)/4) \times (C(5) + 6)) + 7+8+9)) & 7097 &:= (-9 + (((8 + C(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7098 &:= (-1 + (C((2 \times (3+4) + 5)) + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) & 7098 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7099 &:= (C(((9+2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5)) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 7099 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) \times 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7100 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4 \times 5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)) & 7100 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) - 6 - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
7101 &:= (((-1+2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 7101 &:= (-9 \times (C(((8-7) \times 6)) - (5 + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7102 &:= ((-1 + (C(2 \times 3)/4)) \times (C(5) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) & 7102 &:= (((-9-8 + C(7)) + (6^5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7103 &:= (-1 + ((C((2 - (3-4-5))) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 7103 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times C(7))) - (6 - (C(5+4) \times (3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7144 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7145 &:= (-1 - (C(2 + 3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7146 &:= (-1 \times (C(2 + 3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7147 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((4 + 5) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
7148 &:= (-1 - (((2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5 + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7149 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7150 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7151 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times C(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7152 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (C(3) + 4 + 5)) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7153 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7154 &:= ((-1 + (2^3 \times C(4))) \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7155 &:= (((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7156 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) \times (4 - (C(5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7157 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) \times (4 + C(5)))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7158 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) + ((4 \times 5) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))))) \\
7159 &:= (-1 + (((2 + C(3)) \times C(4)) + ((5 + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7160 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4)) - (5 - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
7161 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3 \times 4) - (C(5) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7162 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times C(4)) - ((C(5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7163 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + C((8 + 9))) \\
7164 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (C(5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7165 &:= (C((-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4)) + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
7166 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7167 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7168 &:= (C((-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)) \times (5 + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7169 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7170 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7171 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times 4 \times 5)) + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
7172 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7173 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7174 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7175 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7176 &:= ((C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7177 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7178 &:= (((-1 + 2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7179 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 + (C(5) + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7180 &:= (C((-1 + 2^3 + 4)) + (C((5 + (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
7181 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7182 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7183 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7144 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) \times (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7145 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + (6 \times (C(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7146 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (C(7) - ((C(6 + 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7147 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5) \times ((4 + 3) - 2 - 1)))) \\
7148 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + (7 + C(6 + 5)))) \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7149 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 - C(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7150 &:= (((-9 + C(8 + 7 - 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7151 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 - (C(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7152 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + C(6 + 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7153 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7154 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7155 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 \times (C(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7156 &:= (-9 + 8 - (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7157 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7158 &:= ((((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5^4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7159 &:= (-9 - (C(8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7160 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7161 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 - C(4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7162 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) \times C(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7163 &:= (-9 - ((C(8 + 7) + (C(6) - 5)) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7164 &:= (-9 \times ((C(8) \times 7) - (6 + (C(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7165 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7166 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) \times 7) + (C(6) + C(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7167 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (C(7) - (C(6 + 5) - C(4)))) + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7168 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) \times C(((4 + 3) - 2 - 1))) \\
7169 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7170 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7171 &:= (-9 + (((C(8) \times 7) + 6)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7172 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (C(5 + 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7173 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7174 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7175 &:= ((-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + C(6 + 5))) \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7176 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (C(7) + 6)) \times 5 \times 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7177 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7178 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7179 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (C(7) + C((6 + 5 - 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7180 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (5 \times C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7181 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + C(5)))) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7182 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7183 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7184 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7185 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + C(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
7186 &:= (-1 + (C((2 \times (3^{\sqrt{4}}))) + (C(5+6) + 7+8+9))) \\
7187 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) + (C((5+(6+7))) - (8+9))) \\
7188 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7))) + 8+9)) \\
7189 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((C(4) \times (C(5) - (6+7))) + 8+9)) \\
7190 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) + (C((4 \times 5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7191 &:= (C(-1+2^3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) + (6 - (7+8+9))))) \\
7192 &:= ((-1 + C(2+3)) \times (4 + ((5 \times 6) + 7+8+9))) \\
7193 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^4) + (5 + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7194 &:= (C(-1+2+3) + ((4 \times 5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7195 &:= ((-1-2+C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7196 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3^4) + (5 + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7197 &:= (-1+2 + ((3^4) + (5 + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7198 &:= (((-1+2^3) \times 4^5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7199 &:= (-1 + (((2+C(3)) - (4-5)) \times (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
7200 &:= ((-1-2 + (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7201 &:= (((-1-2+C(3)) \times 4) - (5 - (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7202 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times C(4)) - (5 + C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7203 &:= ((-1-2) \times (C(3+4) - C((5+(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7204 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3^4)) \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7205 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3 \times 4)) + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7206 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7207 &:= (-1 - (C(2 \times 3) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7208 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3^4) \times 5) + C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7209 &:= (((-1+2+C(3)) \times (C(4) + (5+(6+7)))) + C((8+9))) \\
7210 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times C(4)) - ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7211 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (C(4) \times (5+(6+7)))) + C((8+9))) \\
7212 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times C(4)) + (5 - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7213 &:= ((C((-1+2) \times 3) \times 4) - (5 - (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7214 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (C(5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9))))) \\
7215 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7216 &:= (((-1+C(2+3)) \times C(4)) - (5 \times (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7217 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) + (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7218 &:= (((-1-2) \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7+8+9)) \\
7219 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7220 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9) \\
7221 &:= ((C(-1+2^3) \times 4) + (C((5+(6+7))) + 8+9)) \\
7222 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + (C(4) \times (5+(6+7)))) + C((8+9)))) \\
7184 &:= (((-9 + ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6+5))) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7185 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 \times 6 - C(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7186 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7187 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) - ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7188 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) + (6-5))) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7189 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (C((6 - (5-4))) - C(3+2+1))) \\
7190 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + C((7 - (6-5))))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7191 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times C(6)) - C(5+4)))) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7192 &:= (((-9/(8+7-6)) + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
7193 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7194 &:= (-9 + ((8+7+6) \times C((5 - (4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
7195 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((C(7) + 6) \times 5 \times 4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7196 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7+6) + (5 \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7197 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7 - ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4)))) + 3+2+1) \\
7198 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7+6) + C(5)))) \times 4) - (3+2+1)) \\
7199 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6) \times 5)))) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7200 &:= ((-9 + C((8 + ((7-6)^5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7201 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - (7 - C(6))) \times (5 \times (4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
7202 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7203 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) \times (6 - C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
7204 &:= ((-9 - 8 - C(7)) + ((6^5) + (4 - C(3+2+1)))) \\
7205 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((C(7) + C(6+5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1))) \\
7206 &:= (-9 + 8 + (C(7) + (((C(6) \times 5) + C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7207 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 + C(6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7208 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) \times 7) + 6+5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7209 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7210 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) - C(6)) \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7211 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7212 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times 7 + C(6+5)) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7213 &:= (((-9+8) \times C(7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + C(3+2+1)) \\
7214 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6+5)))) - (4 + C(3+2+1))) \\
7215 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (C(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7216 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + ((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
7217 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) \times 6) - C(5)) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
7218 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7219 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (((7+6) \times (C(5) \times 4)) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7220 &:= ((-9 - (8+7+6)) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7221 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7222 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6+5)))) + (4 - C(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7223 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7224 &:= ((C((-1+2+3+4)) + (5 - C(6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7225 &:= ((-1 + C((2+3) \times 4)) - ((C(5) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
7226 &:= (((-1+2 - C(3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) + 7+8+9) \\
7227 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
7228 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
7229 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7230 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7231 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6 \times (7+8+9)) \\
7232 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)) \\
7233 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7234 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7235 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7236 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7237 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7238 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) + (C(5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7239 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4 \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
7240 &:= ((-1 - (2+3+4)) \times (5 - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7241 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
7242 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7243 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))))) \\
7244 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7245 &:= (-1 + 2 - (C(3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7246 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times 4) \times (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7247 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7248 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times C(3+4)) + C(5+6)) \times (7+8+9) \\
7249 &:= (-1 - ((2 - C(3)) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7250 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + C(3)) \times ((C(4) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7251 &:= (((-1 + 2+3) \times 4) + (C(5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7252 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C((C(3) - 4 - 5)) - C(6+7)))) - (8+9)) \\
7253 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7254 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7255 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (C(4+5) - (C(6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
7256 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (C(5) - (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7257 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((C(3) + C(4)) \times (5+6))) + (C(7) + C((8+9)))) \\
7258 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7259 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
7260 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7261 &:= (C((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - ((5 - C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7262 &:= (-1 + (C(2 - 3 + 4) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7223 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (C(7) + (C(6) + (C(5) + (4 + C(3+2+1))))))) \\
7224 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6+5+4)) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7225 &:= (-9 - (((C(8) - (C(7+6) + C(5))) \times 4) + 3+2+1)) \\
7226 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6)) + C((5 \times 4))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7227 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - C(6))) + (5 + (4 \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
7228 &:= ((-9 - ((C(8) - (7 - C(6))) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7229 &:= (C(((9 - 8 \times (7+6))/5)) + (C((4+3)) + C((2+1)))) \\
7230 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (C(5) + (4 \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
7231 &:= (-9 + ((C(8+7-6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7232 &:= ((-9 - (8+7-6)) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7233 &:= (-9 - 8 + (C(((7-6) \times 5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7234 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1)) \\
7235 &:= ((-9 - ((8-7) \times 6)) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7236 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - C(5+4))) + 3+2+1) \\
7237 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7238 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7239 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - C(7))) + ((6+5) \times (C(4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7240 &:= ((-9 \times C(8) - (C(7) - C(6+5))) \times (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7241 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times C(5)) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
7242 &:= (-9 - 8 - (C(7) - ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7243 &:= (C(((9 - 8 \times (7+6))/5)) + (C(4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7244 &:= ((-9 + 8 + C(7)) - ((6 - C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7245 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + ((C(7) \times 6) - C(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7246 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times C(5)))) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7247 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + C(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7248 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + C(6+5)) - 4) \times (3+2+1) \\
7249 &:= ((-9/(8+7-6)) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7250 &:= ((-9 + (C(8+7-6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7251 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - (7 - (C(6) + 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7252 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - 7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7253 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + C(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3))) - C((2+1))) \\
7254 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (C(6+5) + 4)))) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7255 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - C(7))) + ((6^5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
7256 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - C(7)) \times ((6+5) \times 4)) + C(3+2+1)) \\
7257 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (C(6+5) - C(4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7258 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7259 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (C(7) - ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7260 &:= ((-9 - 8 - 7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7261 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6+5) \times (C((4+3)) - 2 - 1))) \\
7262 &:= (9 \times (C(8) + C(7))) - (C(6) + (5 - 4 + C(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7263 &:= (C((-1-2) \times (3-4)) \times (C(5) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
7264 &:= ((-1-2 \times 3 + C((4 \times 5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7265 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7266 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + C((4 \times 5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7267 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
7268 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)) \\
7269 &:= (((-1+2-3) + C((4 \times 5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7270 &:= ((-1 + C(((2 + C(3)) - 4 - 5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7271 &:= (C((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
7272 &:= 1 + C(2 + C(3) - 4 - 5) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
7273 &:= ((-1 + C((2+3) \times 4)) - ((C(5) \times 6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7274 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + C((4 \times 5))) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)) \\
7275 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7276 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - (5 \times C(C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7277 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (4 - C(5+6))))) - (C(7) - C((8+9)))) \\
7278 &:= (-1 + (2^3 + (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7279 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - C(4)) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7280 &:= (((-1-2-3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6+7+8+9 \\
7281 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
7282 &:= (-1 + (((C(2+3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
7283 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7284 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7285 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (C(3) + 4^5)) + (C(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7286 &:= (((-1 + C(2+3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7287 &:= (-1 - 2 + (C(3) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7288 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (C(3) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7289 &:= 1 - 2 + C(3) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
7290 &:= (C((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7291 &:= (-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7292 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7293 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7294 &:= ((-1 - C(2+3+4)) + (C((5!/6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
7295 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (C(3) + 4+5)) \times (C(6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7296 &:= ((-1 + (C(2^3) + (4+5 - C(6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7297 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7298 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times C(3+4)) + C(5)) \times (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7299 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7300 &:= (((-1-2 + C(3)) - 4) \times (C(5) + (C(6) + 7+8+9))) \\
7301 &:= (((-1+2 \times C(3)) - 4) \times (5+6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
7302 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (C(4) + (C(5) + (C(6+7) + C((8+9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7263 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7 + (6-5)) - (4 \times C(3+2+1)))) \\
7264 &:= (((-9 - (C(8) - 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7265 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) + ((C(5) - 4) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7266 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (C(6) - (5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7267 &:= ((-9+8) \times (C(7) + (((6 - C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
7268 &:= (-9 - (C(8+7-6) - (C((5 \times 4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
7269 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + C(5)))) - (C(4) - (3+2+1))) \\
7270 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (C(7) + (6 - C(5))))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7271 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + C((7 - (6 - 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7272 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7273 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (C(4) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7274 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) + (C(5+4) + 3+2+1)) \\
7275 &:= (((-9+8+(7 \times C(6))) \times 5) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7276 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7+6) + C((5 \times 4))) - C(3+2+1))) \\
7277 &:= (((-9+8+C(7))/6) \times C(5)) - (C(4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7278 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6+5) - 4)))) + 3+2+1) \\
7279 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (C(6) + C(5+4)))) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7280 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + (C((5 \times 4)) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7281 &:= (-9 + (C((8 + ((7-6)^5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7282 &:= 9 \times C(8) + (C(7) + (C(6+5) + C(4+3+2+1))) \\
7283 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7 \times ((C(6) \times 5) + 4)) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7284 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) - (4 \times (3+2+1))) \\
7285 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6+5) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
7286 &:= (((-9 + (C(8) + 7)) + (6^5)) - C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7287 &:= (-9 - ((C(8) - C((7+6 - (5-4)))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7288 &:= (((-9 - (((8 - C(7)) \times 6) + C(5))) \times 4) - C(3+2+1)) \\
7289 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + C(5))) - 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7290 &:= (C(((9 \times (8-7-6))/5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7291 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + C(6) - 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7292 &:= (((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) + (6-5)) \times (4 - (3+2+1)) \\
7293 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7294 &:= ((-9 - C(8)) \times (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7295 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (C(7) - (6 + (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
7296 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + (C(6) + C(5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7297 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times 7) + ((6+5) \times C((4+3))) + 2+1) \\
7298 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7299 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (7 \times (C(6) - C((5+4 - (3+2+1))))) \\
7300 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - (7 - C(6)))) \times (5 \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7301 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5-4) - C(3+2+1))) \\
7302 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (C(6+5) + C(4)))) \times (3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7303 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + (5 \times C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7304 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3^4)) \times (C(5) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7305 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7306 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3)) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7307 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7308 &:= (((C(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7309 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) - (C(4) + (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
7310 &:= ((((-1 + 2^3) \times C(4)) - (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7311 &:= (-1 - (((2^3 - C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7312 &:= ((((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times C(4)) + 5!) - (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7313 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - ((4 - C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7314 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times C(3)) \times (4 + (C(5) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7315 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3 \times C(4))) \times (C(5) - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7316 &:= (((-1 - C(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7317 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7318 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7319 &:= (-1 + ((C(2^3) + (4 + 5 - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7320 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (C(3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7321 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((C(3) + (C(4) - C(5))) \times C(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7322 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (C(4 + 5) - C(6 + 7))) + 8 + 9)) \\
7323 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7324 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7325 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) + (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7326 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 \times C(4) + C(5) \times (-6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7327 &:= (-1 + (C(2^3) + ((4 \times C(5) - C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7328 &:= (C((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) - (C(5) - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9)))) \\
7329 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((C(3) + 4) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7330 &:= (-1 - 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7331 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (C(3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7332 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7333 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4^5)) + (C(6 + 7) + 8 + 9))) \\
7334 &:= (((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7335 &:= (C(-1 + 2 + 3) + (C((4 \times 5)) - C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7336 &:= (-1 - ((2 + C(3)) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7337 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3^4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7338 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7339 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3 \times 4) \times (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7340 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - 3 \times 4)) \times (5 + C(C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7341 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (((C(3) + 4) \times C(5)) - C(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7342 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 + (6 + 7)))) - C((8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7303 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times C(5)))) + (C(4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7304 &:= (((-9 + C(8) - (C(7) - C(6))) \times 5 \times 4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7305 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) + C(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7306 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6 + 5)))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7307 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 - 6) + C(5)) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7308 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7309 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (C(7 + 6) + (C((5 + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
7310 &:= ((-9 + (C(8) + (7 + (C(6) + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7311 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + 5) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7312 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 \times (6 - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7313 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + ((C(5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7314 &:= ((-9 + C(8) - (7 + 6 - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7315 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 - C(6)))) \times 5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7316 &:= ((((-9 - C(8)) \times 7) - 6 - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7317 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + C(7)) \times C(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7318 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7319 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (C(6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7320 &:= (((-9 \times C(8)) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7321 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7322 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (C(7) + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7323 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - ((6 \times C(5)) + C(4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7324 &:= ((((-9 - 8 + C(7)) \times 6) - C(5)) \times ((4 + 3) - 2 - 1)) \\
7325 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times C(7)) + ((6 \times C(5 + 4)) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7326 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (C(6) + (5 + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6 - (C(5) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7328 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (((6 - C(5)) \times C(4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7329 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times C(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7330 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - (4 \times C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7331 &:= (-9 + ((C(8 + 7 - 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7332 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6 + 5)))) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7333 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (C(7) - (6 \times (C(5) + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7334 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + ((7 \times (C(6) + C(5 + 4))) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7335 &:= (-9 + (C(8) + (C((7 + 6 + 5)) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7336 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7337 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + C(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7338 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - (C(6 + 5) + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7339 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5))) - (4 + C(3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7340 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6 + 5) - (C(4) + C(3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7341 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7 - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7342 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (C(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

7423 := $(-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))$
7424 := $(C((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))$
7425 := $(-1 + (2 \times (C(3) - (C(4) - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
7426 := $((((-1 - 2 + C(3)) - 4) \times C(5)) + ((6 + 7) + C((8 + 9))))$
7427 := $(((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))$
7428 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))$
7429 := $((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))$
7430 := $(-1 - 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7431 := $(-1 \times 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7432 := $(-1 - ((C(2 + 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7433 := $(-1 \times ((C(2 + 3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7434 := $(-1 + 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7435 := $((((-1 + (2 + 3) \times C(4)) - C(5)) \times (6 + 7)) + C((8 + 9)))$
7436 := $(((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))))$
7437 := $(-1 - (2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
7438 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + (4 - (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7439 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((3 - 4 + C(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7440 := $(((-1 - 2 + C(3 + 4)) - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
7441 := $(-1 + 2 - ((C(3) + (4 - (C(5) + C(6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
7442 := $((((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$
7443 := $(((-1 - 2 \times 3 + C(4)) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
7444 := $(C(-1 + 2^3) - (4 + 5 - (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9))))$
7445 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((C(3) \times (4 + C(5))) + (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7446 := $(((-1 - C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (C(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
7447 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 - C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
7448 := $(-1 - 2 + (C(3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))))$
7449 := $((C((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) - (5 - C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$
7450 := $(-1 + 2 + ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (5 - C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
7451 := $(C((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7 + 8 + 9))))$
7452 := $((-1 - 2 - 3) \times ((C(4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7453 := $(-1 - (2 \times (C(3) - (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
7454 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) - (4 + (C(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7455 := $(-1 \times (C(2 + 3 + 4) - ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
7456 := $(-1 + 2 - ((C(3) \times (C(4) - (C(5) + C(6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
7457 := $(-1 - (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7458 := $(-1 \times (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
7459 := $(-1 + 2 + (C(3 + 4) + (5 + (C(6 + 7) + C((8 + 9))))))$
7460 := $(((-1 + C(2 + 3)) \times (C(4) - 5)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
7461 := $(-1 - 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
7462 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times C(5) - C(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$

7423 := $((((-9 + 8) \times C(7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7424 := $((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7425 := $(-9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 6)) + C(5)) - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
7426 := $(-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
7427 := $(-9 - ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
7428 := $(9 + (C(8 + 7 - 6) + (C(5) \times 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$
7429 := $(-9 + 8 - ((7 - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
7430 := $((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7431 := $(-9 + ((C(8) - ((7 - 6) - C(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7432 := $((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) + (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7433 := $(-9 + (((C(8) - C(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7434 := $(-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))$
7435 := $(-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
7436 := $((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7437 := $(-9 + ((C(8) + C(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7438 := $((((-9 \times 8 + (C(7) \times 6)) - C(5)) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
7439 := $(-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + C(5)) - (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7440 := $((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - C(6)) - (5^4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)$
7441 := $(-9 + ((8 - (C(7) - (C(6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
7442 := $((-9 + 8 - C(7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7443 := $(((-9 + 8) \times C(7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
7444 := $((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + C(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
7445 := $(((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6^5) + (4 - C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
7446 := $(((-9 + C(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)$
7447 := $(-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (C(5 + 4) + C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
7448 := $(-9 - (C(8) - (7 + ((C(6 + 5) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7449 := $(((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (C(6) - (C((5 \times 4)) - C(3 + 2 + 1))))$
7450 := $((-9 - (C(8 + 7) + (C(6) + C(5)))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7451 := $(((-9 + C(8 + 7)) - 6 - 5) + (4^{3+2+1}))$
7452 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((C(6) - (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$
7453 := $(-9 - (C(8) - (((C(7) \times 6) - C(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7454 := $((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$
7455 := $(-9 + (8 \times ((C(7) \times 6) - (C(5) + C(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
7456 := $((-9 + 8 - C(7)) + ((6^5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7457 := $(((-9 + 8) \times C(7)) + ((6^5) + (4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7458 := $(((-9 - 8 - 7 + C(6 + 5)) - C(4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$
7459 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (C(6) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7460 := $((-9 \times (C(8) + (7 - C(6 + 5)))) - (C(4) - C(3 + 2 + 1)))$
7461 := $(-9 \times (8 + ((C(7) + C(6 + 5))/(4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$
7462 := $(-9 + (C(8 + 7) + C((6 - (5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)))))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
7463 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (C(3+4) - (5 \times 6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7464 &:= (((-1 + (C(2^3) + C(4+5))) \times 6) + 7+8+9) \\
7465 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (4 \times C(5) - C(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7466 &:= (-1 - (C(2+3) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7467 &:= (-1 \times (C(2+3) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7468 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) \times (5 + (6+7))) - C((8+9)))) \\
7469 &:= (-1 + (((C(2^3) + C(4+5)) \times 6) + 7+8+9)) \\
7470 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7471 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + (C(4) + (5 \times C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7472 &:= ((-1 + (((2-3) + C(4)) \times (C(5) - 6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
7473 &:= (((-1 - ((2-3) \times C(4))) \times (C(5) - 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
7474 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) - C(4)) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7475 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7476 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times 4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7477 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times C(3)) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))))) \\
7478 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 - C(4)) \times C(5)) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
7479 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((C(4) \times 5) - C(6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7480 &:= (-1 - ((C(2+3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
7481 &:= (-1 \times ((C(2+3) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + 6 \times (7+8+9))) \\
7482 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) - 4) \times C(5)) + (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
7483 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) + ((6+7) - (8+9)))) \\
7484 &:= ((-1 + C(2+3)) - (C(4) \times (C(5) - (C(6) + 7+8+9)))) \\
7485 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7486 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7487 &:= (-1 - ((C(2^3) + C(4)) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
7488 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (C(4) \times (5+6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
7489 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((C(3) + (C(4) + (5 + C(6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7490 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + C(4)) \times C(5)) + (C(6) + 7+8+9) \\
7491 &:= (((C(-1+2+3) - 4) \times C(5)) - (C(6)/(7+8+9))) \\
7492 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7493 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (C(3) + ((C(4) - (C(5) - C(6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7494 &:= (((-1 - C(2+3)) \times (C(4) - C(5))) - (C(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
7495 &:= (C(-1+2 \times 3) + (((C(4) + C(5)) \times (6+7)) + C((8+9)))) \\
7496 &:= (-1 - (C(2^3) - (C((4 \times 5)) + (C(6)/(7+8+9)))) \\
7497 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7498 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times C(3+4)) + ((C(5) + C(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7499 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3-4)) \times (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7500 &:= ((C((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + C(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7501 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7502 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - (C(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7463 &:= ((-9 + (C(8+7) + (6-5))) + (4^{3+2+1})) \\
7464 &:= ((-9 \times (C(8) - (7 + (C(6+5) + 4)))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7465 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7466 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - 4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
7467 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7468 &:= ((-9 - (C(8) + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + C(3+2+1)))) \\
7469 &:= (((-9 - 8 \times 7) \times (6 - (C(5) - 4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7470 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (C(7) - (6 - 5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7471 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7+6) \times 5) - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7472 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - C(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
7473 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7474 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (C(7) \times ((6+5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7475 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (((6 - C(5)) \times C(4)) + 3+2+1)) \\
7476 &:= (-9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7477 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) - (4 - (3+2+1))) \\
7478 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7479 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((7+6-5) \times C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7480 &:= ((C(-9+8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) + C(4+3+2+1)) \\
7481 &:= (-9 - ((8-7 - (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7482 &:= (-9 - (C(8) + (7 - ((C(6+5) + 4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7483 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((C(6+5) - C(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7484 &:= (((-9 + C(8)) \times (7+6)) + (C(5+4) + C(3+2+1))) \\
7485 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (7 \times C(6))) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7486 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - (7 + C(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
7487 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (((6 - C(5)) \times C(4)) - (3+2+1))) \\
7488 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (C(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7489 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (C(6) \times 5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7490 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7491 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) \times 6) \times (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7492 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7493 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (C(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7494 &:= 9 + ((C(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7495 &:= (-9 - (C(8) - ((C(7) \times (C(6)/(5+4))) - C(3+2+1)))) \\
7496 &:= (-9 + C(8) - (7 \times (6 - 5 - C(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7497 &:= (-9 \times (C(8) - (((7+6) \times C(5)) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))) \\
7498 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7499 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (((C(7) - C(6)) \times (5 - C(4))) - (3+2+1))) \\
7500 &:= ((-9 - (8+7+6)) \times (C(5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)))) \\
7501 &:= (-9 + ((8-7 + (6 \times C(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7502 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6^5)) - (C(4) + C(3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

